

THE INFLUENCE OF EXERCISE ON VASCULAR AND COGNITIVE FUNCTION IN HEALTHY AGEING

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ABSTRACT

This thesis aimed to investigate the influence of acute and chronic exercise on vascular and cognitive function in healthy older adults and to elucidate potential associations between vascular and cognitive health with ageing and exercise. The first study of this thesis consisted of a systematic review and meta-analysis which found that long-term endurance trained healthy older adults exhibit superior brachial artery flow mediated dilation (FMD) compared to sedentary cohorts (mean difference (MD): 2.1 %; $P < 0.001$). However, periods of short-term endurance training did not improve BA FMD (MD: 0.7%; $P = 0.316$). Conversely, in study 2, masters athletes did not exhibit superior brachial artery FMD (MD: -0.38 %; $P = 0.978$), carotid artery (CA) intima media thickness (MD: 0.006 mm; $P = 0.993$), or blood flow (common CA MD: -110.9 ml.min⁻¹; $P = 0.129$; internal CA MD: -65.7 ml.min⁻¹; $P = 0.502$) compared to older recreationally active adults. Additionally, the recreationally active group demonstrated better memory performance during one cognitive test (MD: 5.2 errors; $P = 0.003$). Minimal differences in vascular and cognitive function were also observed between the older and young control groups ($P < 0.05$). Study 3 focused specifically on the vascular and cognitive function of healthy middle-aged physically active and inactive females. Whilst no differences in brachial artery FMD were observed (MD: 0.4 %; $P = 0.762$), the active females demonstrated superior CA compliance when compared with their inactive counterparts (peak circumferential strain MD: 1.9 %; $P = 0.003$; peak strain rate MD: 0.133 s⁻¹; $P = 0.004$). However, the inactive group performed better in one test of executive function compared to the active females (animal fluency MD: 6 words; $P = 0.002$). Finally, 12 weeks of resistance training improved the information processing speed of the previously inactive middle-aged females during Study 4 (Trail A MD: 2 s; $P = 0.047$; Stroop 1 MD: 0.4 s; $P = 0.014$; Stroop 3 MD: 0.7 s; $P = 0.031$). CA compliance was improved at the $P < 0.05$ level when assessed during and immediately after physiological stress (peak circumferential strain MD: 0.7 %; $P = 0.012$). However, no

associations were observed between improved CA and cognitive function within the healthy middle-aged cohort at the $P < 0.05$ level. Overall, the findings from this thesis may suggest that long-term endurance and short-term resistance training may have selective benefits for arterial health with ageing, in which some benefits may only be observed when individuals are exposed to physiological stress. Moreover, cognitive function was positively influenced by short-term resistance, but not long-term endurance exercise. However, it appears that improvements in cognitive function from resistance exercise may not be mediated through simultaneous improvements in extra-cranial vascular function in healthy middle-aged females. Additional research is needed to further investigate potential links between vascular and cognitive function with exercise in ageing.

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‘Life need not be easy, provided only that it is not empty’

- Lise Meitner

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DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis has been composed by myself, and has not been submitted previously, whole or in part, towards any other academic degree. I confirm that this thesis contains original work which was conducted by myself. This thesis is being submitted for the partial fulfilment of the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy at the University of the West of Scotland.

Name: Amy Keenan Campbell

Signature

Personal details withheld.

Date: 25th May 2021

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

1RM	One repetition maximum	CV	Cardiovascular
AGE	Advanced glycated end product	CV	Coefficient of variation
ANCOVA	Analysis of covariance	CVC	Cerebrovascular conductance
ANOVA	Analysis of variance	CVD	Cardiovascular disease
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate	DBP	Diastolic blood pressure
AUC	Area under the curve	DiamDIAS	Diastolic diameter
β_1	Beta-stiffness 1	DiamSYS	Systolic diameter
BA	Brachial artery	DMS	Delayed Matching to Sample
BBB	Blood brain barrier	ECG	Electrocardiogram
BDNF	Brain derived neurotrophic factor	eNOS	Endothelial nitric oxide synthase
BMI	Body mass index	E_p	Petersons Elastic Modulus
BP	Blood pressure	FMD	Flow mediated dilation
B.min⁻¹	Beats per minute	HG	Handgrip
CA	carotid artery	HIT	High intensity training
CANTAB	Cambridge Automated Neuropsychological Automated Test Battery	HR	Heart rate
CBF	Cerebral blood flow	HR_{max}	Maximum heart rate
CCA	Common carotid artery	HRT	Hormone replacement therapy
CES-D	Centre for Epidemiological Studies Depression Scale	ICA	Internal carotid artery
CHD	Coronary heart disease	IGF-1	Insulin like growth factor 1
cm	Centimeters	IMT	Intima media thickness
CO₂	Carbon Dioxide	In	Natural logarithm
CRF	Cardiorespiratory fitness	Kg	Kilograms
CT	Continuous training	kPa	Kilopascal

LDL	Low-density lipoprotein	RCT	Randomised controlled trial
M	Meters	RER	Respiratory exchange ratio
M/F	Male/Female	ROI	Region of interest
MAP	Mean arterial pressure	ROS	Reactive oxygen species
MCA	Middle cerebral artery	RPE	Ratings of perceived exertion
MCAv	Middle cerebral artery velocity	Rpm	Revolutions per minute
MCI	Myocardial Infarction	RTI	Reaction Time
METS	Metabolic equivalents	RVP	Rapid Visual Processing
ml.min⁻¹	Millilitres per minute	SAX	Short axis
mm	Millimetres	SBP	Systolic blood pressure
mmHg	Millimetres of mercury	SD	Standard deviation
MMSE	Mini Mental State Examination	SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
MOT	Motor Screening Task	SWM	Spatial Working Memory
N₂	Nitrogen	TA mean	Time averaged mean
NO	Nitric oxide	UWS	University of the West of Scotland
NOS	Nitric oxide synthase	UWTSD	University of Wales Trinity St David
O₂	Oxygen	VA	Vertebral artery
PA	Physical activity	VCO₂	Carbon dioxide production
PAL	Paired Associated Learning	VE	Ventilation
PAR-Q	Physical activity readiness questionnaire	VEGF	Vascular endothelial growth factor
PCS	Peak circumferential strain	VO₂	Oxygen uptake
PP	Pulse Pressure	VO_{2max}	maximum aerobic capacity
PSR	Peak strain rate	VSMC	Vascular smooth muscle cells
PTT	Pulse transit time		
PWV	Pulse wave velocity		

WEMWBS Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale

WHO World Health Organisation

Δ FMD % Flow mediated dilation percentage change

CHAPTER 1

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

The global ageing population is expanding, where currently 9 % of the population, or 703 million individuals are aged 65 years and over (United Nations: Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2019). Moreover, these figures are projected to rise to 16 %, or 1.5 billion older adults by the year 2050 (United Nations: Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2019). Though increases in the ageing population are mediated by increases in life-expectancy (United Nations: Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2019), older adults are not necessarily living longer healthier lives due to increased susceptibility to ageing-associated health impairments and involvement in poor lifestyle choices including low levels of physical activity (PA) (Leveille et al., 1999; Office for National Statistics, 2019). As increasing age is a non-modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular disease (CVD) (Dhingra and Vasan, 2012) and increases the risk of cognitive decline (Lipnicki et al., 2013), cardiovascular disease (CVD) and conditions linked with cognitive impairment are prevalent within the ageing population (De Ronchi et al., 2005; World Health Organisation, 2009). Such conditions can gradually reduce an individual's functional independence, well-being, and quality of life as severity progresses (Bárrios et al., 2013; Taylor, 2014). Whilst pharmaceutical approaches are often used to improve age-associated impairments in health, engagement in lifestyle factors including PA and exercise are frequently encouraged in an attempt to help alleviate or delay the age-related decline in health and well-being.

Lifestyle factors including PA and exercise are widely known to improve aspects of health that are commonly affected by ageing, including physical functioning, cardiovascular health, and cognitive performance. For example, individuals who are physically active are at lower risk of CVD and dementia compared to those who are less active or sedentary (Hamer and Chida, 2009; Li and Siegrist, 2012). More specifically, healthy older individuals who participate in regular PA and exercise exhibit superior extracranial and intracranial vascular

function (Brown et al., 2010; Grace et al., 2015; Braz et al., 2017; Park et al., 2017b), and better cognitive performance (Tseng et al., 2013; Zhao et al., 2016) compared to age-matched sedentary cohorts. Moreover, short term endurance and resistance exercise have also been effective in improving various components of vascular (Figuroa et al., 2011; Williams et al., 2013; Fujie et al., 2014; Grace et al., 2015) and cognitive function (Cassilhas et al., 2007; Erickson et al., 2011; Ruscheweyh et al., 2011; Chapman et al., 2013; Antunes et al., 2015) in previously sedentary older individuals. In comparison to pharmaceutical approaches, the use of PA and exercise to improve health in ageing populations is cost-effective and can also positively influence other aspects of health and well-being including physical functioning and levels of depression (Loprinzi, 2013; Taylor, 2014). Therefore, the use of PA and exercise to manage or delay ageing associated vascular and cognitive impairments may provide a greater benefit to overall health and well-being compared to exclusively using pharmaceutical methods.

While there is a clear importance for encouraging participation within PA and exercise throughout life, not all mechanisms underlying exercise-induced improvements in vascular and cognitive function are fully understood. For example, it is unclear to what extent short and long-term endurance training may benefit endothelial function of the brachial artery in healthy older adults, as assessed by flow mediated dilation (FMD), as the results of existing studies are not consistent. Whilst systematic reviews and meta-analyses have concluded that endurance exercise improves FMD (Montero et al., 2014; Ashor et al., 2015; Early et al., 2017), no previous meta-analysis has included studies involving healthy cohorts greater than 60 years of age only. Investigating the effects of exercise on exclusively healthy older adults is important in order to assess the influence of exercise on ageing, rather than in combination with a variety

of health conditions which could disguise the true effect of exercise on aspects of health which are vulnerable to age-associated decline and impairment.

Additionally, although many studies have reported better cognitive performances in exercise-trained healthy older adults (Tseng et al., 2013; Zhao et al., 2016), less is known about the mechanisms responsible for facilitating improvements or differences in cognitive function observed. It has been speculated that better cognitive function seen in regular exercisers may be due to concurrent improvements in vascular function (Barnes and Corkery, 2018), however few studies have assessed both vascular and cognitive function within the same cohort. Those which exist have demonstrated associations between better intracranial vascular function and regional stiffness measurements with cognitive performance after long or short term endurance training (Brown et al., 2010; Chapman et al., 2013; Okamoto et al., 2019). However, no previous research has assessed the influence of long- and short-term endurance exercise training, or resistance exercise, on cognitive function and both, central and peripheral vascular function within healthy older cohorts.

Overall, whilst research exists to show that PA and exercise participation is important for vascular and cognitive function in older adults, less is known about the influence of exercise in healthy older adults only, and the mechanisms which facilitate improvements in cognitive functioning. Understanding the influence of exercise on ageing prior to the development of vascular or cognitive dysfunction would allow for a greater insight into the potential of exercise to delay or offset ageing-induced health impairments. Additionally, it is important to elucidate potential associations between vascular and neuropsychological variables to also help understand how to best delay detriment to health and well-being with ageing. Consequently, the purpose of this thesis was to investigate the influence of long and short-term exercise

training on vascular and cognitive function within healthy middle-aged and older adults, in addition to exploring the potential links between vascular and cognitive health with exercise.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter will focus on the available literature investigating the ageing process within the areas of endothelial, central vascular, and cognitive function. The main methods of assessment of each variable will be highlighted in each section, followed by existing research that has investigated the influence of physical activity (PA) and exercise to facilitate healthy ageing. Specifically, research investigating the possible link between vascular and cognitive function in healthy active ageing will be discussed. Following discussion of the main body of literature in the field, the main aims and hypotheses of the successive chapters will be listed in order of occurrence within the thesis.

2.2 Physical Activity and Exercise

2.2.1 Definitions

The terms PA and exercise are often used interchangeably, yet they possess distinct definitions. The World Health Organisation (WHO) and others define PA as *‘any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that requires energy expenditure’*, whereas exercise is defined as *‘a subcategory of physical activity that is planned, structured, repetitive, and purposeful in the sense that the improvement or maintenance of one or more components of physical fitness is the objective’* (Caspersen et al., 1985; World Health Organisation, 2020). Therefore, whilst exercise includes PA, exercise can be categorised into different domains depending on the type of activity which is performed. Broadly, exercise is most commonly categorised as endurance or resistance based.

Endurance exercise consists of activities that rely on the aerobic respiratory system to produce an adequate supply of adenosine triphosphate (ATP), or energy, to maintain performance. Endurance exercise includes activities such as middle and long-distance running, cycling, and swimming. Training of this particular mode of exercise increases the cardiovascular systems' ability to distribute a sufficient blood supply to active muscles and increasing the extraction of oxygen in order to maintain aerobic performance. Conversely, resistance training consists of repetitive exercises whereby skeletal muscles contract against an external resistance to improve muscular endurance and strength.

Exercise intensities are used as a measure of effort performed which is relative to different individuals based on their abilities. Although commonly understood when applying to aerobic-based exercise, measures of intensities are also used in resistance-based exercises. Various factors are measured during aerobic-based exercise to determine exercise intensities being performed, including the relative percentage of $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$, percentage of heart rate maximum (HR_{\max}) and HR reserve (HRR), metabolic equivalents (METS), and Borg's subjective Ratings of Perceived Exertion (Borg, 1970) (Figure 2 - 1). On the other hand, the percentage of the maximum weight an individual can use during a resistance exercise, also referred to as the percentage of one-repetition maximum (1RM), is used to determine intensity during resistance-based exercise.

Intensity category	Objective measures	Subjective measures	Descriptive measures
SEDENTARY	< 1.6 METs < 40% HR _{max} < 20% HRR < 20% VO _{2max}	RPE (C): < 8 RPE (C-R): < 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> activities that usually involve sitting or lying and that have little additional movement and a low energy requirement
LIGHT	1.6 < 3 METs 40 < 55% HR _{max} 20 < 40% HRR 20 < 40% VO _{2max}	RPE (C): 8-10 RPE (C-R): 1-2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> an aerobic activity that does not cause a noticeable change in breathing rate an intensity that can be sustained for at least 60 minutes
MODERATE	3 < 6 METs 55 < 70% HR _{max} 40 < 60% HRR 40 < 60% VO _{2max}	RPE (C): 11-13 RPE (C-R): 3-4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> an aerobic activity that is able to be conducted whilst maintaining a conversation uninterrupted an intensity that may last between 30 and 60 minutes
VIGOROUS	6 < 9 METs 70 < 90% HR _{max} 60 < 85% HRR 60 < 85% VO _{2max}	RPE (C): 14-16 RPE (C-R): 5-6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> an aerobic activity in which a conversation generally cannot be maintained uninterrupted an intensity that may last up to about 30 minutes
HIGH	≥ 9 METs ≥ 90% HR _{max} ≥ 85% HRR ≥ 85% VO _{2max}	RPE (C): ≥ 17 RPE (C-R): ≥ 7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> an intensity that generally cannot be sustained for longer than about 10 minutes

Figure 2 - 1. Categories of exercise intensity reported by (Norton et al., 2010). METs, metabolic equivalents; HR_{max}, maximum heart rate; HRR, heart rate reserve; VO_{2max}, maximum aerobic capacity; RPE, ratings of perceived exertion; C, category scale; C-R; category ratio scale.

2.2.2 Recommended Guidelines

PA and exercise guidelines for health have been advised firstly by the American College of Sports Medicine and Centres for Disease Control and Prevention in 1995 in an attempt to encourage participation in PA and exercise for promotion and maintenance of health (Pate et al., 1995). Since then, PA and exercise guidelines are frequently reviewed and updated

based on the latest research to support their benefits. Currently, the exercise guidelines for adults aged between 18 and 64 years are 150 min.week⁻¹ of moderate to vigorous aerobic activity, or 75 min.week⁻¹ of vigorous intensity aerobic activity, or a combination of both aerobic activities spread across a week. In addition, all adults should also perform moderate to high-intensity resistance-based muscle strengthening activities on two or more days of the week. The guidelines for adults aged greater than 65 years are the same, but also contain balance and flexibility exercises in addition to the strengthening recommendations (Chodzko-Zajko et al., 2009; Chodzko-Zajko, 2014; Chief Medical Officers, United Kingdom, 2019). Moreover, adults and older adults are also encouraged to reduce daily prolonged durations in sedentary positions, as also recommended by the UK Chief Medical Officers' PA Guidelines (2019). However, it should be noted that these represent the minimum PA and exercise guidelines for health and increasing activity above these recommendations will provide greater benefits to health (Chief Medical Officers, United Kingdom, 2019).

2.3 Peripheral Endothelial Function

2.3.1 Overview

The vascular system is a heterogeneous network of vessels that vary greatly in size, composition, and function throughout the vascular tree. Peripheral or muscular arteries originate from the larger central elastic arteries to provide a network of vessels towards the periphery. Compared to central elastic arteries, which contain a greater volume of elastin within the tunica media, peripheral/muscular arteries contain a greater proportion of vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMC) than elastin (Leloup et al., 2015). As such, peripheral arteries exhibit the ability to regulate vascular tone via vasodilation and vasoconstriction of the vessels when required (Leloup et al., 2015). Such mechanisms allow the peripheral vasculature to maintain homeostasis via coordinated vasomotor control throughout the arterial tree. Ultimately, vasomotor control of peripheral arteries is controlled by autonomic, endocrine, and autocrine factors (Edis and Shepherd, 1970; Chopra et al., 2011; Levine et al., 2012).

The arterial endothelium is largely involved in vasomotor control (Feletou et al., 2008). The endothelium consists of a single layer of endothelial cells that line the border of the intima-lumen interface (Tremblay and Pyke, 2019), and forms a selectively permeable barrier separating the extra- and intravascular environments (Cahill and Redmond, 2016). Whilst the endothelium plays an important role in a number of physiological processes including angiogenesis and immune function (Sturtzel, 2017), it is a highly important factor for the control of vascular tone. The endothelium is highly responsive to changes in intraluminal pressure via mechanotransduction of shear stress (Chatterjee and Fisher, 2014). Shear stress is the intraluminal haemodynamic pressures exerted parallel to endothelial walls (Paszkwowiak and Dardik, 2003), which increase as a result of conditions that cause transient increases in

cardiac output such as the commencement of exercise. An increased exposure of endothelial cells to shear stress induces the activation of the enzyme named endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) (Sriram et al., 2016) which is required for the oxidation of the substrate L-arginine (Forstermann and Sessa, 2012). Such processes allow for the production of the highly potent vasodilator nitric oxide (NO), which diffuses into the tunica media and binds to the heme-centred soluble guanylate cyclase receptor on VSMCs (Ignarro et al., 1982). NO causes phosphorylation of myosin to relax the VSMCs and therefore enabling vasodilation to occur (Sanders et al., 2000) (Figure 2 -2). Consequently, vasodilation of the artery normalises elevations in intraluminal flow, reducing shear stress, and establishing haemodynamic homeostasis. As the ability of the endothelium to respond to changes in intraluminal pressure are known to vary with ageing and disease, the evaluation of endothelial function has become an increasingly important avenue of both ageing and general health research.

Figure 2 - 2. Signalling cascade demonstrating the process of shear stress induced NO release from the vascular endothelium, resulting in the relaxation of VSMCs and thus, triggering vasodilation (Forte et al., 2016).

2.3.2 Peripheral Endothelial Function Measurement

Flow-mediated dilation (FMD) was firstly described by Celermajer et al. (1992), and is one of the most commonly used methods to measure endothelial vasodilatory capacity. This particular method uses high-resolution ultrasound to image muscular peripheral arteries such as the brachial or femoral arteries at rest and after a 5 minute period of occlusion of the artery. Firstly, a large diameter cuff is positioned either on the upper or lower arm and rapidly inflated to supra-systolic pressures in order to induce ischemia to the inferior region of the arm for a period of 5 minutes. Following the 5 minute period, the cuff is rapidly deflated, triggering

hyperaemia within the affected artery. Using ultrasound doppler and longitudinal imaging, blood flow and diameter of the artery can be imaged and tracked before inflation and for a set duration after the release of the occlusion to identify the maximum shear rate, and consequently, maximum dilation caused by endothelial response to a rapid increase in shear stress. Ultimately, FMD can be measured via a relative percentage increase in diameter from pre to post occlusion, with the higher the percentage indicating superior vasodilatory capacity. As the method is fast, relatively inexpensive and has high reproducibility when guidelines are followed (Greyling et al., 2016), it is one of the most commonly used non-invasive measures of peripheral vascular vasodilatory capacity or specifically, NO-mediated endothelial function.

Although guidelines for FMD measurement have been published to encourage greater levels of reproducibility (Thijssen et al., 2019), variations in methodology have been reported in earlier studies which have used FMD. Some have recommended that occlusion occurs distally to the ultrasound probe for 5 minutes for sufficient dilatory response to occur (Leeson et al., 1997), but also to minimise dilatory response from factors other than NO (Doshi et al., 2001; Green et al., 2011). Moreover, brachial artery diameter was originally measured manually during 4 cardiac cycles between 45 and 60s after cuff deflation and averaged (Celermajer et al., 1992). However, it has now been recommended that brachial artery diameters are continuously measured for 3 minutes or longer using an edge detection and wall tracking software (Black et al., 2008). Continuous post-occlusion measurements of brachial artery diameter increase the confidence that accurate measurements will be collected within individuals who display longer time to peak brachial artery diameter durations, such as older or unhealthy adults (Black et al., 2008; Fernandes et al., 2014).

2.3.2.1 Diagnosis

As the FMD method specifically assesses endothelial response to increased shear stress, it is recognised as an efficient determinant of endothelial vasodilatory capacity which can also be used to predict future cardiovascular (CV) risk. For example, a 2013 meta-analysis consisting of 23 studies and over 14,500 participants reported that individuals with smaller brachial artery FMD % at baseline demonstrated greater cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk upon follow-up periods of 12 months or longer (average of 42.9 months) (Ras et al., 2013). Furthermore, the association was stronger in individuals who were described by the authors as being ‘diseased’ at baseline, compared to those described as ‘asymptomatic’ (Ras et al., 2013). More specifically, an earlier meta-analysis by Inaba et al. (2010) reported that 1 % decreases in brachial artery FMD are linked with an increase in the risk of future cardiovascular events by 8 %. Therefore, this particular measure can be used to predict future events alongside the traditional CV risk factors such as hypertension, diabetes, and dyslipidaemia (Schenck-Gaustafsson, 2019). However, whilst the technique is useful for identifying endothelial dysfunction between individuals who do and who do not have CVD, it has been reported that it is not as sensitive at differentiating between endothelial vasodilatory capacity within individuals with different CVD severity (Yeboah et al., 2008).

2.3.2.2 Prognosis

Whilst FMD is impaired within individuals who exhibit CVD (Yeboah et al., 2008), reductions in FMD can also be assessed in individuals with no pre-existing medical conditions. As reductions in FMD occur before the onset of disease or vascular impairment, FMD has been shown to be effective at assessing endothelial vasodilatory capacity in asymptomatic individuals (Celermajer et al., 1994a). Consequently, it has been reported that an inverse

relationship exists between lower FMD with increased CV risk factors including age, sex, body mass index (BMI), and levels of C-reactive protein (Zhong et al., 2018). The FMD method therefore exhibits the sensitivity to detect declines in endothelial vasodilatory capacity prior to the advancement of debilitating diseases. The early detection of endothelial decline via FMD therefore allows for the commencement of lifestyle or pharmaceutical interventions to reduce further impairment and progression of vascular disease. Thus, FMD is a commonly used method for assessing the endothelial function of peripheral muscular arteries in individuals with and without pre-existing health conditions.

2.3.3 Peripheral Endothelial Function and Ageing

Since its development as a research tool in 1992, FMD has been used widely as a simple, non-invasive, and relatively cost-effective technique to assess endothelial vasodilatory capacity (Celermajer et al., 1992). Consequently, studies using this particular technique have frequently examined the effects of different factors such as age, sex, and disease on endothelial vasodilatory capacity. For example, observational studies containing thousands of participants of ages spanning from the second to the 8th decade have demonstrated declines in FMD with advancing age (Benjamin et al., 2004; Skaug et al., 2013). Such results have been seen regardless of whether participants were healthy or affected by conditions such as hypertension, diabetes, and coronary artery disease (Benjamin et al., 2004; Skaug et al., 2013). Moreover, a number of cross-sectional studies assessing FMD in healthy young versus older non-exercise trained adults have reported similar results, whereby the older individuals exhibit smaller FMD values compared to their young counterparts (Eskurza et al., 2005; Franzoni et al., 2005; Yavuz et al., 2008; Black et al., 2009; Walker et al., 2009; Pierce et al., 2011a; DeVan et al., 2013; Brislane et al., 2020).

A number of studies have focused on the differences in endothelial impairment with age between males and females. One of the first reports to investigate endothelial sex differences in ageing was by Celermajer et al. (1994b) who reported that males experience a decline in FMD from the fourth decade, whereas declines were not evident in females until menopause which was reported to occur at an average age of 51 years. Notably, the decline in FMD per year after menopause was over double that experienced by men (0.48 % and 0.21 %, respectively). A strength of this particular study was that only healthy participants with no known health conditions or those not using medication were recruited for the study, thus reducing the effect of any confounding factors which may have influenced FMD. Skaug et al. (2013) also used an observational approach to investigate whether sex influences differences in FMD in healthy ageing. It was reported that males exhibited steady declines in FMD from the third decade onwards, whereas females demonstrated large declines from the 4th decade, and despite having greater FMD than males until the 7th decade, females have consistently experienced steeper declines per decade from middle age onwards (Figure 2 - 3) (Benjamin et al., 2004; Skaug et al., 2013).

However, Jensen-Urstad and Johansson (2001) reported similar FMD levels between middle-aged males and females. Interestingly, the same study also did not find any association between FMD and CV risk score or age in young and older males, even within a sub-analysis which removed individuals taking medications. Such findings contrast with a large study which demonstrated correlations between FMD and the Framingham risk score (Benjamin et al., 2004), which uses an algorithm to calculate 10 year CV risk based on traditional CV risk factors including hypertension, diabetes, and smoking status (Wilson et al., 1998; Mahmood et

al., 2014). The disparity between Jensen-Urstad and Johansson (2001) and the larger Framingham Heart Study (Benjamin et al., 2004) may be due to several reasons. For example, Jensen-Urstad and Johansson (2001) studied a much smaller sample of participants ($n = 212$) in comparison to the Framingham Heart Study which sampled 2883 participants. Moreover, as Jensen-Urstad and Johansson (2001) only recorded FMD data for 50 – 70 s after cuff deflation, FMD may have also been underestimated as it has been reported that peak FMD diameter occurs later in females compared to males (Evanoff et al., 2016). As post-occlusion FMD data were collected for 2 minutes in the Framingham Heart Study, the FMD results reported by Benjamin et al. (2004) may better represent the influence of ageing and CV risk factors on endothelial vasodilatory capacity.

Time to peak brachial artery diameter during reactive hyperaemia has also been reported in the literature, although not as often as FMD itself. Although not as widely used as FMD, it is believed that increases in time to peak brachial artery diameter with age and disease may demonstrate reduced enzyme rates responsible for vasodilation and may also represent increases in arterial stiffness with advancing age (Black et al., 2008). However, the importance of time to peak brachial artery diameter is less clear since some studies report longer times in older and unhealthy individuals compared to younger participants (Black et al., 2008; Brislane et al., 2020), or healthy individuals (Fernandes et al., 2014). Conversely, others have not reported such differences (Thijssen et al., 2009a; Liuni et al., 2010). Although it has been suggested that delays in peak brachial artery diameter may be due to reduced compliance from ageing-associated adaptations of the endothelium (Black et al., 2008), time to peak FMD has been shown to be highly heterogeneous even within the same cohort (Liuni et al., 2010). Moreover, evidence for the lack of differences between healthy and diseased individuals (Donald et al., 2008; Liuni et al., 2010), and a lack of association between the Framingham risk

score (Chironi et al., 2008) suggests that, unlike FMD %, time to peak FMD may not be a sensitive measure of endothelial function.

Figure 2 - 3. Demonstration of the decline in percentage of brachial artery flow-mediated dilation in males (squares) and females (circles) with advancing age (Benjamin et al., 2004). Data presented as means and standard errors. $P < 0.0001$ represents higher flow-mediated dilation in females at the $P \leq 0.05$ level compared to males until 70 years of age.

2.3.4 Ageing Mechanisms of Peripheral Endothelial Function

The age-related decline in FMD, observed in both cross-sectional and longitudinal studies, is believed to occur due to a number of age-associated mechanisms. One mechanism includes increases in peptides named endothelin-1; a potent vasoconstrictor that contributes to increases in arterial tone (Van Guilder et al., 2007). In addition to increases in arterial tone, ageing has been shown to reduce endothelial NO bioavailability as a result of declines in NO production and increased degradation of bioavailable NO. For example, the ageing process is linked with reductions in expression and activity of the enzyme eNOS, which is responsible

for the synthesis of NO (Chou et al., 1998; Smith et al., 2006; Cau et al., 2012). Consequently, lower levels of NO are synthesised as a result (Smith et al., 2006) which negatively affect NO-mediated endothelial function, and therefore cause reductions in FMD values. In addition, ageing associated declines in NO production have also been attributed to increases in oxidative stress due to increased production of mitochondrial by-products such as reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Kuka et al., 2014). Healthy older adults have exhibited improvements in FMD after intravenous infusion of ascorbic acid, which is known to reduce oxidative stress by functioning as an antioxidant electron donor (Padayatty et al., 2003). However, increases in oxidative stress have been shown to reduce NO by oxidising cofactors required for eNOS, such as tetrahydrobiopterin (Landmesser et al., 2003). Such processes cause eNOS to uncouple, thus reducing the production of NO and contributing to further increases in ROS (Landmesser et al., 2003). The ageing process also causes increased inflammation and senescence of endothelial cells in healthy older adults which has been associated with impaired FMD (Rossman et al., 2017). There is evidence that such processes are due to DNA damage, telomere shortening, and oxidative stress (Vasa et al., 2000; Muñoz-Espín and Serrano, 2014). Furthermore, a pro-inflammatory endothelial environment is also experienced during ageing which can alter the function of the endothelium as a result, including the downregulation of eNOS, and increased apoptosis (Csiszar et al., 2003, 2004; Herrera et al., 2010). Consequently, age-associated increases in vasoconstrictors, increases in ROS, and inflammation within the vasculature all contribute to the promotion of vascular damage. Endothelium-dependent vasodilation therefore becomes impaired partly due to ageing-associated endothelial impairment from reductions in NO bioavailability.

Reductions in the vasodilatory capacity impairs the ability of artery to alleviate increases in intraluminal pressure, such as increased shear stress. Such events contribute to

elevations in blood pressure (BP) and may ultimately lead to hypertension if unresolved. Increases in intraluminal pressures experienced by the arterial walls is associated with increases in intima-media thickness (IMT) within brachial artery (Iwamoto et al., 2012). Moreover, augmented intraluminal pressures and consequently, endothelial damage, triggers the upregulation of inflammatory processes (Ungvari et al., 2004). Subsequently, increases in inflammatory cells and processes including foam cell formation and arterial remodelling contribute to the formation of plaques the development of vascular diseases, such as atherosclerosis (Bentzon et al., 2014).

As mentioned earlier, it has been reported that females have preserved FMD with ageing, which occurs until menopause. Such differences occur between the sexes as oestrogen has a protective effect on the endothelium. Oestrogen (E2) has cardioprotective properties as a result of improving mitochondrial function, which reduces ROS concentrations, and increases antioxidant production through enhanced antioxidant synthesis (Iorga et al., 2017). Furthermore, the binding of E2 to receptors within the endothelium upregulates NO production from an increased transcription of eNOS (Iorga et al., 2017). Thus, females exhibit beneficial effects from the presence of oestrogen throughout adulthood which dissipate upon the onset of menopause and the subsequent decline in oestrogen levels.

2.3.5 Long-Term Endurance Exercise and Peripheral Endothelial Function

While some vascular impairment is unavoidable with advancing age, approaches which reduce the rate at which vascular damage accumulates will in turn reduce the risk of disease development. PA and exercise are two non-pharmacological approaches that have been shown to improve vascular health (Ashor et al., 2015; Early et al., 2017).

Most cross-sectional studies state that endothelial function assessed via FMD is superior in exercisers, compared to untrained healthy adults aged 60 years and over. Rywik et al. (1999) firstly recognised that endurance trained healthy adults aged 70 ± 5 years had superior FMD compared to sedentary participants aged 71 ± 5 years (8.9 ± 4.2 % vs 5.7 ± 3.5 %, respectively). Since 1999, a number of cross-sectional studies have been published which all documented that their competitive masters endurance athletes also exhibited better FMD at the $P < 0.05$ level compared to untrained adults of a similar age (Jensen-Urstad et al., 1999; Rinder et al., 2000; Eskurza et al., 2005; Franzoni et al., 2005; Galetta et al., 2006; Pierce et al., 2011a, 2011b; DeVan et al., 2013). Similarly, Grace et al. (2015) most recently reported that life-long exercisers had greater FMD compared to life-long sedentary healthy adults, together with a mean age of 61 ± 5 years (5.4 ± 1.4 % vs 3.4 ± 1.5 %, respectively). However, although the cross-sectional studies within the literature shared similarities such as including healthy participants aged 60 years and over and assessing endothelial function using the FMD method, differences between the studies were also observed.

Within many cross-sectional studies, ‘trained’ participants were described to partake in regular endurance exercise by some for a minimum of 2 years (Eskurza et al., 2005; DeVan et al., 2013), and by others for at least 5 years (Rywik et al., 1999; Pierce et al., 2011a, 2011b). Conversely, the trained participants recruited by Jensen-Urstad et al. (1999), Franzoni et al. (2005), and Grace et al. (2015) were described as ‘life-long’ exercisers, as they had exercised consistently for greater than 30 years. Again, all trained participants had superior FMD compared to their sedentary counterparts, where FMD ranged from 5.9 % to 6.4 % in those training for at least 2 years (Eskurza et al., 2005; DeVan et al., 2013), and from 4.8 % to 5.4 %

in individuals who had been training for greater than 30 years (Jensen-Urstad et al., 1999; Franzoni et al., 2005; Grace et al., 2015). These findings suggest that endurance exercise training can be effective at reducing the age-related decline in FMD regardless of whether individuals had trained for as little as 2 years or were life-long exercisers. The superior FMD in the trained participants may have occurred from an increased NO bioavailability in response to exercise over time, increasing vasodilation (Goto et al., 2003). However, it must be noted that the oldest group of masters athletes were aged 75 ± 3 years (Jensen-Urstad et al., 1999), whereas the oldest group of individuals who had trained for at least 2 years were 66 ± 4 years old (Eskurza et al., 2005). As FMD is negatively affected by age, the slightly lower FMD % reported in the masters athletes could be due to older age. Overall, these data suggest that FMD deteriorates with increasing age, however active individuals may offset the progression of vascular dysfunction.

$\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ values were also used by researchers to separate participants into trained and sedentary groups within the cross-sectional studies. Franzoni et al. (2005) recruited participants based on their $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ values measuring greater than $50 \text{ ml.kg.min}^{-1}$ in the trained, and less than $45 \text{ ml.kg.min}^{-1}$ in the untrained groups. Similarly, Galetta et al. (2006) also recruited participants based on $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ data, but with those who had values greater than $40 \text{ ml.kg.min}^{-1}$ in the trained and less than $35 \text{ ml.kg.min}^{-1}$ in the untrained category. Despite these particular cut-off values being used to distinguish between trained and untrained groups in the two studies identified, many of the participants recruited by Galetta et al. (2006) would have been identified as 'untrained' if recruited within the Franzoni et al. (2005) study. Moreover, the trained participants from the cross-sectional studies discussed previously would have also been categorised as 'untrained' participants within the Franzoni et al. (2005) study, as their mean $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ values were also less than $45 \text{ ml.kg.min}^{-1}$ (Jensen-Urstad et al., 1999; Rywik et

al., 1999; Rinder et al., 2000; Eskurza et al., 2005; Pierce et al., 2011a, 2011b; DeVan et al., 2013; Grace et al., 2015). However, despite the inconsistencies between the studies, the trained groups all had greater $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ and FMD % compared to their respective sedentary groups.

Conversely, Walker et al. (2009) did not detect any differences in FMD between trained and untrained healthy adults aged 60 years and over. The 16 trained individuals were reported to participate in three or more sessions of vigorous aerobic endurance exercise per week, whereas the 15 sedentary individuals participated in no regular exercise for two years. Although the reported FMD was 6.2 % for the trained and 4.8 % for the sedentary participants, the difference between the two was not different at the $P < 0.05$ level. Despite no difference, similar FMD values have been measured by comparable cross-sectional studies by Pierce et al. (2011a, 2011b), identifying that FMD was higher at the $P < 0.05$ level in the trained compared to the untrained participants. However, sample sizes within two studies by Pierce et al. (2011a, 2011b) were greater than within the Walker et al. (2009) study, and therefore could have explained why significance failed to occur between participant groups. However, Walker et al. (2009) stated that increasing participant number would not have altered the results as the minimum number of participants required to detect meaningful differences had been included.

2.3.6 Short-Term Endurance Training and Peripheral Endothelial Function

Since several studies have demonstrated greater FMD in trained older participants, many studies have investigated the effectiveness of interventions using aerobic exercise training programmes on FMD %. However, there are discrepancies within the literature regarding whether an exercise intervention can improve FMD in previously sedentary or untrained healthy adults aged 60 years and over. FMD prior to the exercise interventions varied

considerably between studies (1 to 10 %), as did measures recorded post intervention (5 to 16 %). Those which did report an improvement at the $P < 0.05$ level include studies by Wray et al. (2006), Grace et al. (2015), and Landers-Ramos et al. (2016), who used moderate and high-intensity exercise protocols. It is therefore possible that exercise intensity may have an impact on the extent of improvement which occurred in vascular health.

2.3.6.1 Light Intensity

Firstly, a randomised controlled trial (RCT) by Suboc et al. (2014) measured FMD before and after a walking intervention at mainly a low intensity. A ‘pedometer only’ intervention group consisting of 36 healthy older male and female participants were asked to increase their PA levels by 10 % over 12 weeks to reach a daily target of 10,000 steps. Although participants increased their mean step count from 5136 ± 1554 to 9596 ± 3907 steps over the 12 week intervention, FMD failed to improve post-intervention at the $P < 0.05$ level compared to the control group of 41 participants (6.7 ± 3.9 % and 6.3 ± 2.7 %, respectively). Suboc et al. (2014) also reported improvements in FMD in a separate intervention group when moderate to vigorous PA was performed for 20 minutes or more per day. However as less than half of the participants within the ‘pedometer only’ group exercised for 20 minutes or more per day, overall FMD within the group did not improve.

2.3.6.2 Moderate to Higher Intensity

Landers-Ramos et al. (2016) measured the effectiveness of a treadmill intervention prescribed at approximately 70 % $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$. Eleven male and female participants aged 61 ± 7 years completed the intervention for 1 hour daily over 10 consecutive days. The authors

reported that mean FMD increased from $10 \pm 4.3 \%$ to $16 \pm 4.6 \%$ over the short-term intervention. The data reported suggest that moderate to higher intensity exercise may have greater benefits for vascular health as FMD improved after only 10 consecutive days, whereas the lighter intensity intervention carried out by Suboc et al. (2014) failed to improve FMD after 84 consecutive days.

Wray et al. (2006) also reported an improvement in FMD from $1 \pm 2.5 \%$ to $5 \pm 2.5 \%$ after a 6 week single-leg knee extensor aerobic training intervention. The six male participants aged 71 ± 5 years completed short higher intensity (70 to 95 % maximum work rate (WR_{max})) and longer lower intensity (40 % to 65 % WR_{max}) exercise over a 1 hour period, three days per week. However, an 8 week cycling intervention performed at 65 % to 85 % heart rate reserve failed to improve FMD % in eight men aged 70 ± 1 years (Thijssen et al., 2007). In contrast with Landers-Ramos et al. (2016) and Wray et al. (2006), the participants in the Thijssen et al. (2007) study exercised for only 20 minutes, but also on 3 days per week. Thus, although moderate intensity interventions have reported improvements in FMD, the results from Thijssen et al. (2007) and Suboc et al. (2014) may suggest that training load may also have to be high for improvements in FMD to occur (Thijssen et al., 2007; Suboc et al., 2014).

However, although there was no improvement in FMD, pre intervention FMD levels was reported as $6.9 \pm 3.4 \%$ by Thijssen et al. (2007), whilst Suboc et al. (2014) reported control group FMD values as $6.3 \pm 2.7 \%$. These results may help to explain the lack of improvement in FMD after endurance training as both, pre-intervention and control values were higher than post-intervention FMD levels reported by Wray et al. (2006). Such results may suggest that higher baseline FMD values could provide less room for improvement from endurance-based

exercise training. However, it is also possible that Wray et al. (2006) may have been reporting vasodilatory response which was not exclusively due to endothelial-derived NO as a result of using an upper arm occlusion method of FMD (Doshi et al., 2001). Furthermore, whilst potential limitations of the studies include very small sample sizes ($n < 10$) (Wray et al., 2006; Thijssen et al., 2007), both studies reported that an adequate number of participants were included to achieve statistical power of at least 80 %. Nonetheless, future studies within this area should increase the number of participants sampled in order to further increase confidence in the results reported.

2.3.6.3 High Intensity

The effectiveness of high intensity exercise training on FMD has also been examined. Klonizakis et al. (2014) investigated whether 2 weeks of high intensity training (HIT) or continuous training (CT) interventions could improve FMD in 18 female healthy older adults with a mean age of 64 years. Relative exercise intensities for participants were determined from peak power values recorded during an earlier incremental cycling test. The HIT intervention consisting of thrice weekly 10 x 1 minute cycling intervals at 100 % peak power output failed to improve FMD as surprisingly, post interventional FMD decreased by 1.6 %. Likewise, the CT intervention consisting of 40 minutes of cycling at 65 % of peak power output 3 times per week also reduced FMD levels by 1.9 % compared to pre-intervention measures. Nonetheless, despite no improvement in FMD, pre-intervention mean FMD was reported as 8.1 ± 7.2 % and 8.9 ± 7.9 % in the HIT and CT groups, respectively and was higher than most post-intervention FMD values reported in the studies previously discussed (Wray et al., 2006; Thijssen et al., 2007; Suboc et al., 2014). Therefore, there may not have been great scope for improvement as FMD was already high prior to the intervention. Additionally, all 18

participants were postmenopausal and not receiving hormone therapy. Therefore, it is possible that a lack of improvement in FMD after exercise training may have been due to a lack of oestrogen, as similar results have been identified previously (Moreau et al., 2013).

However, Grace et al. (2015) found an improvement in FMD by 2 % in 22 healthy older men after performing 6 weeks of moderate-intensity conditioning training to the American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM) guidelines before completing a further 6 weeks of high-intensity interval training (HIIT). The HIIT consisted of 6 x 30 second sprints separated by 3 minute breaks, occurring once every 5 days, and was reported to maintain the prior increases in FMD achieved through moderate-intensity conditioning. It therefore appears that aerobic exercise training programmes can also be effective at improving FMD in a relatively short time frame, and low frequency HIIT based training may help to prolong such benefits . However, a greater number of high-quality studies, such as RCTs with larger sample sizes may be required before a definitive conclusion can be made on whether different types of exercise interventions are effective at improving FMD and thus, endothelial function.

2.3.7 Short-Term Resistance Training and Peripheral Endothelial Function

In comparison to endurance-based exercise, less research has investigated the effects of resistance exercise on FMD levels of healthy, unmedicated middle-aged and older adults. A 2007 study reported that despite improvements in strength performance of various muscle groups, a twice-weekly moderate to high-intensity resistance intervention over 18 weeks failed to alter brachial artery FMD levels in healthy and non-medicated postmenopausal females (59 ± 5 years) (Casey et al., 2007). Yet recently, thrice-weekly resistance training at 40 to 65 % 1RM over 8 weeks increased plasma NO levels in a group of 24 healthy and previously non-

resistance trained postmenopausal females (67 ± 6 years) (Ardakani et al., 2018). Although Ardakani et al. (2018) did not measure FMD levels, the increase in NO at the observed could identify that FMD may have been improved as a result of the 8 week intervention. However, regardless of differences between resistance interventions and the mean age of participants between the two studies, it cannot be certain how the results of these two studies compare as each measured different outcome variables.

Conversely, a number of studies have reported improvements at the $P < 0.05$ level (McGowan et al., 2006a; Dobrosielski et al., 2009; Vona et al., 2009; Stensvold et al., 2010) or no changes (McDermott et al., 2009; Kwon et al., 2011) in FMD after resistance training within middle-aged and older adults, albeit in individuals who report having medical conditions including type 2 diabetes, hypertension, peripheral artery disease, previous myocardial infarction, hypertension and metabolic syndrome. Moreover, although a number of the studies reported a mixed-sex sample, the majority of participants have consisted of male participants. Furthermore, a large amount of heterogeneity exists between resistance training studies due to the variety of resistance exercises, frequency of training, intensities, and duration of interventions completed. Whilst existing evidence suggests that resistance training can improve FMD in older adults with comorbidities, these data do not necessarily suggest that older adults without serious health conditions will experience the same benefits of resistance training. Thus, in order to gain an understanding into the influence of resistance exercise on FMD levels in healthy ageing exclusively, it is important to assess individuals who are free from CV illnesses and are not receiving medication which could augment or hinder the potential sole effects of resistance exercise.

2.3.8 Peripheral Endothelial Function Exercise Mechanisms

While the underpinning mechanism regarding the effects exercise has on FMD responses remains to be fully elucidated, some suggested mechanisms have been proposed. Firstly, transient elevations in blood flow which occur during exercise or PA increases the exposure of the endothelium to shear stress. For example, Tinken et al. (2010) reported improvements in brachial artery FMD after 8 weeks of handgrip training in young healthy males. However, improvements in FMD were only evident in non-cuffed arms of participants which were exposed to increases in shear stress (Tinken et al., 2010). Whilst these findings demonstrate the local improvement of FMD and thus, endothelial function of the exercising limb, different reports have demonstrated systemic improvements in endothelial function as brachial artery FMD was also improved in the non-cuffed arm after an 8 week cycling intervention which had no physical involvement of the upper limbs (Birk et al., 2012). Importantly, it has been reported that increases in antegrade shear stress are responsible for improvements in FMD, whereas retrograde stress decreases FMD (Green, 2009; Thijssen et al., 2009b; Tinken et al., 2009). Nonetheless, repetitive dynamic exercises such as cycling and walking are known to increase both, antegrade and retrograde shear stress and may still improve FMD (Green, 2009).

Repeated elevations in shear stress following an exercise intervention have been shown to improve FMD likely due to increased production of NO (Figure 2 - 4) (Tinken et al., 2010). Such increases are likely to be due to elevations in shear-induced NOS enzyme activity from elevated mRNA and protein expression, as demonstrated in rat aortas (Nadaud et al., 1996). Such adaptations counteract endothelial impairment caused by ageing by increasing bioavailability of NO and therefore enabling greater ranges of vasodilation to occur.

Additionally, short and long-term exercise has been shown to increase or preserve antioxidant activity in young and older adults, respectively (Miyazaki et al., 2001; Bouzid et al., 2018), likely due to physiological adaptations resulting in the upregulation of antioxidant capacity (Gomes et al., 2012). Moreover, healthy older athletes have demonstrated superior FMD and less oxidative stress compared to their sedentary counterparts, which was believed to be due to the exercise-mediated preservation of NO availability (Taddei et al., 2000). Additionally, frequent participation in PA and exercise has been linked with anti-inflammatory adaptations, such as lower levels of inflammatory biomarkers, including C-reactive protein (Abramson and Vaccarino, 2002; Plaisance and Grandjean, 2006). As C-reactive protein is known to contribute to endothelial dysfunction by reducing eNOS expression (Venugopal et al., 2002), reductions in such proteins will augment eNOS and consequently NO synthesis to reduce endothelial dysfunction.

Whilst increases in shear stress are reported to increase FMD through endothelial-dependent increases in NO, some studies which have assessed FMD throughout exercise interventions have initially reported increases in FMD before returning to values similar to baseline (Tinken et al., 2008, 2010). Reasons for which are postulated to be attributable to structural adaptations within the vasculature which occur to normalise repeated increases in shear stress (Figure 2 - 4) (Laughlin, 1995; Green et al., 2012). Such adaptations are commonly referred to as the 'Athlete's Artery' theory whereby some believe that exercise training causes remodelling of the lumen in order to increase diameter and decrease IMT (Figure 2 - 5) (Thijssen et al., 2012; Green et al., 2013). As baseline diameter is known to influence peak FMD (Thijssen et al., 2008; Green et al., 2013; Atkinson, 2014; Atkinson and Batterham, 2015), FMD and consequently, endothelial function can appear lower after exercise training or in long-term exercise trained individuals. Thus, studies that only report pre and post-

intervention FMD may miss out on identifying improvements before structural adaptations occur. However, such adaptations do not always occur as higher FMD and similar baseline brachial artery diameters have been reported in healthy older adults who were long-term exercise compared to their sedentary counterparts (Campbell et al., 2019).

Figure 2 - 4. Time course of functional (vasodilation; grey line) and structural (diameter; red line) adaptations to exercise training (adapted from Green et al. (2017)). NO; nitric oxide.

Figure 2 - 5. Vascular adaptations to exercise and exposure to cardiovascular disease risk factors, including ageing and physical inactivity (Thijssen et al., 2012). CVD; cardiovascular disease, NO; nitric oxide.

2.4 Central Vascular Structure and Function

2.4.1 Overview

In comparison to the peripheral vascular system, the central vasculature exhibits larger diameters and arterial IMT due to the greater composition of elastin tissue compared to smooth muscle (Martini et al., 2012). Moreover, the tunica-adventitia of large central arteries contain elastic lamellae and collagen fibres which are required to maintain the structural integrity of the artery during phases of fluctuating intraluminal pressures (Wagenseil and Mecham, 2009; Martini et al., 2012). The large central elastic arteries can therefore expand while also withstanding large arterial pressures as a result of having structurally stable arterial walls. The intrinsic properties of the arterial walls enable the arteries to expand during large intra-luminal pressures experienced during systole (Chan et al., 2011), therefore avoiding damage that would occur if the walls were not as compliant. During systole, potential energy is stored within the arterial walls which when released during diastole causes a rapid recoil of the arterial walls and the projection of blood throughout the remainder of diastole (Safar and Struijker-Boudier, 2010). In addition to ensuring a steady flow of blood throughout the cardiac cycle, a highly compliant central artery acts to buffer high pulsatile blood flow via the Windkessel effect (Safar and Struijker-Boudier, 2010).

2.4.2 Central Vascular Structure and Function Measurement

Assessment of central arterial structure, compliance, and stiffness is commonly measured via high-resolution ultrasound, in which a number of measures have been widely shown to be highly valid and reliable within a range of individuals. For example, the ultrasound assessment of IMT is widely used to measure the extent of intimal and medial thickening

through age and disease, whereby it can determine cardiovascular risk as a result of being positively associated with conditions including coronary heart disease (CHD), myocardial infarction (MCI), and stroke (O’Leary et al., 1999; Kablak-Ziembicka, 2004). In addition to arterial IMT, local arterial stiffness is also commonly measured via a number of different separate measures, most commonly including beta-stiffness index (β_1) and Peterson’s Elastic Modulus (E_p). Such measures also require the collection of carotid blood pressures as well as ultrasound in order to relate changes in carotid diameter to pressure changes during systole and diastole. In addition to measures of local arterial stiffness, regional arterial stiffness can also be measured non-invasively via pulse wave velocity (PWV) which calculates stiffness based on the pulse transit time around specific regions of the arterial tree (Hamilton et al., 2007). PWV is currently recognised as the gold standard approach for assessing arterial stiffness as a large volume of data has supported its use for assessing and predicting cardiovascular events (Laurent et al., 2006). However, although PWV is recognised as the gold standard assessment of arterial stiffness, it cannot provide information regarding local arterial stiffness of particular arteries of interest. Furthermore, the commonly used conventional measures of arterial stiffness present some limitations as they only provide a 1-dimensional approach of assessing arterial mechanics, and do not assess properties of the elastic artery throughout its circumference (Bjallmark et al., 2010).

An alternative method of assessing arterial stiffness and compliance include the novel ultrasound method named speckle tracking. Speckle tracking technology was originally developed for echocardiography (Leitman et al., 2004; Reisner et al., 2004), and has since been introduced into central arterial assessment of the aorta and carotid arteries (Oishi et al., 2008; Bjallmark et al., 2010; Yuda et al., 2011). The technique uses specialised software which tracks ultrasound speckles, which occur when the ultrasound beam becomes scattered by the arteries

imaged (Figure 2.6). When the speckles are tracked frame by frame, measurements including circumferential strain (percentage change in size) and strain rate (rate of change) can be calculated by the software (Bansal and Kasliwal, 2013). The technique therefore has the ability to follow the movement of the full circumference of an arterial wall throughout systole and diastole to gain more information than conventional methods as to how each section of the artery expands and recoils. Additionally, the technique does not only assess the percentage of arterial expansion (peak circumferential strain; PCS), but also the rate of change during an expansion (peak strain rate; PSR) and recoil, which cannot be evaluated using conventional methods such as β_1 and E_p . Moreover, the technique can also provide an estimate of pulse transit time, which provides regional in addition to local arterial stiffness data (Sculthorpe et al., 2020). Although speckle tracking is not as widely used as other conventional measures, studies have reported excellent inter and intra-investigator reliability (Figure 2 - 7) (Yuda et al., 2011), in addition to associations with CV risk as assessed by the Framingham Risk score (Park et al., 2012).

Figure 2 - 6. Demonstration of ultrasound speckles which are tracked and followed frame by frame throughout a cardiac cycle to determine the movement of myocardial tissue (as pictured) (Bansal and Kasliwal, 2013) and more recently, the arterial wall.

Figure 2 - 7. The intra-observer (left) and inter-observer (right) variability of common carotid artery peak circumferential strain as assessed by ultrasound speckle tracking (Yuda et al., 2011).

Central arterial blood flow is also commonly assessed via high-resolution ultrasound Doppler use. Whilst many studies often report peak systolic and end diastolic blood velocity, particularly in arteries where it is not possible to measure diameter, others report blood flow volume. Such measurements within central arteries including the carotids and vertebral arteries can provide information regarding cerebral blood flow (CBF), as internal carotid artery (ICA) flow has previously been reported to correlate well with CBF (Soustiel et al., 2003).

2.4.3 Ageing Mechanisms of Central Vascular Structure and Function

A number of structural and functional adaptations occur within the central vascular system as a result of the ageing process. Although adaptations are known to occur gradually across the life span, further adaptations can occur due to non-modifiable and modifiable risk factors including family history and lifestyle habits including diet and PA levels, respectively. Arterial stiffness of the large elastic conduit arteries increases with advancing age, as demonstrated regionally via PWV (The Reference Values for Arterial Stiffness' Collaboration,

2010), or locally by conventional methods such as β_1 and E_p (Bjallmark et al., 2010). Whilst β_1 and E_p are commonly used, it has been reported that they are less sensitive at detecting differences in carotid stiffness with age compared to the novel method of speckle tracking. For example, Bjallmark et al. (2010) reported lower peak circumferential strain and early strain rate by 3 % and 0.5 s^{-1} , respectively in older compared to younger participants, whilst also reporting that inter and intra-observer validity of speckle tracking was superior to conventional measures β_1 and E_p . Speckle tracking has also been shown to have better reproducibility than conventional methods, thus making it a useful method for assessment of vascular compliance across the age span (Yuda et al., 2011). Consequently, it has been reported that speckle tracking techniques are highly feasible and may be superior to conventional measures of arterial stiffness (Bjallmark et al., 2010; Yuda et al., 2011; Park et al., 2012).

Age associated adaptations within central arteries are caused by a number of factors that cause structural and functional adaptations over time. Elevations in blood pressure and consequently, pulse pressure (PP), are known to cause arterial remodelling as a result of the fatiguing effect of cyclic strain on the arterial walls which initiate a cascade of detrimental vascular phenotypic modifications (Laurent et al., 2001). For example, long-term exposure to cyclic pressures damages arterial walls and augment the expression of genes within arterial walls including the synthesis of collagen and VSMC (Leung et al., 1976; Reusch et al., 1996). Similarly, cyclic stress also increases the presence of collagen fibres within the adventitia including collagen I and II, which have been reported in carotids of aged animal models (Fleenor et al., 2010). Moreover, collagen type I and III gene expression has also been shown to increase in response to hypertension in the intima, media, and adventitia layers of aortas from rabbits, likely as a protective mechanism from increases in tensile stress (Xu et al., 2000). Arterial elastin content is also negatively affected with ageing as it is described to decline or

become weaker and more fragile, and matrix structural adaptations may occur as a result of cyclic damage, and consequently mechanical fatigue over time (O'Rourke, 1990; Safar, 1990; Avolio et al., 1998; Fritze et al., 2012). Moreover, additional disruption to arterial structure includes increased advanced glycation end products which contributes to the adverse collagen and elastin structure by promoting cross-links between collagen fibres, further augmenting arterial wall stiffness (Zieman and Kass, 2004). Such structural adaptations reduce the capacity of the artery to expand to increases in pressure and therefore contribute to reductions in compliance and increases in stiffness observed in ageing.

Ageing is also associated with increases in sympathetic neuron activity, resulting in an increase in systemic vascular tone and increases in blood pressure in older adults (Narkiewicz et al., 2005). Consequently, increases in resting vascular tone and stiffness elevate vascular resistance (Safar and Struijker-Boudier, 2010). Elevated arterial resistance increases the speed of both, antegrade and retrograde pressure waves within the arterial tree (Laurent et al., 2006). Furthermore, a stiffer artery will allow for antegrade and retrograde waves to travel at greater velocities throughout vessels (Laurent et al., 2006). Such changes influence increases in systolic and diastolic blood pressure, in addition to elevating cardiac afterload and consequently, ventricular hypertrophy (Tarazi and Levy, 1982). Increases in central arterial diameter are typically seen in ageing individuals (Schmidt-Trucksäss et al., 1999; van den Munckhof et al., 2012), which may be as a compensatory response to increases in IMT which also occur in ageing (Thijssen et al., 2016).

Ageing associated increases in arterial IMT, stiffness and reductions in compliance consequentially impairs conduit artery Windkessel function due to reduced capacity of the

arterial walls to stretch and recoil within each cardiac cycle. Such adaptations impair the ability of affected vessels to buffer high intraluminal pressures and therefore cause augmentations of pulsatile flow and haemodynamic stress. For example, the low-resistance cerebral microvessels are vulnerable to high pulsatile and cyclic blood flow from extracranial arteries, microvascular damage can occur including micro-haemorrhages and tissue ischemia (Mitchell et al., 2011; Thorin-Trescases et al., 2018). Such events increase the risk of conditions such as cerebrovascular disease and cognitive impairment (Thorin-Trescases et al., 2018).

Central conduit arteries are susceptible to gradual increases in IMT with ageing, particularly the common and internal carotid arteries (Allan et al., 1997; Garipey et al., 1998; Ando et al., 2000; Depairon et al., 2000; Homma et al., 2001; Brislane et al., 2020). Additionally, increases in PP has also been previously shown to be associated with increases in carotid IMT with age (Zureik et al., 1999; Laurent et al., 2001). Studies including large samples of participants across several decades have also reported that common carotid artery (CCA) IMT is greater within males compared to females of a similar age (Allan et al., 1997; Garipey et al., 1998; Ando et al., 2000). Whilst one study has shown that males and females aged 40 to 79 years without carotid bulb plaques demonstrated increased IMT by 0.04mm per decade (Ando et al., 2000), a separate study also in CV risk-free participants aged 20 - 60 years reported IMT increases of 0.0018mm and 0.0034mm per year in females and males respectively, although the differences between the sexes did not reach significance (Depairon et al., 2000). Increased IMT is believed to help predict future vascular events (Lorenz et al., 2007), and is influenced by cardiovascular risk factors including smoking and higher low-density lipoprotein (LDL) levels (Salonen and Salonen, 1990).

Reductions in CCA blood flow velocity have been observed with advancing age with falls of $0.713 \text{ cm.s.year}^{-1}$ during systole (S1) and $0.122 \text{ cm.s.year}^{-1}$ during diastole in healthy males and females aged between 20 and 76 years old (Azhim et al., 2007b). Additionally, Schmidt-Trucksäss et al. (1999) also reported declines in CCA blood flow velocity across a 59 year range (16 to 75 years) in male participants. Their results identified a decline of peak CCA blood flow velocity by 9.3 cm.s^{-1} every decade, which is slightly higher than decade decreases observed in both males and females over a larger age range (Schmidt-Trucksäss et al., 1999; Azhim et al., 2007b). Whilst blood flow velocity through the CCA may not necessarily represent declines in CBF due to branching not only into the ICA but also the external CA, studies have reported lower blood velocity within the middle cerebral artery (MCA) with ageing (Brislane et al., 2020). Additionally, reports using MRI have highlighted reductions in total CBF in an older versus younger healthy cohort, whilst an inverse linear relationship also existed between age and total CBF within the older cohort (Stoquart-ElSankari et al., 2007). Such decreases have been argued to occur due to reductions in oxygen and substrate demand as a result of lower cerebral metabolism with advancing age (Tarumi and Zhang, 2018). Nonetheless, reductions in CBF may contribute to cerebral hypoperfusion in older adults with declining brain health, such as those who experience cognitive decline and dementia (Ruitenberg et al., 2005), possibly from impaired synthesis of neural proteins (Zlokovic, 2011).

2.4.4 Long-Term Exercise Training and Central Arterial Function

2.4.4.1 Arterial Stiffness and Compliance

Whilst central vascular compliance declines with ageing, research has also focused on the effects of PA and exercise levels as lifestyle factors to mitigate the detrimental effects of ageing. A number of studies have taken a cross-sectional approach in an attempt to identify

whether arterial compliance is preserved, and stiffness reduced in healthy older physically active adults. Findings from over two decades ago were one of the first to show that middle-aged and older endurance males exhibited less carotid and aortic stiffening by 36 % and 26 %, respectively compared to their sedentary peers (Figure 2 - 8) (Vaitkevicius et al., 1993). Moreover, aortic stiffness values of the older endurance-trained cohort, as assessed using PWV, were, at the $P < 0.05$ level, not different to the young individuals, suggesting that long-term endurance training can delay arterial ageing (Vaitkevicius et al., 1993). Studies have since reported similar data, supporting the argument that healthy older adults who participate in long-term endurance training exhibit less systemic arterial stiffness when assessed in females (Tanaka et al., 1998), or mixed-sex cohorts (Deiseroth et al., 2019).

Whilst a number of studies have assessed the influence of exercise on systemic vascular stiffness via measurements of PWV, fewer investigations have focused on local arterial stiffness using method β_1 stiffness and E_p . However, long-term endurance training has been reported to also improve measures of local arterial stiffness. For example, Tanaka et al. (2000) reported reductions in β_1 stiffness in older endurance-trained healthy males at the $P < 0.05$ level in comparison to recreationally active and sedentary counterparts. Thus, these findings suggest that reductions in carotid stiffness may only occur with vigorous exercise at least 5 times per week, as those who were recreationally active (> 3 times per week) did not exhibit differences in arterial stiffness compared to those who do not perform any regular PA. More recently, Shibata et al. (2018) investigated the influence of different life-long exercise frequencies (> 25 years) on carotid β_1 . Whilst carotid β_1 did not differ at the $P < 0.05$ level between exercising groups, only the casual (1 session per week) and competitive (4 - 5 sessions per week) exercisers demonstrated less carotid stiffness in comparison to the sedentary group, whereas the committed exercisers (2 - 3 sessions per week) did not. Whilst these findings also show

that participation in exercise has a beneficial effect on arterial health, the results differ from those of Tanaka et al. (2000) who only seen benefits in vigorous exercisers (more than 5 days per week). However, the participants recruited by Shibata et al. had continuously exercised for > 25 years, whereas Tanaka et al. (2000) reported durations of only 2 or more years. These results may suggest that in order to have a beneficial effect of β_1 stiffness, in particular, lower exercise frequencies such as 'casual exercisers' need to be performed over longer-term periods (i.e., ≥ 25 years). However, it should be noted that although the casual exercisers exhibited a lower β_1 compared to the sedentary group, the P-value was close to the $P < 0.05$ level ($P = 0.047$), and thus, similar to the 'non-significant' difference between the sedentary and committed exercisers ($P = 0.052$). Whilst an alpha level of < 0.05 was used, the results could demonstrate that greater frequency of activity may be required to see the greatest benefit in arterial health, as demonstrated by the competitive exercisers ($P = 0.009$) (Shibata et al., 2018). However, the absence of power calculation and small sample sizes within each group ($n < 30$) could also suggest that the results were affected by a type II error and thus the committed exercisers may have had an arterial benefit over the sedentary group. Nonetheless, the lack of differences in β_1 between the three exercise groups may demonstrate that exercise of any frequency may better for arterial health than remaining sedentary (Shibata et al., 2018).

Whilst a number of studies have assessed the effects of long-term exercise on central arterial stiffness using conventional measures, fewer have used the novel speckle tracking method to assess arterial compliance. Only two studies at present have used speckle tracking to investigate the link between exercise and carotid compliance, where PCS and PSR was shown to be higher in healthy young and older male participants with higher levels of cardiorespiratory fitness (CRF) at the $P < 0.05$ level compared to their age-matched counterparts with lower CRF levels (Pugh et al., 2018; Talbot et al., 2020). However, no

previous research has used speckle tracking to investigate the arterial compliance of exercise-trained and untrained healthy middle-aged or older females. Whilst the advantages of speckle tracking compared to conventional methods of arterial stiffness and compliance have been described previously (Bjallmark et al., 2010; Yuda et al., 2011), research using speckle tracking is required to further understand the influence which exercise training has on central vascular compliance within healthy middle-aged and older cohorts.

2.4.4.2 Intima-Media Thickness

Since increases in carotid IMT are known to occur within healthy ageing, IMT has been assessed in long-term endurance exercisers to identify whether such lifestyle factors can protect against arterial ageing. However, cross-sectional analyses of endurance-trained and untrained healthy middle-aged and older adults have produced contrasting results with many reporting no differences between the groups in all male (Tanaka et al., 2002) and all female cohorts (Moreau et al., 2002). A later study agreed with these findings, as Sandrock et al. (2008) reported similar CCA IMT between healthy older sedentary and active group which had participated in endurance exercise greater of equal to three days per week for ≥ 30 years. In contrast, studies which have specifically used objectively measured CRF data rather than subjectively collected training volume have reported inverse relationships between $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ and IMT in middle-aged and older men (Lakka et al., 2001; Kang and Ko, 2019). Thus, these data suggest that greater levels of aerobic capacity rather than training frequency may mitigate arterial structural adaptations caused by ageing.

In addition to CRF levels, healthy older adults who demonstrate faster objectively measured walking speeds also exhibited smaller carotid IMTs in comparison to individuals with slower walking paces, even after controlling for factors including sex and systolic blood pressure (SBP) (Hamer et al., 2010). As well as objectively measured factors, associations between CCA IMT and subjective measures of PA have also been assessed. Nordstrom et al. (2003) reported associations between leisure-time PA levels and IMT measured over a one-and-a-half-year period in 500 healthy middle-aged adults. Specifically, the increase in IMT per year were 14.3 ± 1.7 , 10.2 ± 1 and 5.5 ± 1.5 microns for sedentary, moderately and vigorously active adults, respectively, thus identifying that a dose-response relationship may exist between PA levels and arterial protection (Nordstrom et al., 2003). These findings contrast with an earlier report within 51 male participants aged between 16 and 78 years who did not demonstrate differences in IMT between those who self-reported high and low levels of leisure-time PA (Schmidt-Trucksäss et al., 1999). However, whilst Schmidt-Trucksäss et al. (1999) approached the question with a cross-sectional view, Nordstrom et al. 2003 reported IMT changes over a 3 year period. These data could suggest that PA levels may not necessarily demonstrate differences in IMT at a single time point, but rather higher PA levels can identify reductions in IMT progression when assessed over longer periods of time.

2.4.4.3 Blood flow and Velocity

Long-term exercise training has also been reported to reduce age-associated declines in CBF in healthy middle-aged and older adults. In a cohort of healthy young and older adults analysed together, those who regularly performed thrice weekly endurance-based exercise exhibited higher peak systolic and end diastolic velocities by 18 % and 9 %, respectively (Azhim et al., 2007b). Ainslie et al. (2008) reported similar findings the following year when

assessing blood velocity within the middle cerebral artery (MCAv). Whilst MCAv gradually declined with advancing age, the endurance-trained males aged 18 - 79 years exhibited blood velocities of $9.1 \text{ cm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ greater than their sedentary counterparts throughout the age range, which is believed to equate to a 10 year reduction in MCAv age (Ainslie et al., 2008). However, cross-sectional studies in healthy older adults have also reported differences in MCAv between endurance-trained and untrained healthy males (Braz et al., 2017). In addition to blood flow velocity, measurements of blood flow have also been measured in both, extra and intracranial arteries to determine the relationship between ageing and exercise. Braz et al. (2017) assessed the ICA and vertebral artery (VA) blood flow within healthy older exercise-trained and untrained male cohort. Whilst ICA flow was higher in the exercise-trained compared to the untrained males, a lack of differences was seen in bilateral VA blood flow between groups (Braz et al., 2017). These data may suggest that anterior cerebral flow has a beneficial effect from exercise training, whilst posterior cerebral flow remains unchanged. Additionally, associations between greater estimated CRF has been documented in CBF of the white and grey matter in a cohort of older males and females (Zimmerman et al., 2014).

2.4.5 Short-Term Exercise Training and Central Endothelial Function

2.4.5.1 Arterial Stiffness and Compliance

Though there is some evidence to suggest that long-term endurance exercise can mitigate the effects of arterial ageing, many interventional studies have also investigated whether central arterial ageing can be offset in later life. Thijssen et al. (2007) assessed arterial compliance in healthy older males before and after a thrice-weekly moderate to high intensity 8 week cycling intervention. Whilst improved peripheral compliance was observed in the femoral arteries, central carotid compliance was unaffected by the endurance-based

intervention (Thijssen et al., 2007). However, these findings contrast with studies that included mixed sex healthy middle-aged and older adults which have demonstrated improvements in total arterial compliance, regional arterial stiffness and local carotid stiffness measures after endurance training (Figure 2 - 8). For example, studies ranging from 9 weeks to 1 year, and from progressive walking and jogging exercises to high-intensity intermittent cycling have reported reducing systemic arterial stiffness via PWV and aortic compliance within healthy middle-aged and older mixed-sex and female-only cohorts (Yoshizawa et al., 2009; Fujimoto et al., 2010; Vogel et al., 2013). Furthermore, local carotid stiffness as assessed by β_1 also declined after an 8 week moderate-intensity aerobic intervention within a similar cohort (Fujie et al., 2014). In addition, separate studies have shown that 12 weeks of combined moderate endurance and resistance training, and a home-based bench stepping exercise have reduced PWV and BP compared to their respective control groups in middle-aged and older healthy female cohorts (Figuroa et al., 2011; Ohta et al., 2012). Although different aspects of arterial function were assessed (stiffness and compliance) these data may suggest that longer intervention durations or cycling duration have a better influence on central arterial health.

Figure 2 - 8. The influence of sedentary ageing, long-term and short-term endurance exercise on central arterial compliance in ageing individuals (Tanaka, 2019).

In addition to the effects of endurance-based exercise on central vascular stiffness and compliance, several reports have also highlighted the effects of short-term resistance training on arterial ageing. Whilst there is evidence to suggest that resistance training is detrimental to arterial health within younger cohorts (Miyachi et al., 2004), a number of studies have produced contrasting results within an older population. In 2006, Maeda et al. found no improvements in PWV after 12 weeks of twice-weekly resistance training within an exclusively healthy older male cohort. Carotid stiffness and compliance have also been unaffected by both upper and lower body resistance training performed more frequently and/or over a longer duration in healthy middle-aged and older male and female participants (Poelkens et al., 2007; Cortez-Cooper et al., 2008). However, Williams et al. (2013) reported that 16 weeks of thrice-weekly full-body resistance training reduced arterial stiffness via reduced augmentation index in comparison to a flexibility intervention also performed. Interestingly, such results were only

evident within the healthy older female participants, whilst differences were not observed in the males (Williams et al., 2013). Although these data may suggest that middle-aged and older healthy females may also benefit from resistance training to a greater extent than males, others have reported no changes in PWV after resistance training in other postmenopausal cohorts (Yoshizawa et al., 2009; Rossow et al., 2014). Therefore, previous studies assessing the effects of resistance training on central arterial stiffness have used commonly used conventional measures to assess local, regional, and systemic arterial stiffness. Currently, no study has used the novel ultrasound speckle tracking method to assess the effects of resistance-based exercise on local carotid compliance. The use of this novel method may be beneficial as it has previously been reported to be more sensitive to changes in arterial compliance compared to commonly used traditional methods such as β_1 and E_p (Bjallmark et al., 2010).

2.4.5.2 Intima-Media Thickness

Whilst some exercise interventions may improve arterial function in ageing, there have been some discrepancies as to whether short-term exercise training can affect arterial structure by reducing the age-associated increases of IMT in healthy older adults. Endurance-based interventions ranging between 8 and 12 weeks of progressive walking/jogging and high-intensity cycling have failed to reduce IMT in previously sedentary healthy older males (Tanaka et al., 2002; Thijssen et al., 2007). Furthermore, CCA IMT was also unaffected in 15 healthy males 65 years and older who performed 24 weeks of progressive resistance band training three days per week (Park, 2016). However, older adults who have performed interventions of combined endurance and resistance-based interventions demonstrate contrasting results. For example, 24 weeks of low-moderate combined training (5 days per week) and 12 weeks of low-moderate intensity combined and Korean dance-based exercise (3

days per week) reduced IMT at the $P < 0.05$ level among overweight older females (Park et al., 2015, 2017a). Whilst these data may suggest that combination training and/or females may be more effective in reducing IMT, it is possible that a larger margin for improvement was available compared to 'healthy' cohorts due to the relationship between CCA IMT and BMI (Jin et al., 2018). Moreover, although the $P < 0.05$ level was met, the decrease in IMT was small (0.01 mm), which may not have had a clinical impact on arterial health. Overall, short-term exercise appears to have little to no influence on CCA IMT. Nonetheless, associations between ROS and IMT have been reported (Watanabe et al., 2006). In contrast to short term exercise, lower IMT from high PA levels in longitudinal studies may be due less inflammation over a prolonged period of time (greater than 1 year), thus reducing the rate at which IMT increases with age as a result.

2.4.5.3 Blood Flow and Velocity

Less research has presented findings regarding the effects of exercise training on carotid blood flow within older individuals. Twenty-four weeks of either combined training or resistance-band training has previously increased peak systolic and end diastolic blood velocities within the common carotid arteries of older females with sarcopenic obesity and in healthy older males, respectively (Park, 2016; Park et al., 2017a). Conversely, moderate to high-intensity cycling based endurance exercise failed to augment blood flow profiles within the CCA in healthy older males (Thijssen et al., 2007). Although increases in carotid blood velocity were reported in an unhealthy cohort these data may therefore suggest that durations longer than 8 weeks may be required for improvements in blood flow to occur. However, a greater number of studies are required to assess the effects of endurance and resistance-based training on carotid blood flow in healthy middle-aged and older adults.

2.4.6 Central Arterial Function Exercise Mechanisms

The underlying mechanisms surrounding the decreases in arterial stiffness in exercise-trained older adults has been investigated. Some previous studies have suggested that the intrinsic properties of the artery may be affected by long-term exercise or training, such as the media elastin and collagen content. For example, it was reported that endurance-trained rats exhibit more elastin and lower collagen content within the media of the aorta and reduced advanced glycation end products consequently resulting in greater arterial compliance and reduced stiffness (Koutsis et al., 1995; Gu et al., 2014). Additionally, 10 - 14 weeks of endurance training reduced carotid stiffness from decreased arterial calcification, and medial and adventitial collagen I and III in older mice (Fleenor et al., 2010). Such adaptations are likely to influence the compliance and stiffness of an artery by increasing the elasticity and allowing for greater expansion compared to arteries with greater collagen and less elastin content. Whilst this might be true for long-term trained older adults, structural adaptations may not necessarily occur during short-term interventions in previously sedentary healthy older adults (Shibata and Levine, 2012; Sacre et al., 2014; Deiseroth et al., 2019).

Decreases in carotid artery compliance have also been associated with increases in sympathetic neuron activity in older age (Tanaka et al., 2017). Although cause and effect cannot be confirmed through correlational data, it is believed that increases in sympathetic neuron activity which occur with advancing age increases arterial vasoconstrictor tone and reduces the ability of the artery to expand (Tanaka et al., 2017). Whilst others support that exercise training or long-term endurance exercise may increase sympathetic neuron activity

(Ng et al., 1994; Sugawara et al., 2007), some believe that long-term exercise may increase parasympathetic tone in older adults (Ueno and Moritani, 2003). Though the results of previous studies are conflicting, central arterial compliance was not measured alongside neural activity. Therefore, it is unclear whether potential adaptations in sympathetic or parasympathetic activity from exercise training can influence central carotid compliance in older adults. Nonetheless, 12 weeks of endurance training has reduced concentrations of the potent vasoconstrictor endothelin-1 in healthy middle-aged and older adults, resulting in improvements in carotid compliance due to reductions in vascular tone (Maeda et al., 2009)

Research investigating the effect of resistance training on central arterial stiffness has provided mixed results, however, the majority of studies have reported no adverse effect of resistance training on arterial health in healthy older adults. A limitation, however, is that most interventions have been short-term, where many last between 8 weeks and 1 year. Therefore, there is a lack of research investigating the effects of long-term resistance training, such as durations greater than 1 year, on central arterial structure, stiffness, and compliance in exclusively healthy middle-aged and older adults. Nonetheless, progressive resistance training has been reported to reduce total cholesterol, the ratio of total cholesterol to high-density lipoprotein, low-density lipoprotein and triglyceride levels in adults (Kelley and Kelley, 2009), thus creating a healthier vascular environment. Whilst decreases in oxidative stress and inflammation may also provide a beneficial effect as described previously within peripheral arteries (Section 2.3.8), the mechanisms surrounding the influence of resistance training on arterial health are still being investigated.

Although reductions in CCA IMT have not always been reported, reductions are believed to be due to factors such as increased systemic arterial wall shear stress which occur with repeated bouts of exercise (Thijssen et al., 2011, 2012). Additionally, reductions in oxidative stress and inflammation as a result of regular exercise participation has also been believed to contribute to reductions in IMT (Thijssen et al., 2012; Seyedsadjadi et al., 2018). Whilst these adaptations may occur from higher levels of habitual PA as demonstrated in longitudinal studies, less is known about the effects of long-term resistance training on the inflammatory status and IMT of the CA.

2.5 Cognitive Function

2.5.1 Overview

Cognitive functioning represents the neuropsychological processes required to complete daily tasks. More specifically, cognitive function has been defined as ‘the mental action or process of acquiring knowledge and understanding through thought, experience, and the senses’ (Cambridge Cognition, 2015). Cognitive function is composed of several domains which have distinct functions, yet they work collectively to contribute to overall cognition. Examples of specific domains include executive function, attention, language, memory, and psychomotor speed, with each containing its own subdomains (Figure 2 - 9). Cognitive domains have been referred to as a ‘hierarchy’ as some only require simple cognitive processing, whilst others demonstrate greater complexity (Harvey, 2019). For example, complex cognitive processes such as executive functioning consist of various subdomains of decision making, planning, and inhibitory control in order to successfully perform daily cognitive tasks. Conversely, information processing speed is a less complex cognitive domain that require less high-order cognitive processing. Nonetheless, the coordination of less complex cognitive domains such as motor speed and reaction time is required for the completion of more complex cognitive tasks (Harvey, 2019).

Figure 2 - 9. Neurocognitive domains (far left) and associated sub-domains (right) (Cambridge Cognition, 2015).

2.5.2 Cognitive Function Measurement

Cognitive tests have been designed to assess specific subdomains of different cognitive domains. As cognitive domains work collectively to facilitate cognitive function and the completion of different cognitive tasks, many discrete abilities can be measured via cognitive assessments (Harvey, 2019).

A number of validated cognitive assessments have been used within the literature to assess cognitive function in a range of individuals, including different ages and cognitive abilities. Traditional cognitive test batteries are a group of tests that are often referred to as ‘pencil and paper’ tests that assess a wide range of cognitive domains. Traditional tests have

been used since the early to mid-20th century, as some examples including the Stroop test which was developed in 1935 (Stroop, 1935), the verbal fluency test was first reported in 1944 (Bousfield and Sedgewick, 1944), and the Trail Making tests which were also reported within the 1940s (Army Individual Test Battery, 1944). Similarly, the Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale (WAIS) which was developed in 1955 contains a battery of tests aimed at assessing domains including verbal comprehension, perceptual reasoning, working memory, and processing speed (Doppelt and Wallace, 1955).

In addition to traditional cognitive test batteries, more recently computerised, or digital test batteries were introduced during the 1980s. One of the first touch-screen computerised test batteries was the Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery (CANTAB), originally developed for the assessment of neurodegenerative diseases (Sternin et al., 2019). However, CANTAB can be used to assess cognitive function in cognitively impaired, psychiatric, and cognitively healthy cohorts.

2.5.3 Cognitive Function and Ageing

Various domains of cognitive function such as processing speed, working and long-term memory become increasingly impaired with healthy ageing, even from the second decade (Park et al., 2002). The extent of cognitive decline is not homogenous (Mungas et al., 2010), as some individuals will experience greater declines in function with age than others (Figure 2 - 10) (Wilson et al., 2002). For example, cognitive reserve, which defines the resilience of an individual to declines in cognitive function from damage within the brain, differs between individuals. Reasons for differences between individuals include factors such as PA levels, intelligence and education level attained (Stern, 2002; Mortimer and Stern, 2019), as for

example, individuals with higher levels of education experience less cognitive decline with age (Leibovici et al., 1996; Ren et al., 2018). Individuals who exhibit higher levels of cognitive reserve are therefore believed to be more resilient to age-associated changes in brain structure and function, which reduces the rate of cognitive decline compared to those with lower levels of cognitive reserve.

Figure 2 - 10. Individual variation in longitudinal cognitive decline with advancing age in older adults who were cognitively intact at time of recruitment (presented by Buckner (2004) and adapted from Rubin et al. (1998)).

Whilst overall cognitive performance declines with advancing age, not all cognitive domains are affected equally (Figure 2 - 11). Cognitive domains have been classified into different groups referred to as crystallised and fluid intelligence which are based on cognitive familiarity and use throughout the lifetime (Harada et al., 2013, 201). Crystallised intelligence includes cognitive domains such as language and is less affected by the ageing process due to its high familiarity and being well-practiced (Harada et al., 2013). Conversely, fluid

intelligence concerns an individual’s ability to adapt within changing environments, including problem-solving, learning, and processing new information (Harada et al., 2013). In contrast to crystallised intelligence, fluid intelligence is known to decline gradually from approximately 30 years of age (Salthouse, 2012).

Figure 2 - 11. Representation of cognitive domains which are, and are not affected by advancing age (presented by Buckner (2004) using data from Park et al. (1996)).

Moreover, different cognitive domains are shown to have negative effects on one another, meaning that any decline may not be exclusively related to one cognitive domain only. For example, information processing speed is known as one of the first cognitive domains to become affected by increasing age yet declines within this domain negatively affect a number of other cognitive areas (Salthouse, 1996), particularly those which are classed as fluid measures such verbal fluency and memory (Finkel et al., 2007; Harada et al., 2013). Moreover, declines in attention not only occurs with advancing age but has also been associated with declines in working memory performance (Gazzaley et al., 2005), as healthy older adults who demonstrated a reduced suppression of non-relevant information also exhibited lower working

memory. Such declines in fluid intelligence cause a detrimental effect on cognitive processes required for daily tasks and can negatively impact independent living (Murman, 2015).

Whilst heterogeneity in the decline of different cognitive domains also exists within individuals with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and dementia (Mungas et al., 2010), it is important to highlight that healthy ageing-associated cognitive decline does not necessarily infer cognitive disease. Neurodegenerative conditions including MCI, vascular dementia, and Alzheimer's disease impacts on cognition and independence to varying extents and are differentiated from natural cognitive ageing by the means of clinical neuropsychological screening, such as the Mini Mental State Exam (MMSE) (Arevalo-Rodriguez et al., 2015). However, in order to understand the influence that PA and exercise has on healthy ageing exclusively, this thesis focuses specifically on research involving healthy cognitive ageing unless otherwise stated.

2.5.4 Ageing Mechanisms of Cognitive Function

Ageing has been associated with declines in structure and function of a number of brain regions (Fjell and Walhovd, 2010), with the greatest changes occurring after the age of 70 years (Scahill et al., 2003). Age-associated adaptations include brain shrinkage in various regions (Raz et al., 2010), including within grey and white matter volume (Meier-Ruge et al., 1992; Hafkemeijer et al., 2014). Such structural and functional adaptations have been linked with declines in cognitive functions with age, including executive function (O'Sullivan et al., 2001) and information processing speed (Penke et al., 2010). Neuron density and structure are also negatively affected with ageing (Murman, 2015), partly due to declines in neurotrophic factors including brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) (Tapia-Arancibia et al., 2008) which is

responsible for neuronal plasticity, growth, and survival. Consequently, individuals with Alzheimer's disease exhibit lower levels of BDNF compared to healthy controls, which highlight that reductions in BDNF can be linked with cognitive dysfunction (Ng et al., 2019).

Age-associated declines in vascular health may also negatively impact cognitive function in healthy ageing. It has been previously suggested that individuals who have vascular impairments such as hypertension are also at an increased risk of cognitive impairment, compared to those with normal vascular function (Debette et al., 2011; Roberts et al., 2013, 2015; González et al., 2018). This may be due to structural adaptations within the artery which occur with ageing such as increases in central arterial stiffness may reduce the ability of the carotid artery to expand with pulsatile flow (Section 2.4.3). As a result, it may not buffer the pulsatile flow to the brain, and low-resistance cerebral micro-vessels become vulnerable to micro-vascular damage which can cause micro-haemorrhages and cerebral tissue ischemia to occur (Mitchell et al., 2011).

Additionally, ageing associated remodelling of arterial walls has also been linked with damage within the brain including white matter lesions (Bos et al., 2011). The resulting vascular and tissue damage in the brain may therefore contribute to cognitive impairment (Thorin-Trescases et al., 2018). Findings from an update of the longitudinal Lothian Birth Cohort identified that associations between increasing pulsatility and impaired cognitive function within areas of processing speed and visuospatial function at the age of 70 years. Moreover, after adjusting for vascular risk factors such as CVD and hypertension, ICA pulsatility index (PI) was associated with declines in crystallised intelligence with advancements in age over the 6 year study period (Wardlaw et al., 2017). Higher levels of ICA

PI have also previously been shown to correlate with cerebral white matter hyperintensities in generally healthy community-dwelling older adults (Aribisala et al., 2014). As PI represents the pulsatile environment within the artery, it appears that high pulsatile flow may have caused damage to the low-resistance cerebrovascular system, including micro-vessels, negatively affecting cognitive function as a result (O'Rourke and Safar, 2005).

Impaired endothelial function, as assessed by brachial artery FMD has also been associated with reductions in cognitive function. Reductions in working memory have been reported to directly associate with brachial FMD in healthy middle-aged adults when assessed independently of age, sex, SBP and intelligence scores, (Gonzales et al., 2010). Additionally, an index of peripheral vascular health also containing measurement of brachial FMD has been reported to predict cognitive impairment when assessed in a cohort of healthy young and older adults (Csipo et al., 2019). Furthermore, impaired FMD is more prevalent in older adults who have MCI, despite when exhibiting no risk factors for CV impairment other than age (Vendemiale et al., 2013). Specifically, it has been reported that impaired FMD is most commonly associated with declines in cognitive domains including attention and executive function as well as working memory (Naiberg et al., 2016). Studies have suggested that FMD may provide information concerning the function of the cerebral endothelial function when assessed via cerebrovascular reactivity (Pretnar-Oblak et al., 2006; Naiberg et al., 2016). Moreover, endothelial dysfunction may also represent damage to the blood-brain barrier (BBB) which has been linked with increases in inflammation (Goodall et al., 2018) and declines in cognitive function (Bowman et al., 2018). As endothelial function also influences neurovascular coupling, disturbances in endothelial-mediated vasodilation disrupt the necessary cerebral blood delivery and consequently, cerebral homeostasis (Tarantini et al.,

2017). Therefore, it is likely that cerebrovascular endothelial dysfunction may contribute to the cognitive impairments seen in ageing and in conditions including MCI and dementia.

In addition to measures of extracranial vascular function, links between cognitive decline and cerebrovascular function with age have also been reported. One study reported decreases in CBF of 4.1 ml.min⁻¹ every year in healthy young and older participants together, whereas yearly declines of 9.38 ml.min⁻¹ were reported when assessed in the older cohort only (Stoquart-ElSankari et al., 2007). The evidence surrounding the link between CBF decline and cognitive dysfunction is conflicting with declines in CBF being both associated (Rabbitt et al., 2006), and not associated (Poels et al., 2008) with cognitive decline. Furthermore, others have seen associations between global CBF with some, but not all cognitive domains (Rabbitt et al., 2006). Nonetheless, older individuals with Alzheimer's disease demonstrate lower levels of CBF at the $P \leq 0.05$ level compared to healthy individuals, where the declines have been associated with cognitive dysfunction (Roher et al., 2012).

2.5.5 Long-Term Exercise Training and Cognitive Function

Whilst cognitive function is known to decrease with advancing age, various modifiable lifestyle factors have been researched as ways to positively influence cognitive ageing. Similar to the effect of exercise on vascular function, a significant amount of research has been conducted surrounding the influence of habitual PA levels on cognitive function in cognitively healthy older adults. Some studies have taken a longitudinal approach in an attempt to understand the influence of habitual PA levels on age-associated cognitive decline. For example, healthy older adults who have self-reported higher levels of PA at baseline have often demonstrated superior cognitive functioning during follow-up periods many years later,

compared to their less active counterparts (Laurin et al., 2001; Yaffe et al., 2001; Barnes et al., 2003; Larson et al., 2006; Nyberg et al., 2014; Zhu et al., 2014; Hörder et al., 2018). Whilst longitudinal studies of varying durations have been reported, some have investigated whether PA levels during early adulthood are involved in cognitive function in later life. Nyberg et al. (2014) initially assessed cardiovascular fitness via a cycling $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ test, and cognitive function including logical, verbal, visuospatial, and technical cognition in a cohort of healthy 18 year-old males. After 42 years it was determined that low CRF and cognitive function at age 18 were linked with the risk of developing MCI and early-onset dementia aged 60 years (Nyberg et al., 2014).

Others have approached this question with the aim of determining whether PA levels in mid to later life may mitigate cognitive ageing when elderly. Greater levels of self-reported PA and CRF during mid-life have been shown to reduce dementia risk after 6.2 and 44 years, respectively (Larson et al., 2006; Hörder et al., 2018). Aside from diagnosis of dementia risk, the rate of cognitive decline has also been assessed using the MMSE. Yaffe et al. (2001) reported smaller reductions in cognitive function in 5925 healthy elderly females when higher levels of self-reported PA were reported eight years earlier. Furthermore, the cognitive functioning of both, middle-aged and older adults has also been negatively influenced by low and moderate levels of PA compared to higher activity levels when measured approximately six and 11 years earlier (Singh-Manoux et al., 2005). Although there are limitations of using methods of self-reported PA including over-estimation and reduced accuracy of data, Barnes et al. (2003) also identified less cognitive decline when higher levels of objectively measured CRF were recorded six years earlier. Furthermore, positive associations between CRF measured at baseline and cognitive domains measured simultaneously (Voelcker-Rehage et al., 2010; Weinstein et al., 2012), and after follow-up periods of six (Barnes et al., 2003) and 25

years (Zhu et al., 2014) have also been reported. Conversely, not all studies support the benefit of exercise and cognitive function, as some have demonstrated no associations between exercise and various cognitive domains with one study also reporting lower logical memory performance with higher self-reported walking reported 2 years earlier (Broe et al., 1998). However, activity levels were collected when participants were aged > 75 years, which therefore represents baseline PA levels during old age and not mid-life. As PA decreases with advancing age (Milanovic et al., 2013), it is likely that PA levels measured during mid-life may be a better predictor of cognitive decline at later stages in life.

In addition to longitudinal studies, cross-sectional research investigating the effects of committed long-term exercise on cognitive function spans decades. Early reports investigated cognitive functioning between racquet sports masters athletes compared to non-active controls (Spirduo, 1975). The exercise-trained males participated in their activity for > 30 years and were reported to benefit from superior simple and discriminatory reaction time. Since then, others have also demonstrated superior cognitive function in domains including verbal memory and reaction time (Tseng et al., 2013; Zhao et al., 2016) within both male and female masters athletes when compared to their sedentary controls. Whilst cross-sectional studies have limitations including reduced certainty of cause and effect compared to longitudinal studies, many have controlled for levels of education or intelligence to increase confidence that improvements in cognitive function are not as a result of underlying confounding factors (Tseng et al., 2013; Zhao et al., 2016).

Others, rather than having distinct trained and untrained cohorts, have divided their cohorts post inclusion based on their objective PA levels or objective fitness values. Clarkson-

Smith and Hartley (1989) firstly reported superior reasoning, working memory, and reaction time after separating the older individuals into their self-reported 'most' versus 'least' active PA groups. Subsequent studies have used a similar approach, whereby the middle-aged and older male and female cohorts were separated into two groups based on $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ values only, or from both, $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ scores and self-reported activity levels (Shay and Roth, 1992, 19; Brown et al., 2010). The studies concluded that that only visuospatial function was elevated in a highly fit vs less fit male cohort (Shay and Roth, 1992), whereas overall cognitive function was superior in 'active' versus 'sedentary' postmenopausal females (Brown et al., 2010). Whilst the studies including exclusively male or female cohorts are not directly comparable, these findings suggest that males and females have different cognitive responses related to differences in CRF as both used extensive neuropsychological test batteries (Shay and Roth, 1992; Brown et al., 2010). Furthermore, an earlier study that split participants based on self-reported PA and submaximal $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ measures found that better reaction time performance during complex, but not simple tasks were seen in the active cohort (Abourezk and Toole, 1995). These results highlight that cognitive tests of higher complexity, particularly within sensorimotor tasks may be required in order to differentiate cognitive function between highly active and inactive older individuals.

2.5.6 Short-Term Exercise Training and Cognitive Function

There is clear evidence that habitual and long-term engagement in endurance-based exercise can mitigate the ageing associated declines in cognitive function compared to sedentary or less active controls. However, research has also focused on the commencement of exercise participation in later life in an attempt to see whether cognitive declines can be ameliorated with short term bouts of exercise.

2.5.6.1 Aerobic exercise

Research investigating the influence of endurance-based exercise interventions again spans back decades, with Madden et al. (1989) one of the first to assess cognitive function after 16 weeks of cycling at 70 % HRR or yoga training compared to a non-exercise control. However, it was reported that despite improvements in CRF from thrice weekly aerobic training, reaction time did not improve after the intervention (Madden et al., 1989). Similarly, cycling interventions of the same frequency, intensity, and duration, or less (8 weeks) have also failed to show improvements in cognitive function including reaction time and memory compared to control or yoga cohorts despite improvements in CRF (Blumenthal et al., 1991; Whitehurst, 1991). Whilst ceiling effects are likely to occur when using reaction time as a cognitive outcome variable, reaction time has been described as a sensitive measure of cognitive function in older adults as results can occur over a greater range than many other traditional cognitive assessments (Christ et al., 2018).

However, endurance-based interventions of greater durations have demonstrated improvements in cognitive function in previously sedentary older adults. For example, Albinet et al. (2016) reported improvements in executive function from lower interference within the Stroop test, and a greater number of correct answers during a verbal running span task compared to an age-matched stretching control group. Sufficient duration of moderate-intensity exercise training is emphasised as improvements in function were reported after 21 weeks, yet not after 10 weeks (Albinet et al., 2016). A number of studies have reported similar findings when assessing cognitive function before and after longer durations of endurance exercise. Improvements in domains including memory, attention, and executive function have been reported after 6 months of endurance-based training in healthy older adults (Kramer et

al., 1999; Ruscheweyh et al., 2011; Antunes et al., 2015). Whilst most of these studies implemented moderate-intensity training compared to a control group, low-intensity training has also been sufficient in improving memory performance in community-dwelling older adults (Ruscheweyh et al., 2011).

Interventions of longer durations, typically 12 months have also had a beneficial effect on cognitive function in healthy ageing. Many have seen improvements in domains including spatial memory when compared to a stretching control group (Voss et al., 2010; Erickson et al., 2011), or less cognitive decline than controls (Muscarello et al., 2009). However, whilst 6 months of training has improved cognitive function elsewhere (Kramer et al., 1999; Ruscheweyh et al., 2011; Antunes et al., 2015) a moderate intensity walking intervention produced improvements in cognitive function at 12, but not 6 months (Voss et al., 2010). Therefore, it appears there is ambiguity as to the optimal duration of endurance training required to improve cognitive function in healthy older adults, although longer durations seem to benefit on cognitive function more consistently. However, as training studies within the literature differ in respect to absolute intensities and training frequencies, a direct comparison between studies cannot be made. Nonetheless, a 2015 meta-analysis of 12 RCT studies ranging from 6 to 26 weeks reported that endurance-based exercise interventions did not improve cognitive function at the $P < 0.05$ level when 11 cognitive domains were assessed in cognitively healthy adults aged > 55 years (Young et al., 2015). The lack of improvement in cognitive function was also observed despite improvements in CRF. Taken together, there is evidence to suggest that long-term endurance training likely has a greater effect on cognitive function within the ageing population than does short term exercise training in cognitively healthy sedentary ageing cohorts.

2.5.6.2 Resistance Exercise

Whilst fewer studies exist which assess the long-term effects of resistance exercise participation, interventional studies have attempted to identify the effects of resistance training on cognitive functions of healthy older adults. Unlike endurance-training studies which have failed to see improvements after shorter intervention periods, resistance training of just 6 weeks has shown to improve cognitive function at the $P < 0.05$ level. Fragala et al. (2014) stated that twice-weekly resistance training equating to a moderate intensity, as indicated from RPE, improved cognitive domains including visual and physical reaction time to a greater extent in healthy older adults compared to a control group. This included improvements in spatial awareness by 40 % in the resistance-trained group compared to only 2.9 % within the control (Fragala et al., 2014). Moreover, 10 weeks of twice-weekly instability resistance training improved executive performance at the $P < 0.05$ level in cognitively healthy older adults (Eckardt et al., 2020). Whilst these data may suggest that resistance training of shorter durations can have a beneficial impact on cognitive function, 12 weeks of either high (75 – 85 % 1RM) or low intensity (55 – 65 % 1RM) resistance training failed to improve cognitive function in sedentary, but medically healthy older adults (Tsutsumi et al., 1997). Additionally, 12 weeks of twice-weekly moderate-intensity resistance training failed to improve executive functioning when compared to a health education control group (Kimura et al., 2010). Whilst participants recruited in said studies were similar in age, cognitive functioning, and physical health status, it is possible that shorter durations of moderate-intensity training may benefit cognitive function when a greater number of repetitions or resistance type exercises are performed (Fragala et al., 2014). Nonetheless, this would not explain the lack of improvement in cognitive function after high-intensity resistance training which consisted of similar sets and repetitions as the successful moderate-intensity intervention (Tsutsumi et al., 1997; Fragala et al., 2014). However, the majority of cognitive domains assessed, and neuropsychological tests

used differed between studies (Tsutsumi et al., 1997; Kimura et al., 2010; Fragala et al., 2014). Therefore, the optimal resistance training mode cannot be confirmed until many studies compare results from similar cognitive tests and domains.

Although 12 weeks of high or low-intensity resistance training did not improve cognitive function (Tsutsumi et al., 1997), results published a decade later contrast with these earlier findings. Cassilhas et al. (2007) reported improvements in cognitive domains at the $P < 0.05$ level including executive function and memory in both the moderate and high-intensity thrice-weekly interventions compared to a control group of older males, albeit after 24 weeks. Resistance training interventions lasting a year in duration have also shown improvements in specific cognitive domains (Liu-Ambrose, 2010; Tsai et al., 2015). For example, Liu-Ambrose et al. (2010) reported that both once or twice weekly resistance training of a progressively high intensity improved selective attention and conflict resolution as assessed by the Stroop test at the $P < 0.05$ level compared to a stretching and toning control group. However, other cognitive domains including set-shifting and working memory did not appear to be influenced by the high-intensity training in the previously sedentary all-female cohort, suggesting that resistance training may improve select cognitive domains (Liu-Ambrose, 2010). A recent meta-analysis somewhat supports these claims, reporting that executive function, memory and working memory were most likely to be improved from resistance training based on previous studies (Northey et al., 2018). Moreover, the results from Liu-Ambrose et al. (2010) are similar to Cassilhas et al. (2007) as increases in frequency or intensity did not appear to increase the cognitive benefits observed. Nonetheless, a recent meta-analysis has reported that moderate-intensity exercise including endurance, resistance, and tai-chi all improved cognitive function in healthy older adults, whereas lower-intensity interventions including yoga and those of less than 45 minutes in duration did not benefit cognition (Northey et al., 2018).

Figure 2. 12. Ageing associated vascular impairments and possible links to age related cognitive decline. Aerobic exercise may help prevent cognitive decline through vascular pathways (Barnes and Corkery, 2018). Solid lines, support within literature; dashed lines, possible links yet to be investigated.

2.5.7 Cognitive Function Exercise Mechanisms

There are a number of factors which may cause improvements in cognitive function from regular participation in exercise and higher levels of CRF. Many studies support the benefit of exercise participation for increases in cerebral volumes including regions such as the hippocampus (Erickson et al., 2011), grey, and white matter (Tseng et al., 2013). Additionally, exercise participation can upregulate neurotrophins (Erickson et al., 2011; Ruscheweyh et al., 2011; Barnes and Corkery, 2018) and growth factors (Cassilhas et al., 2007; Tsai et al., 2015) which are associated with increases in cerebral volumes and improvements in cognitive

function (Leckie et al., 2014). Notably, increases in insulin like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) are believed to facilitate the up-regulation of BDNF in order to enhance neurogenesis and increase synaptic plasticity (Carro et al., 2001; Lista and Sorrentino, 2010). Moreover, IGF-1 has also been found to be associated with other growth factors following endurance-based exercise, including vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), thus stimulating angiogenesis (Lista and Sorrentino, 2010). Increased presence of IGF-1 may therefore facilitate in adaptations to CBF to augment cognitive function.

As exercise has been shown to have a beneficial impact on vascular function, some studies have focused on the relationship between cognitive function and exercise-induced improvements in vascular function (Figure 2 - 12). Firstly, as CBF increases during endurance exercise, it is believed to slow the progression of neuropathology within the brain, including the build-up of β -amyloid plaques (Mattsson et al., 2014), and therefore protecting the cerebrovascular environment. Furthermore, repeated increases in CBF from exercise augments the shear stress experienced by the cerebral vessels. One possibility is that endothelial function within the cerebral vasculature benefits from such processes, similar to the endothelial function, or FMD, of the brachial artery (Barnes and Corkery, 2018) as previous results have demonstrated a lack of age-associated decline in vasodilator function of the MCA in habitually exercising individuals (Miller et al., 2018). Recently, endurance-based exercise has also demonstrated improvements in processing speed and executive function in healthy older adults, possibly due to simultaneous reductions in regional arterial stiffness (Okamoto et al., 2019). Additionally, it has been shown in animal models that middle-aged exercising mice exhibit superior endothelial function, as well as improved structure and function of the cerebral vessels compared to their sedentary counterparts (Latimer et al., 2011; Leblond et al., 2013). As elevations in central arterial stiffness increase PP and cause cerebrovascular damage (Thorin-

Trescases et al., 2018), improvements in arterial stiffness may facilitate cognitive improvement by alleviating heightened PP, and thus reducing intracranial micro-vascular damage.

Although the primary objective of a number of previous studies was to assess the interaction between exercise and cognitive function, attempts have been made to elucidate the underlying mechanisms causing cognitive function to improve. Healthy postmenopausal females with $\dot{V}O_{2\max} > 90\%$ of their age-predicted maximum have demonstrated greater cerebrovascular conductance and lower mean arterial pressure within the MCA compared to their lesser fit counterparts. Furthermore, positive associations were observed between $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ and cognitive function, and MCA function during isocapnia were observed as predictors of cognitive function (Brown et al., 2010). More recently, Tarumi et al. (2015) reported that healthy endurance-trained middle-aged adults demonstrated superior cognitive function and BA FMD at the $P < 0.05$ level compared to similarly aged sedentary cohorts. Furthermore, positive associations between cognitive function and both, cerebrovascular reactivity and FMD measures were also reported, thus signifying that superior vascular function may augment cognitive abilities (Tarumi et al., 2015). Conversely, although positive associations between PA levels and cognitive function have also been reported in healthy community-dwelling middle-aged and older adults, cerebrovascular function was not found to mediate said associations (Gill et al., 2015; Guiney et al., 2019).

In addition to observational studies, 12 weeks of endurance training has increased CRF, CBF and cognitive function in healthy older adults (Chapman et al., 2013; Kleinloog et al., 2019). Whilst positive associations between CBF and cognitive function were seen in one study (Chapman et al., 2013), a second study did not assess for associations between the two

variables (Kleinloog et al., 2019). Additionally, 20 weeks of low and high intensity walking intervals improved carotid – femoral PWV and cognitive function in healthy older adults, with associations being present between the two (Okamoto et al., 2019). Whilst correlational data cannot determine causation, these data suggest that there is a link between exercise-induced improvements in intra- and extra-cranial vascular function, and consequent improvements in cognitive function.

Although some evidence exists in the literature to suggest that age-associated cognitive declines might be delayed as a result of exercise-induced improvements in peripheral and central vascular function, it is apparent that research connecting all factors within the same cohort is limited. Whilst studies have seen links between vascular and cognitive function, such associations have mostly been between intracranial vascular function and cognition. Consequently, no study has investigated the effects of exercise on local central extra-cranial vascular structure and function, brachial FMD, and cognition together within the same healthy ageing cohort. Moreover, no previous research has attempted to assess the possible link between vascular and cognitive function in healthy middle-aged and older adults after short-term resistance exercise training.

2.6 Overall Summary

Whilst ageing is associated with an increase in comorbidities and conditions, it is apparent that ageing is a non-modifiable risk factor that gradually plays a part in declining levels of systemic physical and neuropsychological health, even in apparently healthy individuals. Whilst non-modifiable risk factors including genetics may influence the rate at which an individual experiences age-associated declines in health, lifestyle factors play an

important role in the rate at which one experiences ageing. The present literature informs that there are large volumes of evidence to support the use of PA and exercise to reduce age-associated declines in vascular and cognitive health in healthy older adults.

Many studies have assessed the influence of long- and shorter-term exercise on vascular and cognitive health with ageing. However, fewer have assessed multiple factors within the same cohort. Although it is often suggested that engagement in PA and exercise may delay the ageing-associated cognitive decline process by preventing decline or augmenting vascular function, such assumptions are speculative until firm evidence is available to determine whether the highlighted physiological and neuropsychological factors are, in fact, linked in ageing. Thus, further research is required to investigate the possible link between exercise-mediated improvements in vascular function, and possible subsequent improvements in cognitive function in a healthy older cohort. Whilst many studies include participants with health conditions and various comorbidities, it is important to consider the inclusion of healthy disease-free cohorts in an attempt to assess the direct link of exercise on cognitive and vascular function on healthy ageing.

2.7 Thesis Aims and Hypotheses

2.7.1 Study 1

Aim 1: Assess whether brachial artery endothelial function, as assessed via FMD, is superior in healthy long-term endurance exercise-trained older adults compared to age-matched untrained individuals

Aim 2: Determine whether short-term endurance-based interventions improve brachial artery FMD in previously sedentary healthy older adults

Hypothesis 1: Healthy long-term endurance-trained adults would exhibit superior brachial artery FMD compared to their sedentary counterparts,

Hypothesis 2: Short-term endurance intervention would improve brachial artery FMD at the $P < 0.05$ level in healthy older previously sedentary adults

2.7.2 Study 2

Aim 1: To identify whether vascular and cognitive function are superior in mixed-sex masters athletes compared to a healthy untrained older cohort

Aim 2: Determine if associations between vascular and cognitive function exist

Aim 3: Investigate the extent that vascular and cognitive function of masters athletes and an untrained healthy older cohort differ from a young inactive cohort

Hypothesis 1: The masters athletes would exhibit superior vascular and cognitive function compared to their untrained counterparts

Hypothesis 2: Associations would be present between vascular and cognitive function

Hypothesis 3: The young inactive cohort would have better vascular and cognitive function compared to the older untrained group

2.7.3 Study 3

Aim 1: Investigate whether physically active healthy middle-aged females exhibited superior vascular FMD, structure, blood flow, and cognitive function compared to their age-matched inactive counterparts

Aim 2: Determine whether CCA speckle tracking-derived compliance measures are superior in the active versus the inactive cohort

Aim 3: Establish whether differences in CCA compliance exist between groups when measured pre, during and immediately after a 3-minute isometric hand-grip exercise

Aim 4: Assess whether associations are present between vascular and cognitive variables

Hypothesis 1: Physically active healthy middle-aged females exhibited superior vascular FMD, structure, blood flow, and cognitive function compared to their age-matched inactive counterparts

Hypothesis 2: CCA speckle-tracking-derived compliance measures will be superior in the active when compared to the inactive middle-aged females

Hypothesis 3: CCA compliance will also be superior in the active group when assessed during and immediately after a 3-minute isometric hand-grip exercise

Hypothesis 4: Improvements in cognitive function would be associated with superior central and peripheral vascular function

2.7.4 Study 4

Aim 1: Assess the influence of 12 weeks of low-frequency, high-intensity resistance training on FMD, and the vascular structure and blood flow of previously sedentary healthy middle-aged females

Aim 2: Identify whether the resistance training intervention could positively influence cognitive function

Aim 3: Determine whether CCA speckle tracking-derived compliance measures were superior after the resistance training intervention

Aim 4: Establish whether differences in CCA strain exist between visits when measured pre, during and immediately after a 3-minute isometric hand-grip exercise

Aim 5: Identify whether potential changes in vascular and cognitive function are linked

Hypothesis 1: 12 weeks of resistance training would benefit FMD, and the vascular structure and blood flow of previously sedentary healthy middle-aged females

Hypothesis 2: 12 weeks of resistance training would improve cognitive function in the health middle-aged female cohort

Hypothesis 3: CCA speckle-tracking-derived compliance measures would be superior after the 12 week resistance training intervention

Hypothesis 4: CCA compliance would be superior after the 12 week resistance training intervention when assessed alongside a 3-minute isometric hand-grip exercise

Hypothesis 5: Improvements in vascular function would be linked with improvements in cognitive function.

CHAPTER 3

LONG-TERM AEROBIC EXERCISE IMPROVES VASCULAR FUNCTION INTO OLD AGE: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW, META-ANALYSIS AND META REGRESSION OF OBSERVATIONAL AND INTERVENTIONAL STUDIES

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3.1 Introduction

Impaired vascular vasodilatory capacity as a result of ageing occurs due to the coalition of environment, oxidative stress, and inflammation (Donato et al., 2007; Seals et al., 2011). These factors result in reduced nitric oxide (NO) bioavailability, causing a failure of the vasculature to dilate in response to increases in shear stress during hyperaemia (Taddei et al., 2000, 2001; Viridis et al., 2010). Furthermore, vascular structure is also compromised with age as wall stiffness increases, reducing flexibility. Therefore, vascular dysfunction promotes cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk and contributes both to a reduction in health span and overall life expectancy (Roger et al., 2012). Given this premise, there is an increasingly important but unmet need for interventions that aim to reduce inflammation and oxidative stress while developing an environment conducive to vascular function (Seals et al., 2009).

Modifiable lifestyle factors, such as increased physical activity (PA) and/or exercise have been advocated to reduce vascular impairment and restore NO-dependent vasodilatation, even in apparently healthy older cohorts (Taddei et al., 2000; Grace et al., 2015). Multiple lines of evidence, including both human and pre-clinical models demonstrate that those individuals who are regularly active enjoy a superior vascular vasodilatory capacity, with lower levels of systemic inflammation and oxidative stress (Eskurza et al., 2004; Lesniewski et al., 2013; Seals, 2014; Grace et al., 2015). Despite this, more than 1 in 4 of all adults, and 85 to 90 % of older adults in developed countries fail to meet the PA guidelines to maintain cardiovascular health (Sparling et al., 2015; The World Health Organisation, 2017). This represents a contemporary challenge for researchers and healthcare providers to provide evidence-based strategies to improve engagement with PA, and to improve vascular function in older adults as a primary therapeutic target (World Health Organisation, 2011).

Vascular function, or specifically endothelial function, is commonly assessed non-invasively using the flow mediated dilation (FMD) technique. As cardiovascular events can be independently predicted by endothelial compliance, FMD has emerged as a conventional method to determine endothelial vasodilatory capacity (Inaba et al., 2010). Although assessment of whole vascular function includes measures of arterial stiffness, FMD is specific to measuring endothelial function whereby endothelial NO contributes to the vasodilation of vessels after a temporary occlusion of blood flow (Green et al., 2014). However, there are few systematic interrogations of literature examining vascular function of healthy older adults, and those that have been performed, while well executed, have key limitations. For example, Ashor et al. (2015) and Early et al. (2017) reported that exercise training improved brachial artery FMD in healthy and diseased cohorts, but in both cases, data pooling mixed young and old participants, preventing direct assessment of the effect of exercise on FMD exclusively in older individuals. Moreover, since disease may superimpose additional vascular dysfunction on top of ageing alone, it is unclear whether exercise improves FMD due to direct effects of disease, on age *per se*, or a combination of the two. A further review by Montero et al. (2014) identified that exercise trained adults had displayed superior BA FMD compared to their untrained counterparts. However, this review compared trained and untrained adults and did not address the effects of training programmes on FMD in older adults. Moreover, their inclusion criteria encompassed studies of both middle and old age cohorts. Given that the beneficial effects of exercise may reduce with increasing age, it is difficult to interpret the results of Montero et al. (2014) in an exclusively older population.

Consequently, no meta-analysis has assessed the degree to which older (> 60 years) trained individuals may have greater indices of FMD than their untrained counterparts.

Equally, there are no meta-analyses assessing the effectiveness of exercise or PA interventions in improving FMD in similarly aged, but otherwise healthy adults. Unpicking the relationships between FMD, ageing, and exercise is necessary to enable evidence-based proposals to support health in old age. Therefore, given these gaps in the literature, the aim of this systematic review and meta-analysis was to address the following questions:

- (i) Do longer-term trained older persons have more favourable vascular function, as determined by FMD, than age-matched sedentary controls?
- (ii) Do short-term endurance-based exercise training interventions improve vascular function in previously sedentary but healthy older individuals?

3.2. Methods

The current systematic review and meta-analysis was conducted in accordance with the 2009 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) checklist, and the 2000 Meta-analysis Of Observational Studies in Epidemiology checklist (Stroup et al., 2000; Moher et al., 2010).

3.2.1 Search strategy

An electronic database search was conducted to identify relevant exercise studies using FMD to determine the endothelial vasodilatory capacity of older healthy exercising and sedentary adults. PubMed/MEDLINE (abstract/title), Web of Science (title only), and ScienceDirect (abstract/title/keywords) online databases were searched, and all studies from inception to the date searched (January 2018) were included. The search string included

(brachial artery flow mediated dila* OR vasodilation OR vascular function OR vascular reactivity OR vascular health OR endothelial function OR brachial artery) AND (exercise OR train* OR physical activity OR untrain* OR fitness OR program*). Filters were applied to ensure that only records in English with human participants were included in the search results. Reference lists from eligible articles were reviewed to search for additional relevant studies which may not have been present during the database search, before being subsequently screened for potential inclusion into the meta-analysis.

3.2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria consisted of: (1) non-pharmacological studies of male and female human participants; (2) aged 60 years and over, and (3) employing either cross-sectional, cohort or randomised control trial (RCT) study designs. (4) Cross-sectional design studies had to have an aged-matched control group, while in the aerobic exercise intervention, studies both pre and post-intervention (cohort) or RCT designs were included. (5) Studies had to include physically healthy cohorts comprising of sedentary individuals for intervention studies, or regular exercisers and sedentary individuals for cross-sectional studies. (6) Vascular function was determined using endothelium-dependent FMD of the BA using valid ultrasonic techniques and occlusion of the lower arm. (7) Studies must have also been published in English language literature. FMD was used as the main measure of vascular function as it is the most widely used non-invasive assessment of endothelial function, and thus gives an accurate representation of endothelial health. As FMD can predict vascular events within asymptomatic persons, it can identify impairments in endothelial vasodilatory capacity within healthy older adults. There was no limitation imposed on the method of subsequent analysis, thus studies using either fixed post-deflation time points or continuous edge detection methods

were included. Other measures of vascular function such as pulse wave velocity (PWV) were not included within the meta-analysis as we were specifically interested in measuring endothelial function, rather than arterial stiffness. However, since arterial diameter has been suggested as a potential confounder when assessing FMD (Atkinson and Batterham, 2015) we included analysis of this structural measure. There were also no limitations regarding the length, duration, or intensity of exercise interventions.

Studies were excluded if they (i) used pharmacological stimulus, (ii) assessed a single acute exercise bout (iii) assessed resistance interventions only, or (iv) assessed vascular function using a method other than FMD. In addition, (v) studies that occluded the upper arm during the FMD protocol were also excluded as this can cause a greater vasodilatory response after ischemia, possibly from mechanisms other than NO (Berry et al., 2000). As the current study aimed to assess the vasodilatory capacity of the vascular endothelium as a measure of vascular function, only lower arm occlusion was included as the post occlusion vasodilation is mainly NO-mediated, and more representative of endothelium function (Doshi et al., 2001; Green et al., 2011). For example, there is evidence that increases in arterial diameter as a result of hyperaemic shear are abolished in the presence of a selective blockage of NO production within lower arm occlusion, but not upper arm occlusion (Doshi et al., 2001). We therefore excluded studies that occluded the upper arm during the FMD protocol as this method causes a greater ischemic response which may not be exclusively due to NO, and thus endothelial function. Furthermore, including lower arm occlusion also helped to standardise the FMD protocol between the included studies.

3.2.3 Study Selection

The literature search and selection of studies was performed by authors AC and AB. Following an initial screen of titles and abstracts (AC), full scrutiny of potentially eligible studies was independently screened by AC and AB using the specific inclusion criteria. NS arbitrated any disagreements in study inclusion.

3.2.4 Data Extraction

Data from the final list of eligible studies were extracted and entered into a spreadsheet (Microsoft Excel 2010). Extracted data included the following for all participant groups in each study: (1) participant ages, (2) participant activity status, (3) participant maximum oxygen uptake ($\dot{V}O_{2\max}$), (4) sample size, (5) study type, (6) intervention type, frequency, duration and intensity (for interventional studies), (7) relative BA FMD percentage change (Δ FMD %), (8) BA baseline diameter (mm, when reported), (9) endothelial independent vasodilation (EIDV) (% when measured), (10) supervised and non-supervised interventions, (11) shear rate/stress (when measured) and (12) details of FMD protocols. When studies reported both cross-sectional and interventional data from their analysis, each was screened individually to determine their eligibility. Given the suggestions of morphological adaptations in response to training (Green et al., 2012), we also sought to examine structural changes. Arterial diameter was extracted from studies to determine whether structural adaptations also occurred as a result of exercise. As arterial hyperaemic response is influenced by baseline diameter, extracting arterial diameter may help to understand why some studies show an increase in FMD or not.

Δ FMD % data were extracted as the main outcome variable. If not reported, Δ FMD % was calculated as: $[(\text{post occlusive peak BA diameter} - \text{baseline BA diameter})/$

(*baseline BA diameter*) * 100], where post occlusive diameter was the peak artery diameter which occurred following cuff deflation, and baseline was the diameter determined at rest. All data were entered as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). When studies reported standard error of the mean (SEM), conversion to SD was performed using the equation $SD = SEM * \sqrt{N}$, where N was the number of participants. Authors of several eligible studies were contacted by email when data were not available from the text, figures, or tables. Where authors failed to respond, mean and standard deviation were extracted from graphs using the calibrated measuring function within the software 'ImageJ' (Image Processing and Analysis in Java, Maryland, USA) (Abramoff et al., 2004).

3.2.5 Study Quality Assessment

Appraisal of study quality was undertaken using an assessment tool established by the National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute (NHLBI, Bethesda, MD). Individual quality assessment tools specific to the RCT, cohort, and cross-sectional study designs were used and subsequently classified as good, fair, or poor (NHLBI, 2014a, 2014b, 2014c).

3.2.6 Statistical analysis

All study data were analysed using the Comprehensive Meta-Analysis software (Biostat: V 2.2.064, Englewood, NJ, USA). Data were entered in accordance with the research questions: (1) Δ FMD % of sedentary participants compared with those who were long-term trained; and (2) pre and post Δ FMD % of previously sedentary participants who had completed an exercise intervention.

The meta-analysis calculated the mean difference (MD) of BA Δ FMD %, BA diameter (mm) and BA EIDV (%) between the long-term trained versus sedentary participants (question 1) and pre to post-intervention in sedentary participants (question 2). A meta-analysis comparing the Δ FMD % of supervised and non-supervised interventions was also included within the analysis. Pooled data were analysed using a random effects model, and differences in means in a positive direction represented an increase in FMD, baseline diameter and EIDV in favour of exercise, whereas a negative direction indicated a decrease. Between study heterogeneity was calculated for each study question, and reported as Cochran's Q and I^2 , with variability of measurement characterised as low, medium or high as 25 %, 50 % and 75 %, respectively (Higgins et al., 2003). A method of moments mixed effects meta-regression was conducted to determine if age moderated the effect on Δ FMD % at the $P < 0.05$ level. Publication bias was assessed by Egger's regression. All data are presented as mean \pm SD, and a $P \leq 0.05$ level was chosen.

Figure 3 - 1. PRISMA flow chart of study selection from the original search on PubMed, Web of Science, and ScienceDirect.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Study selection

Following the literature search from all three databases, 3199 records were identified after the removal of duplicates. Based on the title and abstracts, 3132 records were excluded, primarily due to the inclusion of participant morbidity. With the inclusion of 1 study from an external source following reference list examination, full texts of the remaining 68 articles were screened in accordance with the study inclusion and exclusion criteria. Fifty-five studies were excluded for the following reasons: non-reporting of scaling used in FMD analysis (n = 1); occlusion of the upper arm during the FMD protocol (n = 3); no intervention group (n=1); no sedentary group (n = 2); participants were under 60 years of age (n = 11); participants were unhealthy (n = 2); FMD was not used (n = 6); BA FMD was not performed (n = 1); conference abstract only (n = 26) and no full text available (n = 2). Consequently, 13 studies were deemed eligible for analysis. One study consisted of both an intervention and a cross-sectional design and analysis, however only the cross-sectional section met all inclusion criteria (Pierce et al., 2011b). Additionally, one of the interventional studies contained both baseline and post-intervention data and was therefore included in both comparisons (Grace et al., 2015). As a result, the overall analysis contained 10 cross-sectional (Jensen-Urstad et al., 1999; Eskurza et al., 2004, 2005; Franzoni et al., 2005; Galetta et al., 2006; Walker et al., 2009; Pierce et al., 2011a, 2011b; DeVan et al., 2013; Grace et al., 2015) and four interventional studies (Thijssen et al., 2007; Klonizakis et al., 2014; Suboc et al., 2014; Grace et al., 2015) (Figure 3 - 1). The included studies were believed to be mainly of ‘good’ quality as measured using the National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute study quality assessment criteria (Tables 3 - 1 to 3 - 5).

The cross-sectional and interventional analyses were found to have moderate and low heterogeneity ($I^2 = 63.6\%$; $P = 0.003$ and $I^2 = 47.4$; $P = 0.12$, respectively). To compensate for the heterogeneity identified, the meta-analysis was conducted using random effect models, as recommended by the Cochrane guidelines (Higgins and Green, 2011).

Table 3 - 1. Cross-Sectional Studies Characteristics.

Study	Training Status	N	Age (years)	% Male	Physical Activity Levels	$\dot{V}O_{2max}$ (ml.kg.min ⁻¹)	FMD % Change	Overall Findings	Study Quality
DeVan et al. (2013)	Trained	23	62 ± 4	91	> 45 min day ⁻¹ , ≥ 5 days week ⁻¹ for previous 2 years.	($\dot{V}O_{2peak}$): 42.0 ± 9.6	6.4 ± 1.7	↑ Trained	Fair
	Sedentary	35	62 ± 5	86	< 30 min day ⁻¹ , ≤ 2 days per week for previous 2 years.	($\dot{V}O_{2peak}$): 31.0 ± 5.9	5.3 ± 2.2		
Eskurza et al. (2005)	Trained	12	66 ± 4	100	> 3 sessions week ⁻¹ of vigorous endurance exercise > 2 years.	41.3 ± 4.2	5.9 ± 1.7	↑ Trained	Good
	Sedentary	9	62 ± 6	100	No regular PA > 2 years.	29.1 ± 6.3	3.9 ± 2.1		
Franzoni et al. (2005)	Trained	16	64 ± 6	100	$\dot{V}O_{2max}$ > 50 ml.kg.min ⁻¹ . Vigorous endurance exercise > 5 times week ⁻¹ & participate in national & international road-running races. Training for 37 ± 5 years.	54.7 ± 3.7	5.3 ± 3.2	↑ Trained	Good
	Sedentary	16	64 ± 4	100	$\dot{V}O_{2max}$ < 45 ml.kg.min ⁻¹	28.0 ± 5.9	2.3 ± 1.0		
Galetta et al. (2006)	Trained	30	65 ± 5	100	$\dot{V}O_{2max}$ > 40 ml.kg.min ⁻¹ Competitive endurance runners for 40 years. 1-2hour day ⁻¹ for 5 days (3 days long distance running & 2 days walk-weight training) or 5 – 10 km weekly or 20 km once every 2 weeks.	45.7 ± 3.7	6.2 ± 2.0	↑ Trained	Good
	Sedentary	28	66 ± 6	100	$\dot{V}O_{2max}$ < 35 ml.kg.min ⁻¹ and no regular exercise	28.0 ± 5.9	2.4 ± 1.5		

Study	Training Status	N	Age (years)	% Male	Physical Activity Levels	$\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ (ml.kg.min ⁻¹)	FMD % Change	Overall Findings	Study Quality
Grace et al. (2015)	Trained	17	61 ± 5	100	Life-long exercisers and completed on average 280 min exercise training week ⁻¹ . Most participants were active competing in endurance sports.	39.2 ± 5.6	5.4 ± 1.4	↑ Trained	Good
	Sedentary	22	63 ± 5	100	No formal exercise programme for ≥ 30years.	27.2 ± 5.2	3.4 ± 1.5		
Jensen-Urstad et al. (1999)	Trained	9	75 ± 3	100	Participants had been and were still among the best in their respective age groups in running since ages of 15-25. Between 3 - 7 hours strenuous exercise week ⁻¹ .	41.0 ± 7.0	4.8 ± 5.0	↑ Trained	Good
	Sedentary	11	75 ± 2	100	Sedentary or moderately active.	27.0 ± 5.0	1.1 ± 2.1		
Pierce et al. (2011a)	Trained	13	62 ± 7	100	Vigorous aerobic exercise (competitive running, cycling and triathlons) ≥ 5 days.week ⁻¹ for ≥ 45min day ⁻¹ > 5 years.	42.0 ± 3.6	6.3 ± 1.8	↑ Trained	Good
	Sedentary	28	63 ± 5	100	No regular aerobic exercise (< 30 min day ⁻¹ , < 2 days week ⁻¹ , ≥ 2 years).	29.0 ± 5.3	4.9 ± 2.1		

Study	Training Status	N	Age (years)	% Male	Physical Activity Levels	$\dot{V}O_{2max}$ (ml.kg.min ⁻¹)	FMD % Change	Overall Findings	Study Quality
Pierce et al. (2011a)	Trained	65	62 ± 6	69	Vigorous aerobic exercise (competitive running, cycling and triathlons) > 5 days week ⁻¹ for > 45 min day ⁻¹ > 5 years.	41.5 ± 7.7	6.1 ± 2.9	↑ Trained	Good
	Sedentary	102	62 ± 10	59	No regular aerobic exercise (< 30 min day ⁻¹ , < 2 days week ⁻¹ , > 2 years).	27.4 ± 6.6	4.8 ± 2.3		
Walker et al. (2009)	Trained	16	66 ± 4	100	> 3 sessions week ⁻¹ vigorous aerobic endurance exercise.	42.8 ± 5.2	6.2 ± 2.6	→	Good
	Sedentary	15	66 ± 4	100	No regular exercise for 2 years	29.9 ± 4.7	4.8 ± 1.6		
Eskurza et al. (2004)	Trained	9	64 ± 6	100	> 3 sessions week ⁻¹ vigorous aerobic endurance exercise for ≥ 2 years	40.0 ± 6.0	7.0 ± 1.8	↑ Trained	Good
	Sedentary	9	64 ± 6	100	Sedentary (No regular PA) for ≥ 2 years	32.0 ± 3.0	4.6 ± 0.6		

Study characteristics of cross-sectional studies within question 1 (↑ identifies that an increase in FMD % change occurred at the $P < 0.05$ level, and → identifies no change ($P > 0.05$)). N, number of participants; % Male, percentage of male participants; $\dot{V}O_{2max}$, maximum aerobic capacity; FMD% change, flow mediated dilation percentage change; PA, physical activity. Values are displayed as mean ± standard deviations.

Table 3 - 2. Interventional Study Characteristics

Study	Study Design	N	Age (years)	% Male	Exercise Intervention								Overall Findings	Study Quality
					Exercise Type	Intensity	Session Duration	Frequency	Study Duration	$\dot{V}O_{2max}$ (ml.kg.min ⁻¹)	FMD % Change			
Thijssen et al. (2007)	Cohort	8	70 ± 1	100	Cycling training on an ergometer	65 % HRR & gradually increasing by 5 % until 85 %	20min	3 days week ⁻¹	8 weeks	Pre: 30.8 ± 4.8 Post: 33.3 ± 5.5	Pre: 6.9 ± 3.4 Post: 6.4 ± 2.7	→ FMD %	Good	
Suboc et al. (2014)	RCT	77	PED: 64 ± 7 CON: 62 ± 7	PED: 61 CON: 76	PED (n=36) walking CON (n=41)	Increase PA by 10 % weekly above baseline to reach an average of 10,000 steps day ⁻¹	---	Daily	12 weeks	---	Post; CON: 6.3 ± 2.7 HIT: 6.7 ± 3.9	→ FMD %	Good	
Klonizakis et al. (2014)	Cohort	18	HIT: 64 ± 7 CT: 64 ± 4	0	HIT (n=11): cycling intervals on ergometer CT (n=7): continuous cycling	HIT: 100 % PP & light active recovery intervals at 30W CT: 65 % PP	HIIT: 10 x 1 min intervals with 1 min recovery between each CT: 40 min	3 times week ⁻¹	2 weeks	HIT; Pre: 20.4 ± 3.4 Post: 22.6 ± 3.1 CT; Pre: 25.0 ± 7.4 Post: 26.7 ± 5.4	HIT; Pre: 8.1 ± 7.2 Post: 6.5 ± 3.7 CT; Pre: 8.9 ± 7.9 Post: 7 ± 4.3	→ FMD % → FMD %	Good	

Study	Study Design	N	Age (years)	% Male	Exercise Intervention				Study Duration	$\dot{V}O_{2max}$ (ml.kg.min ⁻¹)	FMD % Change	Overall Findings	Study Quality
					Exercise Type	Intensity	Session Duration	Frequency					
Grace et al. (2015)	Cohort	2	63 ± 5.2	100	Progressive conditioning exercise: ACSM guidelines HIIT: sprints on cycle ergometer.	Conditioning exercise: ACSM guidelines (Chodzko-Zajko et al., 2009) & 50 % PP HIIT sprints	Conditioning exercise: 150min week ⁻¹ ≥ 30 min day ⁻¹ (ACSM guidelines (Chodzko-Zajko et al., 2009)) HIIT: 6 x 30 s sprints with 3 min break between each	Conditioning : ≥ 5 days week ⁻¹ (ACSM guidelines (Chodzko-Zajko et al., 2009)) HIIT: once every 5 days	Conditioning: 6 weeks HIIT: 6 weeks	Pre: 27.2 ± 5.2 Post: 32.2 ± 5.6	Pre: 3.4 ± 1.5 Post: 5.4 ± 1.4	↑ FMD %	Good

↑ identifies an increase in FMD % change at the $P < 0.05$ level, and → identifies no change ($P > 0.05$). N, number of participants; % Male, percentage of male participants; $\dot{V}O_{2max}$, maximum aerobic capacity; $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$, peak aerobic capacity; FMD % change, flow mediated dilation percentage change; PA, physical activity; HRR, heart rate reserve; WR_{max} , maximum work rate; PP, peak power; HIT, high intensity training; CT, continuous training; ACSM, American College of Sports Medicine; HIIT, high intensity interval training; PED, pedometer; CON, control. Values are displayed as means ± standard deviations.

3.3.2 Question 1: Cross-sectional Study Analysis

The 10 cross-sectional studies included 485 participants (210 long-term trained and 275 sedentary) (Jensen-Urstad et al., 1999; Eskurza et al., 2004, 2005; Franzoni et al., 2005; Galetta et al., 2006; Walker et al., 2009; Pierce et al., 2011a, 2011b; DeVan et al., 2013; Grace et al., 2015). Ages ranged from 62 to 75 years in the sedentary participants (mean of 65 years) and from 61 to 75 years in the long-term trained participants (mean of 65 years). Cohort sizes ranged from $n = 9$ to $n = 65$ participants in the long-term trained and $n = 9$ to $n = 102$ in the sedentary groups. Seven of the long-term trained groups and five of the sedentary groups contained less than 20 participants (Jensen-Urstad et al., 1999; Eskurza et al., 2005; Franzoni et al., 2005; Walker et al., 2009; Pierce et al., 2011a; Grace et al., 2015). Two of the 10 studies contained both male and female participants (Pierce et al., 2011b; DeVan et al., 2013). Studies with both males and females were included as it has previously been identified that postmenopausal females display a similar BA FMD compared to males of the same age (Jensen-Urstad and Johansson, 2001). Additionally, as only one study presented male and female data individually, results for each sex were analysed together. This was made possible as the authors also presented the data for males and females together, in addition to being split by sex (Pierce et al., 2011b). Long-term trained participants consisted of endurance runners, swimmers and cyclists who trained at least three times per week and with regular exercise participation between 2 and 37 years (Table 3 - 1).

Studies described cuff occlusion pressures to range from 40 mmHg above systolic blood pressure to 300 mmHg and remained inflated between four and five minutes. Δ FMD % was analysed from all 10 cross-sectional studies and ranged from $4.8 \pm 5 \%$ to $7 \pm 1.8 \%$ in the long-term trained participants and $1.1 \pm 2.1 \%$ to $5.3 \pm 2.2 \%$ in sedentary participants. Δ FMD

% values normalised for shear stress were reported in one study (Eskurza et al., 2005), and for hyperaemic shear in one other (Eskurza et al., 2004). All 10 cross-sectional studies reported mean baseline BA diameter data, whereas only nine studies reported EIDV data.

Data pooling from the meta-analysis indicated that Δ FMD % was greater at the $P < 0.05$ level in long-term trained, versus sedentary older adults (MD: 2.1 %, 95 % CI: 1.4 %, 2.8 %; $P < 0.001$; Figure 3 - 2). Moderate heterogeneity was observed between the 10 cross-sectional studies ($I^2 = 63.6$ %; $P = 0.003$). Egger's regression determined that there was a low risk of publication bias ($P = 0.700$). The meta-regression found no effect of age on Δ FMD% ($P = 0.080$; Table 3 - 6). Data pooling identified that EIDV was not different at the $P < 0.05$ level between the trained and untrained participants (MD: 1.57 %; 95 % CI: -0.13 %, 3.27 %; $P = 0.070$; Figure 3 - 4), and baseline diameter of the BA was also similar between the two groups (MD: -0.10 mm; 95 % CI: -0.09 mm, 0.29 mm; $P = 0.310$; Figure 3 - 3).

3.3.3 Question 2: Intervention study analysis

The 4 intervention studies consisted of three cohort designs (Thijssen et al., 2007; Klonizakis et al., 2014; Grace et al., 2015) and one RCT (Suboc et al., 2014). Included in the four studies were 125 sedentary participants. Sample sizes ranged from eight to 77 participants, where two of the studies contained less than 20 participants (Thijssen et al., 2007; Klonizakis et al., 2014). The ages of participants ranged from 62 ± 7 to 70 ± 1 years, with a mean age of 65 years. One of the studies contained both male and female participants (Suboc et al., 2014), and one study recruited only postmenopausal females (Klonizakis et al., 2014). Again, as the study containing both males and females did not present their results separately, data for each sex were analysed together (Table 3 - 2).

Cuff inflation during the FMD protocol ranged from 50 mmHg above systolic blood pressure to approximately 220 mmHg for a 5 minute period. The duration of study interventions lasted between approximately nine to 84 sessions from two to 12 weeks, with three of the studies including exercise interventions of a moderate to high intensity. One of the cohort studies included two separate interventions; one consisting of high intensity, and the other a moderate intensity intervention (Klonizakis et al., 2014). The frequency of interventions ranged from once every five days to seven days per week and lasting between 20 minutes to one hour per day.

For the cohort studies Δ FMD % was calculated from baseline and post measures, while post-intervention and control values were analysed in the RCT study. Δ FMD% ranged from 3.4 ± 1.5 % to 8.9 ± 7.9 % pre-intervention to 5.4 ± 1.4 % and 7 ± 4.3 % post-intervention. All four of the studies reported baseline BA diameter data, whilst only two studies reported data for EIDV.

The meta-analysis suggests that there was no improvement in Δ FMD % at the $P < 0.05$ level after the exercise interventions in previously sedentary older adults (MD: 0.71 %, 95 % CI: -0.68 %, 2.10 %; $P = 0.320$; Figure 3 - 2). The heterogeneity of the five intervention studies was calculated as low ($I^2 = 47.4$ %, $P = 0.107$), and Egger's regression determined that some publication bias may be present ($P = 0.047$). The meta-analysis identified that there was no increase in EIDV from pre to post-intervention (MD: 1.48 %; 95 % CI: -1.30 %, 4.30 %; $P=0.303$; Figure 3 - 4), however there was an increase in BA baseline diameter post-intervention (MD: 0.10 mm; 95% CI: 0.07 mm, 0.13 mm $P < 0.001$; Figure 3 - 3). Finally,

Δ FMD % was not affected by whether the interventions were supervised or non-supervised (heterogeneity $p = 0.927$; Figure 3 - 5).

Figure 3 - 2. Forest plot of the meta-analysis with mean differences of FMD percentage change between trained vs. sedentary healthy older adults (question 1), and FMD percentage change pre to post exercise intervention in previously sedentary healthy older adults (question two). Outcomes of questions one, two, and the moderator analysis are also presented.

Figure 3 - 3. Forest plot of the meta-analysis of brachial artery baseline diameter (mm) between trained vs. sedentary healthy older adults, and pre to post exercise intervention in previously sedentary healthy older adults. The heterogeneity and moderator analysis are also presented.

Figure 3 - 4. Forest plot of the meta-analysis of endothelial independent vasodilation percentage change (EIDV %) between trained vs. sedentary healthy older adults, and pre to post exercise intervention in previously sedentary healthy older adults. The heterogeneity and moderator analysis are also presented.

Figure 3 - 5. Forest plot of the meta-analysis of brachial artery FMD percentage change within supervised and non-supervised exercise interventions. Heterogeneity and moderator analysis are also presented.

3.4. Discussion

This systematic review and meta-analysis set out to determine the effects of short and long-term exercise training on BA FMD and has two main findings. First, pooled data from cross-sectional studies demonstrate that long-term trained healthy older adults have superior FMD compared with their sedentary but otherwise healthy counterparts; and second that FMD may not improve in sedentary individuals who undertake shorter-term aerobic exercise interventions although there may be an increase in arterial diameter. These data are the first pooled synthesis of controlled observational and interventional studies using healthy older cohorts. The current meta-analysis also allows some comparison between observational and interventional studies since we used the same inclusion and exclusion criteria for studies in both comparisons. Moreover, since all participants were apparently healthy and not taking any medication, the results may provide some insight into the effect of short and long-term training on ageing *per se* rather than on ageing in combination with comorbidities. The current study therefore differs from previous meta-analyses which combined healthy and diseased participants, or mixed middle aged and older participants together in their analysis (Montero et al., 2014; Ashor et al., 2015; Early et al., 2017). Therefore, to our knowledge, the current study is the first meta-analysis to identify BA FMD exclusively in healthy adults aged 60 years and over who are either endurance-trained or untrained or who have completed an endurance intervention having previously been sedentary.

3.4.1 Question 1 – Do long-term trained older individuals demonstrate superior vascular function, as determined by FMD, than age matched sedentary controls?

As outlined above, the meta-analysis indicated that endurance exercise training is associated with improved FMD, despite considerable differences in study designs. Indeed,

within these 10 studies, there was a wide range in prior exercise experience, with trained cohorts ranging from a minimum of two years training through to life-long exercisers and which may have contributed to the heterogeneity in this comparison.

Nevertheless, these data indicate that exercise provides a protective mechanism in long-term trained participants, who experience a slower deterioration of FMD, compared with sedentary but otherwise healthy older adults. While the protective mechanism of exercise remains to be fully elucidated it is widely believed that the hyperaemic effects of exercise, and the repeated exposure of the endothelium to bouts of increased shear stress, act to reduce the deleterious effects of inflammation and oxidative stress (Tinken et al., 2010). The combination of these effects enhances the bioavailability of NO, increasing vasodilation during the hyperaemic response following an ischaemic stimulus (Taddei et al., 2000). From the data presented it appears that the vasculature of healthy older long-term trained adults may be exposed to these physiological mechanisms at a level that preserves FMD relative to their sedentary counterparts.

Previous work has suggested that trained individuals have shown to exhibit wider peripheral artery diameters when compared to untrained individuals. Often referred to as the athlete's artery, it is thought to represent arterial remodelling in response to repeated bouts of shear stress which occur during exercise. It is hypothesised that a widened vessel requires less vasodilation during periods of reactive hyperaemia, resulting in reduced dilatation during FMD (Green et al., 2012, 2013). However, the analysis of long-term trained athletes, in whom any such adaptation may be greatest fails to support this concept since arterial diameters of the trained individuals did not differ from the sedentary cohort. Nevertheless, the present meta-

analysis identified that the trained group had a greater FMD compared to the untrained group, whilst both displaying a similar baseline artery diameter (Figure 3 - 3). These findings agree with a meta-analysis by Montero et al. (2014) who identified that masters athletes BA diameters were similar to untrained controls, whilst FMD was also greater.

The meta-regression aimed to identify if increasing age reduced the improvement in FMD seen in trained individuals compared to sedentary controls. In this case, the lack of an association indicated that the difference between the two cohorts was not reduced with advancing age. Therefore, the present findings underline the notion that exercise can support FMD, well into the eighth decade (Grace et al., 2015). It is also notable, that most (Walker et al., 2009; Pierce et al., 2011a; DeVan et al., 2013), but not all (Franzoni et al., 2005), previous work has demonstrated that the FMD of healthy young untrained adults is greater than older trained adults. These data suggest that, even in well-trained individuals, there may be some unavoidable decrement in FMD with age. In addition, the range in mean ages of the included observational studies was relatively narrow (62 to 75 years); future research should attempt to determine if improvements in FMD are maintained in those who participate in long-term endurance exercise.

3.4.2 Question 2 – Do exercise training interventions improve FMD in previously sedentary healthy older persons?

The results of observational studies support the use of exercise to ameliorate the age-related decline in FMD. However, as is the case in all observational studies, the inability to directly link the main outcome (i.e., FMD) to the exposure of interest (i.e., exercise training) limits the confidence that may be placed in conclusions from such studies (Higgins and Green,

2011). In an attempt to overcome this, the present review further assessed the effectiveness of prospective aerobic intervention studies with otherwise sedentary participants.

Data pooling indicated that the short-term training programmes within the included studies (2 to 12 weeks) did not improve FMD at the $P < 0.05$ level. This finding is at odds with the results of the cross-sectional assessment of endurance-trained participants and controls reported above. However, the training interventions were associated with an increase in diameter of the BA at baseline at the $P < 0.05$ level (i.e., immediately prior to cuff inflation; Figure 3 - 3). Since included studies were not mechanistic in nature, assessing the lack of effect is speculative. For example, it may be that in this age group the recovery of endothelial function is slow and vascular remodelling (i.e., “the athlete’s artery”) becomes a primary method of adaptation (Green et al., 2012). Similarly, it may be that since most studies used cycling exercise, early adaptation is focussed on the most active vascular beds of the lower limbs, and assessment of BA function via FMD is insufficiently sensitive (Thijssen et al., 2007).

Alternatively, there may not be any vascular dysfunction, and the lack of effect on FMD is a result of the increased baseline diameter which aids total blood flow. Indeed, increased shear stress, as a result of an exercise has been suggested to cause systemic arterial remodelling (Maiorana et al., 2011). It is noteworthy that long-term training improved FMD without morphological changes (rationale one), while short term training increased baseline diameter without improving FMD. Given the interventions were between 2 and 12 weeks, and that vascular remodelling may occur within that time frame (Tinken et al., 2008), it is possible that this is responsible for increased baseline diameter within short term interventions. However,

the majority of the interventional studies only measured FMD before and after the exercise intervention. The “pre - post” nature of FMD assessments means that it is possible that improvements were missed by the time post measures were performed. Indeed, future work should assess the presence (or otherwise) of changes in FMD throughout the time course of training interventions. However, it is also worth noting that there was no improvement in FMD after 2 weeks of either continuous or high-intensity training within the study by Klonizakis et al. (2014), suggesting that relatively fast improvements in FMD may not always occur.

It is also worth noting several limitations of the literature pertaining to interventions in this age group. There were a relatively small number of interventional studies which met the inclusion criteria, meaning that again there was a relatively limited age range (62 to 70 years). Moreover, although the studies included within the meta-analysis were endurance based, the four included studies consisted of low, moderate and high exercise intensities, and ranged between 2 and 12 weeks, all of which may have contributed to the moderate heterogeneity of the pooled data. Future analyses may benefit from analysing intensity zones as these may affect FMD responses differently (Ashor et al., 2015; Ramos et al., 2015; Early et al., 2017), as the greatest effect in the available literature was observed following high-intensity interval training (Grace et al., 2015). However, due to the limited number of studies included within the current analysis, it was not possible to categorise studies based on their intensities.

However, despite the lack of improvements in FMD following exercise interventions, there are a number of other physiological advantages of exercise such as increased muscle strength and power (Reid and Fielding, 2012), as well as a reduction in other risk factors involved in ageing (Seals, 2014; Barnes, 2015). It therefore seems prudent to advise older

adults who begin exercising to remain active indefinitely in order to enjoy other health benefits associated with PA and exercise; not least as detraining may reverse potential improvements in various physiological factors (Pullin et al., 2004).

Additionally, the meta-analysis identified that EIDV did not change in either the trained versus untrained participants in the cross-sectional analysis or pre versus post training within the interventional analysis, however, combined pooling suggested a small effect. As EIDV is commonly used as a control test to assess whether improvements in FMD are mainly NO-mediated, these data suggest that improvements in trained participants FMD may be due to exercise induced improvements of the vascular endothelium, rather than alterations in vascular smooth muscle within the tunica media (Maruhashi et al., 2013). Conversely, the previously sedentary participants who completed an exercise intervention found no overall improvements in either FMD or vascular smooth muscle cell function.

3.4.3 Study Quality

The quality of most studies was determined as ‘good’ (see Tables 3 - 3 to 3 - 5); however, some limitations were noted. Firstly, the majority of both observational and cohort studies recruited only a small number of participants (less than 20 participants per group) which increases the chances of type II error, while also increasing the risk of finding a disproportionately large effect size (Button et al., 2013). Furthermore, the current meta-analysis only identified a single RCT from the literature which met the study inclusion criteria. Given that RCTs are widely considered the most internally valid design to determine cause and effect (Evans, 2003), future studies should investigate the use of this approach. Furthermore, few studies reported that outcome assessors were blind to the participant group allocation

during the assessment of FMD, increasing the risk of performance bias (Higgins and Green, 2011).

Moreover, while the included intervention studies performed outcome assessments at the cessation of the training programme, no studies included a sufficient follow-up to allow for the determination of the longevity of any beneficial effect. Although FMD is a useful predictor of vascular endothelial function, longer follow-up periods would be useful to identify whether improvements in FMD from exercise translates into a decreased incidence of vascular disease and mortality. Additionally, there is also the need for more comprehensive reporting of participant characteristics, including confirmation of medical history, training status, training frequency and duration (e.g., mins per week), and intensity as many studies lack sufficient detail.

Table 3 - 3. Cross-Sectional Study Quality.

	Research Question Clear?	Study Population Clear? (including without date and place)	Criteria same within both groups?	Sample size calculation?	Exposure measures clear, reliable and valid? Implemented consistently?	Outcome measures clear, reliable and valid? Implemented consistently?	Blinded assessment of FMD?	Follow-up after baseline 20 % or less?	Key potential confounding variables considered?
DeVan et al. (2013)	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N	NR	Y	Y
Eskurza et al. (2005)	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Franzoni et al. (2005)	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	NR	Y	Y
Galetta et al. (2006) (Galetta et al., 2006)	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	NR	Y	Y
Grace et al. (2014)	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y
Jensen-Urstand et al. (1999)	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	NR	Y	Y
Pierce et al. (2011a)	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y

	Research Question Clear?	Study Population Clear? (without date and place)	Criteria same within both groups?	Sample size calculation?	Exposure measures clear, reliable and valid? Implemented consistently?	Outcome measures clear, reliable and valid? Implemented consistently?	Blinded assessment of FMD?	Follow-up after baseline 20 % or less?	Key potential confounding variables considered?
Pierce et al. (2011a)	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Walker et al. (2009)	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	NR	Y	Y
Eskurza et al. (2004)	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

Study quality assessment of the cross-sectional studies included in question 1 developed by the National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute (NHLBI, 2014c). Y, yes; N, no; NR, not reported.

Table 3 - 4. Cohort Study Quality.

	Research Question Clear?	Participant eligibility criteria clear? (without date and names)	Were participants representative of general population of interest?	Were all eligible participants enrolled?	Was sample size sufficient to provide confidence in the findings?	Was the intervention clearly described and delivered consistently?	Outcome measures clear, reliable and valid? Implemented consistently?	Blinded assessment of FMD?	Loss to follow-up after baseline <20 %	Did the statistical method examine changes pre and post intervention?
Grace et al. (2015)	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	NR	Y	Y
Klonizakis et al. (2014) (17)	Y	Y	Y	Y	CD	Y	Y	NR	Y	Y
Thijssen et al. (2007)	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	NR	Y	Y

Study quality assessment of the cohort studies included in question 2 developed by the National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute (NHLBI, 2014b).

Y, yes; N, no; NR, not reported; CD, cannot determine.

Table 3 - 5. Randomised Control Trial Study Quality.

Described as a RCT?	Was the method of randomisation adequate?	Was the treatment allocation concealed?	Were the investigators blinded?	Were groups similar at baseline on important characteristics that could affect outcomes?	Was overall drop-out rate $\leq 20\%$	Was the differential drop-out rate at endpoint $\leq 15\%$?	High adherence to intervention protocols?	Were other interventions avoided or similar in the groups?	Outcome measures clear, reliable and valid? Implemented consistently?	Sample size sufficient to detect difference with at least 80% power?	Were outcomes reported or subgroups analysed pre-specified?	Were all randomised participants analysed in the group they were originally assigned?
Suboc et al. (2014)	Y	NR	NR	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

Study quality assessment of the randomised controlled trial study included in question 2 developed by the National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute

(NHLBI, 2014a). RCT, randomised controlled trial; Y, yes; N, no; NR, not reported.

Table 3 - 6. Meta-Regression Analysis.

Comparison	Covariate	n	q	df	SE	β	95% CI	P-value
Trained v Sedentary	Age	10	3.17	1	0.12	0.22	0.02%, 0.46%	0.08

Meta-regressions assessing the effect of age on flow mediated dilation percentage change.

3.4.4 Strengths and Limitations

This is the first systematic review and meta-analysis to focus on the effects of exercise on vascular function via FMD in healthy older adults using both cross-sectional and interventional studies; however, a number of limitations should be noted. Firstly, although FMD measurement protocols were similar between studies, some minor differences in protocols were evident. Studies measured post occlusion BA diameter for different durations, ranging from 90s to 10 minutes after cuff deflation. In addition to differences in methodology, there was also a wide range of baseline Δ FMD % values in intervention studies (3.4 ± 1.5 % to 8.9 ± 4.9 %). Furthermore, only a small number of studies normalised FMD values for hyperaemic stimulus (Eskurza et al., 2004, 2005). Therefore, the varied protocols and lack of FMD normalisation by shear may have all contributed to the differences between the studies. Additionally, despite the majority of the cross-sectional studies including EIDV within their analysis, only 2 of the 4 interventional studies reported EIDV data. This therefore reduces the confidence that any improvements in FMD were mediated by only the endothelium, and not by vascular smooth muscle cells. Also, for the purposes of this analysis, we defined vascular function as FMD response. However, it is plausible that analysis of microvascular function or *in-vitro* assessment of endothelial function may provide different results.

Moreover, although the interventional studies were specifically aerobic in nature, the intensities of the exercises differed considerably. For example, Suboc et al. (2014) conducted a walking intervention, which was of relatively low intensity, whereas Klonizakis et al. (2014) documented a high-intensity protocol requiring participants to work at 100 % of their peak power output, as determined from an earlier incremental cycling test. However, due to the lack of interventional studies meeting the inclusion criteria, all 4 studies had to be analysed together.

A greater number of interventional studies are therefore required within this specific cohort to investigate whether varying exercise intensities would influence vascular improvements differently. Additionally, within the cross-sectional studies, the lack of detail and the wide variation in exercise intensities makes comparison with effects in long-term trained individuals difficult. Furthermore, although there were no differences in Δ FMD % between supervised and non-supervised interventions, only one non-supervised intervention was included in the meta-analysis. Therefore, until further non-supervised interventional protocols meeting the inclusion criteria become available, this result should be interpreted with caution.

All of the studies included within the meta-analysis assessed vascular function of the BA via FMD, despite the interventions and longer-term exercise routines consisting primarily of lower-limb exercise. However, it has previously been identified that cycling can benefit FMD of the non-exercising upper limbs (Birk et al., 2012). Although Birk et al. (2012) assessed only young male participants, their results suggest that lower-limb exercise can cause systemic adaptations to endothelial function, which is likely caused by increases in shear stress. Therefore, it seems likely that the improvement in BA FMD identified within the cross-sectional studies is due to systemic vascular adaptations from many years of lower-limb exercise training.

Additionally, it has been previously shown that FMD in older females decreases at a faster rate than in males (Celermajer et al., 1994b). As the current systematic review and meta-analysis included both male and female participants, it is possible that our results could have differed if males and females were analysed separately. However, there were too few studies containing female participants to split the analysis by sex. Furthermore, it has been previously

found that oestrogen may be required to induce the benefits of endurance exercise on FMD, potentially by increasing NO bioavailability further (Moreau et al., 2013). As the females included in the meta-analysis were postmenopausal and not receiving oestrogen supplementation, perhaps intake of the hormone after menopause alongside aerobic exercise may have benefited FMD further. However, as the majority of the cross-sectional participants within the current meta-analysis were male, the results from the cross-sectional analysis may better represent the male population. Future studies may wish, where possible, to report male and female results separately, and to further report the menstrual status of female participants.

3.5 Conclusion

In summary, the current systematic review and meta-analysis identify that aerobic exercise training during advancing age can maintain healthy endothelial vasodilatory capacity, as assessed by FMD, compared with otherwise healthy sedentary peers. These findings emphasise the importance of remaining active throughout the lifespan. However, currently, there is not enough evidence to suggest that aerobic exercise interventions ranging from 2 to 12 weeks can improve FMD in previously sedentary older adults. Nonetheless, sedentary older individuals should still be encouraged to become active until more evidence becomes available.

CHAPTER 4

GENERAL METHODOLOGY

4.1 Overview

This section will outline the methods conducted in the following experimental chapters: Chapter 5, Chapter 6, and Chapter 7. Within, it will discuss the ethical approval, participant recruitment and screening processes, and the specific measurements performed within each study. Details specific to each individual study such as participant sample sizes and training interventions will be contained within the methodology sections of each of the respective chapters.

4.2 Measures Common to Studies 2 - 4

All participants were provided with a study information sheet that detailed all inclusion and exclusion criteria, in addition to the specific requirements of each participant. All eligible older adults were asked to gain permission from their general practitioner prior to their participation to ensure that they were capable of completing the exercise component of the study protocol. All participants were provided with a study information sheet and given the opportunity to ask questions and take time to consider if they were happy to participate.

All participants who were willing to participate provided informed consent prior to participation, and were informed of their rights during their participation, including the right to withdraw from the study at any time without having to provide a reason for doing so.

4.2.1 Anthropometry

Participants were asked to remove their shoes before all stature (meters, m) and body mass (kilograms, kg) measurements which were collected using a stadiometer (Harpenden, HAR-98.602) and body mass scales (877, Seca, Germany), respectively, in Chapter 5. A Tanita (MC-980MA Plus) body composition analyser was used to collect anthropometric data within Chapters 6 and 7. Body mass index (BMI) was subsequently calculated using the following equation:

$$(1) \quad BMI (kg/m^2) = \frac{Weight (kg)}{Height (m)^2}$$

4.2.2 Carotid Artery Structure and Blood Flow

All carotid artery imaging during chapters was performed using a high-resolution B-mode ultrasound (Vivid IQ) and a 12MHz linear array transducer (GE Medical, London; Figure 4 - 1). Image optimisation was attained by altering the gain, depth, zoom and focus positions, and image capture was set to record for 5s. After laying supine for 10 minutes, the internal carotid artery (ICA) was located, and longitudinal images were captured for assessment of arterial diameter. Longitudinal images of the common carotid artery (CCA) were also measured approximately 1 to 2 cm inferior to the bifurcation to measure the posterior intima-media thickness (IMT). An M-mode was then positioned perpendicular to the arterial wall for later measurement of maximal and minimal CCA diameters. Doppler imaging was also used to measure the blood flow velocity of both the ICA and CCA, whereby the insonation angle of 60 degrees was positioned parallel with the artery walls, and the sample volume was manually adjusted to encapsulate the majority of the lumen without protruding into the arterial walls.

Carotid artery (CA) images were analysed offline (EchoPAC, GE Healthcare; version 202). The IMT of the posterior region of the CCA was measured using the automatic post-processing function over at least a 1 cm straight segment 1 to 2 cm inferior to the carotid bifurcation. IMT measures were collected over two consecutive cardiac cycles during diastole, as recommended (Selzer et al., 2001), and averaged per participant (Figure 4 - 3). Maximal diameters (ICA and CCA) and minimal diameters (CCA) during systole and diastole were measured using manual callipers from the luminal IMT edge of the near and far walls from the longitudinal images for the ICA and M-mode images for CCA (Figure 4 - 2). Diameters of the CCA and ICA were measured at approximately the same position as the Doppler gate, and thus where blood velocity was measured. Zoom settings were used on the longitudinal images of the ICA to increase confidence in observing the exact anterior and posterior intima-lumen interface for calliper placement. All diameter measurements (cm) were averaged over three cardiac cycles. The time-averaged mean (TA mean) velocity of blood ($\text{cm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) within the CCA and ICA was measured over at least three consecutive cardiac cycles (Figure 4 - 4). CCA and ICA blood flow per minute was calculated using the following equations as suggested by (Blanco, 2015):

$$(1) \text{ Area} = \pi r^2$$

$$(2) \text{ Blood flow (ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}) = (\text{TA mean} * \text{Area}) * 60$$

Where $\pi = \text{Pi}$, $r = \text{radius of the common carotid artery}$, $\text{ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1} = \text{millilitres per minute}$, $\text{TA mean} = \text{time averaged mean velocity}$

Figure 4 - 1. (A) Vivid IQ ultrasound machine used for imaging of the carotid artery in all chapters and for imaging of the brachial artery during the flow mediated dilation protocol of the active participants in Chapter 6. (B) The 12 MHz linear array transducer which was used for the collection of all vascular data when using the Vivid IQ.

Figure 4 - 2. Assessment of common carotid artery diameter using M-mode (A) and the internal carotid artery (B). Maximum (internal and common carotid) and minimum diameters (common carotid) were manually measured over three consecutive cardiac cycles via callipers. All diameters are presented in centimetres (cm).

Figure 4 - 3. Assessment of common carotid posterior intima-media thickness (mm) during diastole.

Figure 4 - 4. Assessment of common and internal carotid blood velocity via ultrasound Doppler ($\text{cm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$). Time averaged mean is represented by the blue line traced upon the Doppler flow profiles.

Figure 4 - 5. Demonstration of maximum and minimum short axis diameter measurement of the common carotid artery using manual callipers during one cardiac cycle.

4.2.3 Brachial Artery Flow Mediated Dilation

The function of the brachial artery was assessed via flow mediated dilation (FMD). The specific ultrasound used during the FMD protocol is specified within sections 4.4.7 and 4.4.10. Participants lay supine for 10 minutes prior to the FMD procedure. After 10 minutes a large diameter pneumatic cuff was secured distally to the antecubital fossa on the right arm, and the whole arm was abducted to approximately 90 degrees. A linear array transducer was positioned longitudinally above the antecubital fossa on the upper arm to locate a straight and parallel segment of the BA. The image quality of the near and far walls was optimised by adjusting the gain, depth, zoom, focus positions, and dynamic range settings. Duplex ultrasound enabled Doppler imaging was also observed in order to record BA blood velocity, whereby the Doppler gate encompassed the full width of the artery, and an insonation angle of 60 degrees was selected.

Duplex longitudinal and doppler image capture were continuously recorded throughout the FMD protocol. Baseline data was collected for 1 minute, before rapidly inflating the cuff to supra-systolic pressure (220 mmHg) to occlude blood flow to the lower arm for a 5 minute period. The cuff was rapidly deflated after 5 minutes, and data was collected for a further 5 minutes post occlusion. Five minutes was chosen for the data collection duration as shorter collection times have been previously shown to underestimate peak diameter, particularly in older and sedentary individuals (Black et al., 2008).

Each recorded video was then rendered to 2 frames per second for offline analysis. The rendered files for each participant were subsequently uploaded to an automatic edge-detection system (Brachial Analyzer, Medical Imaging Applications LLC, Coralville). The scales for depth and doppler velocity were manually calibrated by aligning the calibrator to the y axis (depth and velocity), and x axis (doppler time). A region of interest (ROI) was then aligned over a section of the BA to encapsulate the near and far walls (Figure 4 - 6), and also the doppler flow profile. BA diameter and blood velocity were simultaneously measured throughout the rendered recording. Following diameter and blood velocity measurements, data were exported to an excel spreadsheet, and the data was subsequently added to custom software. The custom software calculated shear stress, area under the curve (AUC), and arterial diameters averaged over 3 second periods. The spreadsheet was used to calculate absolute (mm), relative (%), and shear normalised FMD values using the following equations:

$$(1) \text{ Absolute FMD (cm)} = \text{Peak Diameter} - \text{Baseline Diameter}$$

$$(2) \text{ Relative FMD (\%)} = \frac{\text{Peak Diameter} - \text{Baseline Diameter}}{\text{Baseline Diameter}} * 100$$

$$(3) \text{ Shear Normalised FMD (\%)} = \frac{\text{Relative FMD}}{\text{Shear AUC}}$$

Figure 4 - 6. Measurement of region of interest of the brachial artery (A) and calibration of ultrasound depth (B) using the Brachial Analyzer software.

4.2.4 Reproducibility

Carotid ultrasound reproducibility measurements were performed on 5 healthy young adults for all carotid peak circumferential strain (PCS) and peak strain rate (PSR) measurements (detailed in Section 4.4.8), and 8 similar participants for all other measurements. All participants were asked to refrain from vigorous exercise for 48 hours, and caffeine and alcohol for 24 hours prior to their visit. The participants rested in a supine position for 10 minutes prior to the first scan, and for approximately 20 minutes between scans 1 and 2. Carotid ultrasound scans were obtained and subsequently assessed as described within Sections 4.2.2, 4.4.8 and 4.4.9. The mean and standard deviations (SD) of each variable for scans one and two were calculated for all eight participants and is presented in Table 4 - 1. The mean and SD were also calculated between scans 1 and 2 for each participant, and the reproducibility of each measure was assessed using the following equation:

$$\text{Coefficient of Variation (\%)} = \frac{\text{Standard Deviation}}{\text{Mean}} * 100$$

As a result of the COVID-19 global pandemic and associated UK-wide lockdown, it was not possible to conduct further assessment of FMD or conventional carotid stiffness measures to identify the reproducibility of these measurements within our laboratory. Consequently, these reproducibility measurements have not been included within this thesis.

Table 4 - 1. Reproducibility of Carotid Ultrasound Scans

Measure	Scan 1	Scan 2	Coefficient of Variation
CCA PCS (%)	8.5 ± 1.7	7.0 ± 1.0	14.6 %
CCA PSR (s ⁻¹)	0.81 ± 0.21	0.77 ± 0.11	13.4 %
CCA Recoil Rate (s ⁻¹)	-0.21 ± 0.04	-0.24 ± 0.07	15.8 %
PTT (ms)	0.05 ± 0.02	0.06 ± 0.02	9.0 %
CCA IMT (mm)	0.48 ± 0.08	0.46 ± 0.09	4.6 %
CCA Max D (cm)	0.62 ± 0.07	0.60 ± 0.06	1.5 %
CCA Min D (cm)	0.55 ± 0.06	0.54 ± 0.05	2.0 %
CCA Flow (ml.min ⁻¹)	558.9 ± 125.2	524.0 ± 118.6	5.4 %
ICA Max D (cm)	0.45 ± 0.04	0.46 ± 0.04	2.6 %
ICA Flow (ml.min ⁻¹)	351.6 ± 91.4	409.5 ± 142.0	9.4 %

Data is presented as overall means and standard deviations ± SD of the raw carotid data for scans 1 and 2, and as the mean coefficient of variation between the two carotid measurements for all participants. CCA, common carotid artery; PCS, peak circumferential strain; PSR, peak strain rate; PTT, pulse transit time; ICA, internal carotid artery; D, diameter.

4.2.5 Statistical Analysis

All data are presented as means \pm SD, and a $P < 0.05$ level was chosen. All figures were produced using Microsoft Excel (Version 16.31).

4.3 Measures for Study 2 (Chapter 5 Only)

4.3.1 Ethics

The University of the West of Scotland (UWS) School of Health and Life Science's ethics committee provided ethical approval for the cross-sectional study within Chapter 5.

4.3.2 Recruitment

Participants within Chapter 5 were recruited within South Lanarkshire and surrounding areas via study advertisement on social media, flyers, local running, cycling, and triathlon clubs, leisure centres, and community clubs including chess, indoor bowls, Men's Sheds, and University of the Third Age groups, in addition to word of mouth.

4.3.3 Study Protocol

Participants were asked to refrain from participating in strenuous exercise for 24 hours, and alcohol and caffeine for 12 hours prior to participation. Physiological testing took place within the Cardiovascular Imaging Laboratory at the University of the West of Scotland, Hamilton Campus. On arrival at each visit, participants completed a medical history, physical activity readiness questionnaire (PAR-Q), and a Training History and Frequency questionnaire. Additionally, participants were also asked how many years of education they had completed.

4.3.4 Blood Pressure and Heart Rate

Participants lay supine on a medical plinth for 10 minutes prior to measurement of their resting heart rate (HR) and blood pressure (BP). HR was measured using a polar chest strap HR monitor which was synchronised with the Polar Beat application on a smartphone (version 3.4.4) via Bluetooth. BP was measured using an automated sphygmomanometer BP monitor (OMRON, 705IT, Hoofddorp, Netherlands). Triplicate measures of both BP and HR were taken at 2 minute intervals and subsequently averaged.

4.3.5 Brachial Artery Flow Mediated Dilation

A Vivid 7 ultrasound machine and a M12L transducer (GE Medical, London; Figure 4 - 7) were used to collect images of the BA.

4.3.6 Aerobic Capacity Assessment

Aerobic capacity was assessed using the Ekblom-Bak sub-maximal predictive $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ test. The assessment was completed on an electronically braked cycle ergometer (Lode, Excalibur, Groningen, Netherlands), where the saddle height and handle-bar position were adapted for each participant. All participants were firstly familiarised with Borg's rating of perceived exertion (RPE) scale (Borg, 1970), and were provided with the test instructions before commencement.

The test consisted of two 4 minute stages in which the participant was asked to maintain a constant cadence of 60 revolutions per minute (rpm). During the first 4 minutes all

participants cycled at 32 watts before pedalling against a higher work rate in the second stage which was specific to their age, fitness, RPE, and average HR (collected every 15 s) in the last minute of the first stage. Participants were also asked for their RPE during the second minute of the second stage to ensure that they were within the required range of 12 to 16. If lower than the RPE range required (12 – 16), the work rate was increased, and the second stage was repeated. Average HR and RPE were also recorded within the last minute of the second stage. It was aimed for HR to be between 120 and 150 b.min⁻¹ within the young group, and between 110 and 140 b.min⁻¹ within the older group at the end of the last stage. $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ was calculated using a sex-specific equation previously reported (Björkman et al., 2016), which divides the change in HR by the change in power output between the two stages. Relative $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ was calculated dividing absolute $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ in ml.min⁻¹ by the body mass (kg) of participants.

Figure 4 - 7. The Vivid 7 ultrasound (A) and M12L transducer (B) used for the collection of brachial artery flow mediated dilation data within Chapter 5.

4.3.7 Cognitive Assessment

The Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery (CANTAB® [Cognitive assessment software], 2019) was used to assess the cognitive function of participants. In particular, the ‘Alzheimer’s Test Battery’ was chosen as it contains tests that are designed for assessment of general cognitive function and are validated for use in both young and older cohorts.

The test was administered in a quiet room on a touch screen device (iPad Air, iOS 12.1). The iPad was placed on an adjustable stand in which participants could change the angle for their own comfort. The test battery lasted approximately 35 minutes and consisted firstly of a motor screening task (MOT) to assess whether participants would comply with the test. Each test commenced with clear audio instructions, following with a practice test before data collection occurred. Participants were also encouraged to ask for help from an investigator in the neighbouring room if they did not understand the test. The following tests were included within the CANTAB Alzheimer’s Test Battery:

4.3.7.1 Reaction Time (RTI)

Participants were required to hold down a button on the bottom of the screen before touching one of five circles as quickly as possible when prompted by a change in their colour. The test assessed movement and reaction time.

4.3.7.2 Rapid Visual Information Processing (RVP)

A box in the centre of the screen displayed single numbers from 2 to 9 at a rate of 100 digits per second. Participants are required to remember up to 3 different 3 digit sequences and are asked to press a button on the lower screen as quickly as possible when the specific sequences appear. This test measures latency of response, probability of false alarms and sensitivity of responding to the correct sequences.

4.3.7.3 Delayed Matching to Sample (DMS)

The delayed matching to sample assessment displays an intricate pattern on the centre of the screen, before showing four similar patterns either simultaneously or after a delay of varying durations (0, 4, 6, 8 and 12s). The participants must select the correct pattern whilst avoiding choosing another pattern that may look similar, except has different shapes or colours associated with it. The assessment is therefore effective at assessing simultaneous memory and short-term visual recognition memory. Overall, the latency of responses and number of correct and incorrect answers are measured for each participant.

4.3.7.4 Paired Associated Learning (PAL)

The paired associates learning test effectively measures visual memory and new learning. Boxes are opened separately for a short period of time to display different patterns. Participants are then shown the patterns individually in the centre of the screen and are asked to correctly identify which box the pattern is located in. The test ranges in difficulty, beginning with 4, and ending with 12 boxes. PAL measures a memory score, and the number of errors, attempts made, and patterns reached.

4.3.7.5 Spatial Working Memory (SWM)

The Spatial Working Memory test measures executive functioning, memory, and manipulation of new information. The SWM test requires participants to use a strategy to identify the location of tokens from within various boxes presented on the screen. Participants who begin a search from the same box they started from within a different search are thought to be implementing a strategy to successfully locate the tokens. Difficulty increases from 6 to 12 boxes within different trials. In addition to measuring strategy, errors are also recorded within the test.

4.3.8 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis for vascular and cognitive variables was performed using SPSS (Version 25) and Jamovi (version 0.9) (The jamovi project, 2019). Raw CANTAB data from the tests outlined in the above section was entered into said commercially available statistical packages prior to performing the appropriate statistical tests (ANCOVA (Jamovi) and partial correlations (SPSS)).

4.4 Measures for Studies 3 and 4 (Chapters 6 and 7)

4.4.1 Ethics

Ethical approval for the studies within Chapters 6 and 7 was granted by the ethics committee at the University of Wales, Trinity St David.

4.4.2 Recruitment

Participants for Chapters 6 and 7 were recruited within the town of Carmarthen and surrounding areas in South Wales, UK. The method of recruitment included using social media, newspaper advertisements, posters and word of mouth.

4.4.3 Study Protocol

Participants were asked to refrain from participating in strenuous exercise for 24 hours prior to participation. Participants were also asked to refrain from consumption of alcohol for 24 hours, and food or fluid (exception of water) for 3 hours before their arrival to the laboratory. Physiological testing took place within the Human Physiology Laboratory at the University of Wales, Trinity St David Carmarthen Campus. On arrival to each visit, participants completed a medical history questionnaire and PAR-Q (Chapters 6 and 7).

4.4.4 Anthropometry

Body fat percentage (%) was also measured in participants within Chapters 6 and 7 using Tanita Body Composition Scales (MC-980MA Plus).

4.4.5 Blood Pressure and Heart Rate

HR was measured using a 3 lead echocardiogram (ECG), which was connected to the ultrasound machine (Vivid IQ). The electrodes of which were placed on each shoulder and the left hip or posterior surface of the hand of participants. Live ECG traces and HR were made visible on the ultrasound screen and were recorded alongside ultrasound images of the common

carotid artery at rest, during and after a 3 minute isometric handgrip (HG) exercise (see section 4.4.8). Offline analysis of the carotid short axis (SAX) images allowed for the extraction of HR data which were recorded during each of the three conditions (see section 4.4.8).

Continuous beat-to-beat BP was measured using a Finapres monitoring device (Finapres Medical Systems, The Netherlands; Model 1). The third finger of the left hand was measured to determine the size of finger cuff to be used. An appropriately sized cuff (small, medium or large) was subsequently positioned on the middle phalanx of the respective finger, whilst the hand was positioned laterally to the torso at the same height as the heart. The beat-to-beat reconstructed finger to brachial blood pressure waveform was stored via the BeatScope Easy software (SMART Medical, UK; Version 02.10 build 004) on a connected computer. During the carotid artery ultrasound scan, markers customised within the BeatScope Easy software were used to identify the BP which occurred simultaneously with each carotid ultrasound image captured (Figure 4 - 8). During resting conditions, markers on the BP data were aligned with longitudinal axis images of the CCA and ICA, and SAX images of the CCA. As a 3 minute bout of acute resistance exercise was also performed during the carotid ultrasound scan (see section 4.3.8), markers were used to identify BP during, and within 20s after completion of the 3 minute HG exercise alongside the corresponding SAX images of the CCA.

During offline analysis, the marked BP measures were matched with their corresponding carotid artery ultrasound images. As at least two or more cardiac cycles of SAX carotid ultrasound images were averaged for analysis (see section 4.3.8), BP from each of the matching cardiac cycles immediately prior to the marker were collected (Figure 4 - 8) and subsequently

averaged. The BP values extracted from the BeatScope software consisted of both, systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP). Mean arterial pressure (MAP) and pulse pressure (PP) was subsequently calculated using the following equations:

$$(1) \text{ MAP (mmHg)} = \frac{(SBP + 2(DBP))}{3}$$

$$(2) \text{ PP (mmHg)} = SBP - DBP$$

SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; MAP, mean arterial pressure; PP, pulse pressure.

All BP values measured alongside longitudinal images of the ICA and CCA were averaged to provide resting BP values. BP values during and immediately after the 3 minute HG exercise were also averaged to provide overall BP values during and post HG.

Figure 4 - 8. Continuous blood pressure collection presented via the BeatScope software. Markers were added simultaneously with carotid artery ultrasound image collection.

4.4.6 Vascular Ultrasound Imaging

Figure 4 - 9. Schematic of the vascular ultrasound protocol order and timing during each visit during the cross-sectional, interventional and follow-up studies in Chapter 6 and 7.

4.4.7 Brachial Artery Flow Mediated Dilation

A Terason uSmart 3300 ultrasound and 15L4 Smart Mark transducer (Teratech, US) were used to image the BA of the inactive participants in Chapter 6 and all participants within Chapter 7. A Vivid IQ ultrasound and a 12 MHz linear array transducer (GE Medical, London) were used to image the BA of the active participants within Chapter 6 (Figure 4 – 1).

Figure 4 - 10. Terason uSmart 330 ultrasound (A) 15L4 Smart Mark transducer (B) used for the collection of brachial artery flow mediated dilation during Chapters 6 and 7.

4.4.8 Common Carotid Artery Compliance

Compliance of the CCA was assessed at rest, during, and immediately after a 3 minute isometric hand contraction (Figure 4 - 9) using ultrasound speckle tracking technology. A 3 minute isometric HG contraction at 40 % of maximal effort was chosen as it has previously

shown to be of sufficient intensity to elicit physiological stress (Weiner et al., 2012), whereby higher intensities are not reported to produce greater BP responses (Seals, 1993).

All CCA SAX images were collected approximately 1 cm distal to the bifurcation, at a depth of 4 cm and a frame rate of 106.9 frames per second. SAX images of at least three cardiac cycles were measured at rest, immediately after collecting the longitudinal CCA images mentioned previously. Using their right hand, participants were then asked to perform a short maximal contraction (2 to 3s) using the HG dynamometer with their arm straight by their torso (Takei T.K.K.5001 Grip A), and 40 % of their maximum effort was subsequently calculated. The participants were then asked to perform a 3 minute isometric HG contraction at 40 % of their maximum grip strength, in which they were encouraged to maintain consistent pressure throughout. SAX CCA images were recorded within the last 30s of the 3 minute contraction, and within 20s after release of the hand dynamometer.

The SAX-AP 2D strain option within EchoPAC was used to measure CCA PCS and PSR. The mid-segment of the ROI was carefully aligned with the wall of the carotid, posterior to any visible IMT during a loop of one cardiac cycle. This enabled the ROI to cover the full circumference of the artery which was subsequently analysed by the software in 6 circumferential segments and averaged to provide a 'global' value. The ECG trace was manually adapted to begin and end immediately before the QRS-complex of the chosen cycle, and immediately before the QRS-complex of the following cycle. Global PCS and PSR of the mid-section were recorded only if four or more segments of the wall were successfully tracked by the software (Figure 4 - 11). Two or more cardiac cycles of the same image were recorded for analysis.

The analysed EchoPAC files were imported into a custom-built software which extracted the required vascular values using a 1000 point cubic spline within both systole and diastole to measure PCS, PSR and recoil rate (Figure 4 - 12). The software also calculates PCS, PSR, and recoil rate corrected for physiologically relevant timings for carotid mechanics (Sculthorpe et al., 2020). Corrected PCS and PSR images were subsequently averaged over a minimum of two cardiac cycles. HR was also extracted from the files which corresponded with each PCS and PSR measure. Additionally, an estimate of pulse transit time was also measured from the software which is calculated as the time between the QRS complex from the ECG, and the onset of CCA expansion measured via ultrasound (Sculthorpe et al., 2020). Minimum and maximum SAX arterial diameters of one of the included PCS and PSR cardiac cycles were assessed at each time point using manual callipers from the intima-lumen interface of the anterior and posterior walls (Figure 4 - 5).

Figure 4 - 11. Short axis image of the common carotid artery during one cardiac cycle prior to speckle tracking analysis (A). Image B identifies the region of interest trace on the same short

axis image of the common carotid. The grid on the lower region of image B identifies that the manually tracked region of interest has successfully tracked the movement of the arterial wall throughout the chosen cardiac cycle.

Figure 4 - 12. The raw traces for circumferential strain (A) and strain rate (B) of the common carotid artery. Traces were later corrected to adjust negative strain values from baseline level. Both A and B contain traces from global values (white dotted line), and traces from each of the segmental regions across the circumference of the artery (seen within Figure 4 - 11).

4.4.9 Common Carotid Artery Stiffness

Conventional measurement of arterial stiffness was also calculated to identify whether CCA stiffness changed from pre, during and immediately after the HG exercise. Conventional stiffness measures Petersons Elastic Modulus (E_p) and Beta-1 stiffness index (β_1) determine arterial stiffness from adjusting changes in systolic and diastolic arterial diameters with

distending pulse pressures (Laurent et al., 2006). As a result, higher values for each of the conventional measures represents greater arterial stiffness.

Arterial stiffness was calculated from the following equations:

$$(1) \beta_1 \text{ stiffness index (cm}^2\text{/kPa)} = \frac{\ln(SBP/DBP)}{(DiamSYS - DiamDIAS)/DiamDIAS}$$

$$(2) \text{ Peterson's Elastic Modulus (E}_p\text{) (kPa)} = \frac{(SBP - DBP)}{(DiamSYS - DiamDIAS)/DiamDIAS}$$

ln, natural logarithm; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; DiamSYS, maximum diameter of the artery during systole; DiamDIAS, minimum diameter of the artery during diastole.

Each conventional stiffness measure was firstly calculated across three consecutive cardiac cycles and averaged within each participant. BP values were retrieved from the BeatScope software as mentioned in section 4.4.5. As mentioned previously (section 4.4.5), longitudinal carotid BP values were used within the arterial stiffness equations at rest, whilst BPs recorded during and after the HG were used for during and post HG stiffness equations. Diameters for the above equations were measured from the maximum and minimum diameters of SAX CCA. As the measurement of diameters across consecutive cardiac cycles produced the same diameters, maximum and minimum diameters were measured as described in section 4.4.8 during one cardiac cycle (Figure 4 - 5).

4.4.10 Aerobic Capacity Assessment

An open circuit spirometry using a Cortex II Metalyser 3B-R2 (Cortex, Biophysik, Leipzig, Germany) was used to measure $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$, and was calibrated according to the manufacturers' guidelines prior to assessment. Expired air was analysed using a volume transducer (Triple V[®] turbine, digital) connected to an oxygen (O₂) analyser. Oxygen (O₂) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) within expired gas were analysed using electrochemical cells and an infrared analyser, respectively. After allowing 60 minutes of warm-up, the sensors for O₂ and CO₂ were calibrated against room air in addition to known compositions of reference gases (5 % CO₂, 15 % O₂ and 80 % N₂). A final calibration for volume was also performed using a 3 litre pump to simulate inspiration and expiration repeated five times.

Participants completed a 5 minute warm-up before undertaking an incremental treadmill test consisting of one-minute stages until volitional exhaustion, whereby $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ was determined. The Metalyser displayed continuous live values of oxygen uptake (VO₂), carbon dioxide production (VCO₂), respiratory exchange ratio (RER) and ventilation (VE) throughout the duration of the assessment. Short-range telemetry (Polar T31, Kempele, Finland) was used to measure HR every 5s, and participants were asked to indicate their perceived exertion using the Borg RPE scale (Borg, 1970), during the last 10s of each 1 minute stage. Breath by breath data were sampled and transferred to a PC for real-time display, and the recorded data was saved to the internal database (Metasoft version 3.7.0). The coefficient of variation (CV) for the determination of $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ in our laboratory is < 3.0 %.

The percentage of age predicted $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ was also calculated in all participants using published aerobic capacity reference data (Loe et al., 2013). The following equation was used to calculate age predicted $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ (%):

$$\text{Age predicted } \dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}} (\%) = \frac{\text{Measured } \dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}}{\text{Reference } \dot{V}O_{2\text{max}}} * 100$$

4.4.11 Cognitive Function Assessment

4.4.11.1 Cognitive Screening

The presence of depression has previously been shown to have a detrimental impact on the cognitive function of individuals (Lim et al., 2013; Rock et al., 2014). Therefore, prior to commencing the cognitive assessments, participants completed the Centre for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (CES-D) and the Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS). Cut off scores ≥ 16 and < 44.5 were used to screen for individuals at risk of depression and low mental wellbeing, respectively (Bianco, 2012). The CES-D and the WEMWBS questionnaires were specifically chosen to screen participants prior to the cognitive assessment as they have both been previously reported as effective screening questionnaires for depression and low mental wellbeing (Bianco, 2012; Vilagut et al., 2016). Although both questionnaires are free to use, permission was granted from the Warwick Medical School (University of Warwick, Coventry, UK) for use of the WEMWBS, as requested for non-profit organisations (submission ID: 505621368).

The following tests are used regularly within cognitive research and have been identified as exhibiting at least adequate levels of test-retest reliability (Franzen et al., 1987;

Siegrist, 1997; Harrison et al., 2000; Wagner et al., 2011; Fawns-Ritchie and Deary, 2020).

Following the screening questionnaires, an examiner described the following cognitive tests to the participants prior to commencing each individual assessment.

4.4.11.2 Trail Making

Trail Making A

Participants were presented with an A4 size sheet of paper (21 x 29.7 cm) containing 25 circled numbers positioned throughout. Participants were asked to draw a straight line between each of the numbers in numerical order without lifting the pen from the paper until the last numbered circle was reached.

Trail Making B

Participants were presented with a similar print out with 25 circles containing either numbers or letters and were asked to draw a line between the numbers and letters in numeral and alphabetical order, switching between each number and letter (1 – A – 2 – B – 3 - C, etc). Again, participants were asked not to lift the pen from the paper until the last circle was reached.

One practice test on an example sheet was permitted for each test before the scored test began. The assessor informed the participants of any errors made when occurred, in which the participant was asked to correct the error before continuing. The objective of the test was to correctly complete each task as quickly as possible, including the time taken to correct any

errors made. Trails A and B have been identified as effective tests to assess processing time and executive function, respectively (Lim et al., 2013).

4.4.11.3 Digit Span

Forward

A list of numbers was read out loud by the examiners (at a rate of approximately one number per second). Participants were asked to correctly repeat the numbers in the same order. The examiner would begin with a 2 number sequence, before increasing the sequence by one number after the previous set of sequences were correctly answered. Participants were required to correctly answer least 5 out of 6 sequences before progressing to the next stage. The digit span score for each participant was determined by the last completed stage in which they correctly answered at least 5 out of 6 sequences. The forward span test is commonly used for assessing short-term memory (Jones and Macken, 2015).

Backward

The backward span was performed similarly to the forward span, except the participants were asked to recite the numbers in the reverse order to which they were read out by the examiner. The first stage again consisted of two numbers before increasing by one number after every successfully completed stage, and the participant's digit span score was determined similarly to forward span. The sequences consisted of a different combination of numbers than the forward span to limit any learning effects. The backwards span has been previously shown to be effective at assessing the cognitive domain of attention (Lim et al., 2013).

4.4.11.4 Verbal Fluency

Animals

Participants were asked to name as many different animals as possible within one minute.

Words beginning with 'S'

Participants were asked to name as many words as possible beginning with the letter 's'. However, the words could not be proper nouns and therefore could not be names of people or places. Additionally, similar sounding words would not be counted as extra points. For example, 'sing' and 'singing' would only be recorded as one point.

Verbal fluency has previously been shown to be effective at assessing the cognitive domain of executive function (Lim et al., 2013).

4.4.11.5 Stroop Test

The Stroop Test consisted of 4 separate assessments. The assessor informed participants of any errors made during each assessment, where participants were then asked to provide the correct answer. The time taken to complete each individual test was recorded (s), with a faster time demonstrating a better performance. The recorded time included participant's self-corrected errors, although the number of errors and corrections made were

not recorded. Each Stroop sheet contained the same number of characters and order of words (n). The four separate Stroop tests were performed as follows:

Stroop 1

Participants were presented with an A4 size print containing the names of colours which were all printed in black ink, in which the participants were required to read the names of the colours aloud.

Stroop 2

Stroop 2 consisted of the names of colours which were all printed in their respective colours. Again, the participants were asked to read aloud the names of the colours.

Stroop 3

Participants were presented with crosses printed in different colours and were asked to say aloud the names of the ink colour. Stroop tests 1 – 3 are commonly used to assess information processing speed (Coetsee and Terblanche, 2017).

Stroop 4

Stroop 4 consisted of names of colours however the colour of the ink did not match the colour name. Participants were asked to correctly identify the colour of the ink the words were printed in, and not the printed word. The Stroop 4 test assesses executive function (Lim et al., 2013).

4.4.12 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis for vascular and cognitive data was performed using Jamovi (version 0.9) (The jamovi project, 2019). Raw cognitive data from the tests outlined in the above section were entered into the Jamovi statistical software prior to performing the appropriate statistical analysis.

CHAPTER 5

ABSENCE OF VASCULAR AND COGNITIVE BENEFIT FROM LONG- TERM ENDURANCE EXERCISE COMPARED TO RECREATIONAL EXERCISE IN HEALTHY OLDER ADULTS

5.1 Introduction

The ageing population is rising, with the number of adults over 60 years of age expected to increase to 2 billion by 2050 (Ghebreyesus, 2017). Despite the population living longer, not all necessarily live a longer healthy life span partly due to the combination of ageing associated health impairments and poor lifestyle choices (Seals et al., 2016). Furthermore, advancing age also increases the prevalence and number of comorbidities (Wolff et al., 2002). For example, ageing adults are susceptible to negative cardiovascular adaptations including impaired peripheral endothelial dysfunction (Seals et al., 2011), central arterial stiffness (Scuteri et al., 2014) and reduced cerebral blood flow (CBF) (Melamed et al., 1980; Stoquart-ElSankari et al., 2007). Elevated central arterial stiffness and intraluminal pressures have been linked with impairments of cerebral tissue including reductions in cerebral volume, increased white matter hyperintensities (Tsao et al., 2013), and microvascular damage (O'Rourke and Safar, 2005; de Montgolfier et al., 2019). Consequently, ageing is also associated with declines in cognitive functioning, whereby cognitive domains including memory, processing speed and executive functions can become impaired (Harada et al., 2013). Whilst the extent of cognitive decline can vary between older individuals (Wisdom et al., 2012), progression of cognitive dysfunction can compromise day to day tasks, affecting the independence and well-being of those affected (Wilson et al., 2013; Diem et al., 2018). As cognitive decline and both, central and peripheral vascular impairments begin to form gradually prior to reaching 'old age' (Melamed et al., 1980; Wisdom et al., 2012; Skaug et al., 2013), identifying declines in all three are important so that early intervention can be put in place in an attempt to alleviate ageing associated dysfunction.

Regular participation in exercise, and consequently, higher cardiorespiratory fitness (CRF), has been shown to mitigate various ageing associated neuropsychological and

physiological impairments. Various reports state that older adults who are exercise-trained, or who exhibit higher CRF or physical activity (PA) levels, demonstrate superior cognitive function, or less cognitive decline in contrast to those who are less active (Baylor and Spirduso, 1988; Clarkson-Smith and Hartley, 1989; Yaffe et al., 2001; Barnes et al., 2003; Ari et al., 2004; Weuve et al., 2004; Hatta et al., 2005; Brown et al., 2010). In addition to improved cognitive function, there is also evidence for improved vascular structure, blood flow and conductance within and out-with the cerebral vasculature. A number of studies have documented that cerebrovascular blood flow and conductance was superior in older adults who were exercise trained as well as in those who exhibit higher CRF levels (Ainslie et al., 2008; Brown et al., 2010; Bailey et al., 2013; Zimmerman et al., 2014). Additionally, exercise-trained older men demonstrate less age-associated declines in blood velocity and increases in blood flow within the central carotid arteries compared to their sedentary counterparts (Azhim et al., 2007a; Braz et al., 2017), suggesting that the extracranial haemodynamic environment is also improved in regular exercisers. Furthermore, long-term endurance training has also shown to benefit the endothelial vasodilatory capacity of peripheral arteries in healthy older adults, as assessed by brachial artery flow mediated dilation (FMD) (Campbell et al., 2019). However, while these effects have not been assessed in the same cohort, regular exercise participation can be an effective lifestyle strategy to reduce ageing associated declines in central and peripheral arterial function, and cognitive health, albeit when assessed separately within different cohorts.

As higher CBF is positively associated with cognitive function (Leeuwis et al., 2018), it could be possible that superior extra- and intracranial vascular structure and function from regular exercise participation may also underpin enhanced cognitive function by promoting a superior cerebral environment (Barnes and Corkery, 2018). Despite this hypothesis, there are

few studies that have assessed whether there are associations between peripheral and central vascular measures with cognitive performance within the same cohort of long-term endurance individuals. One study has demonstrated better cerebrovascular conductance (CVC) and mean arterial pressure (MAP) of the middle cerebral artery, and superior cognitive function in aerobically 'fit' versus sedentary healthy older females (Brown et al., 2010). Whilst vascular measures together during resting and isocapnic conditions were reported to predict cognitive function in the older females, resting measures of CVC and MAP alone did not predict cognition (Brown et al., 2010). Conversely, Tarumi et al. (2015) reported links between cerebrovascular reactivity (CVR) and brachial FMD with cognitive function in a healthy middle-aged exercise-trained and untrained cohort. Moreover, the endurance-trained individuals exhibited superior cognitive performance and brachial artery FMD compared to their untrained counterparts (Tarumi et al., 2015). However, these previous reports have focused on the influence of aerobic capacity or training status on cerebrovascular function. Moreover, no previous research has assessed the influence of long-term exercise training on both, peripheral (brachial) and central extra-cranial vascular measures (carotid) alongside cognitive performance in healthy older adults. Researching within this particular area would help to determine whether systemic vascular function and cognition are both affected by long-term endurance training and whether such variables work synergistically within the same cohort of healthy older adults.

The need for such research is important as in addition to the rise in the global ageing population, a lack of older individuals are meeting the weekly PA guidelines for health as recommended by World Health Organisation (WHO) (World Health Organisation, 2011). Moreover, PA levels are reported to decline further with advancing age in older adults (Townsend et al., 2015). Consequently, physical inactivity contributes to mortality (Arem et

al., 2015; Carlson et al., 2018), and morbidity within the ageing population, including cardiovascular diseases and cognitive declines (Larson et al., 2006; Lachman et al., 2018). Therefore, an increased understanding of the potential systemic vascular and cognitive benefits of long-term endurance training may help to further emphasise the importance of remaining physically active throughout the lifespan. Although assessing differences between the trained and untrained healthy older adults may highlight the effects of long-term endurance exercise on the healthy ageing process, including a young healthy positive control group may also provide information regarding the extent of ageing associated declines occurring in both older groups.

Therefore, the aims of the study were to 1) assess whether peripheral (brachial) and central (carotid) vascular structure and function, and cognitive performance was superior in long-term endurance-trained versus recreationally active healthy older adults; 2) where differences between groups exist, identify whether associations exist between peripheral and central vascular measures with cognitive performance; and 3) assess for differences in the same measures between healthy young and older cohorts. It was hypothesised that both, peripheral and central structure and vascular function, and cognitive performance would be superior in the older endurance-trained compared to the recreationally active group. It was also hypothesised that associations would exist between peripheral and central vascular measures with cognitive adaptations from long-term endurance training. Furthermore, it was hypothesised that the young cohort would exhibit better cognitive performance, and superior measures of peripheral and central vascular structure and function when compared to the older untrained cohort.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Participants

Following ethical approval, 23 healthy endurance-trained older and 35 untrained older adults were originally recruited for the study. Participants were classified as ‘trained’ if at the time of the study they participated in an endurance-based training programme for nine years or more. Conversely, the ‘untrained’ participants consisted of those who did not participate in a structured exercise training programme. Recruitment took place via study advertisements on social media, flyers, local running, cycling and triathlon clubs, leisure centres, and community clubs including chess, indoor bowls, Men’s Sheds, and University of the Third Age groups, in addition to word of mouth. Thirty-nine healthy young participants who did not participate in any regular endurance-based training programmes were recruited via social media, flyers, and word of mouth, and acted as a young control group.

Individuals were excluded if they were greater than 30 years old in the young group or less than 60 years of age in the older groups. Participants were also excluded if they used hypertensive or cardiovascular medication, had cardiovascular disease, or a previous vascular event, had critical hypertension or diabetes, used hormone replacement therapy, or hormonal contraceptives, used protein pump inhibitors, were a current smoker, and those who had been performing continuous endurance-based training for less than nine years. Excluding older individuals who reported less than nine years of continuous endurance training ensured that included participants represented a cohort who had begun exercising from at least middle age. After the exclusion of participants who did not meet study requirements, 9 young, 13 older trained and 14 older untrained participants were included in the study (Figure 5 - 1). All older female participants self-reported being postmenopausal. Long-term endurance trained older

adults consisted mainly of long-distance cyclists and runners. Self-reported duration of continuous endurance training ranged between 9 to 50 years, with an average of 31.8 ± 15.4 years (Appendix 3).

5.2.2 Study Protocol

All participants were provided with a study information sheet and questionnaires as listed in Chapter 4. All participants were required to refrain from vigorous PA for 24 hours, and caffeine and alcohol for 12 hours prior to their visit. All data collection was completed in the Cardiovascular Imaging Laboratory at the University of the West of Scotland.

Figure 5 - 1. Schematic of initially recruited participants, reasons for exclusion, and final included participants for each of the three groups

On arrival, participants lay supine in a darkened room for a 10 minute resting period. Resting blood pressure (BP) and heart rate (HR) measurements were subsequently measured as described in Chapter 4 (Section 4.3.4). Whilst remaining supine, FMD of the BA and assessment of the common (CCA) and internal carotid arteries (ICA) was performed by high-frequency ultrasound and doppler imaging, as also described in detail in Chapter 4 (Sections 4.2.2, 4.2.3 and 4.3.5). Following the vascular ultrasound assessments, the Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery (CANTAB) and $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ test was performed as described in Chapter 4, sections 4.3.7 and 4.3.6, respectively.

5.2.3 Statistical Analysis

Raw CANTAB scores were used within the analysis. All data were tested for normality and homogeneity using a Shapiro-Wilk and Levene's test, respectively. An analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) and Tukey's posthoc tests were used to identify differences in all variables between the young, old trained and old untrained groups. Sex was used as a covariate when assessing participant characteristics and vascular data, whilst both sex and years of education were used as covariates when assessing the CANTAB data. Effect sizes of the main vascular variables were calculated as Eta squared (η^2) where values of 0.01, 0.06 and 0.14 represented a small, medium and large effect, respectively. Pearson's and Spearman Rho partial correlations were also used to assess associations between the vascular and cognitive variables between the older trained and untrained groups, again with sex and years of education as covariates. Statistical analysis was performed using Jamovi (Version 0.9) and SPSS (Version 25), and a $P < 0.05$ level was chosen. All data are presented as means \pm standard deviations (SD).

5.3 Results

ICA blood flow could not be measured in 1 trained and 3 untrained older adults due to poor image quality, and also in 1 young participant due to the inability to image the ICA. Furthermore, 1 IMT value from the young and older trained group could not be measured due to image quality. One participant within the older untrained group did not perform the $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ assessment due to self-reporting an earlier diagnosis of supraventricular tachycardia. Furthermore, 3 older untrained participants stated that they did not understand particular tests within the CANTAB assessment and therefore their data for said tests were removed from the dataset (RTI n=1; SWM n=1; RVP n=1; MOT n=1). Additionally, data from the DMS assessment was removed from 1 older untrained participant as a result of being interrupted during the test, and data from the MOT was removed for another older untrained participant due to a technical fault occurring during the test.

5.3.1 Participant Characteristics

The older untrained group demonstrated lower $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ values than the young and older trained groups (Table 5 - 1; Figure 5 - 1). Resting HR was lower in the older trained group compared to the older untrained or young cohorts. ANCOVA analysis identified that females had lower systolic BP (SBP) ($P = 0.001$) and $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ values ($P = 0.024$) compared to male participants. Additionally, years of education was lower in the older untrained group compared to the older trained and young cohorts.

5.3.2 Vascular Measures

Females had smaller baseline brachial artery diameters compared to male participants ($P < 0.001$). ICA flow was lower in the older at the $P < 0.05$ level trained compared to the younger participants only (mean difference: $172 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, $P = 0.031$; $\eta^2 = 0.21$). In addition, intima-media thickness (IMT) was smaller in the young compared to both of the older groups ($P < 0.001$; $\eta^2 = 0.41$; Table 5 - 1). However, there were no other differences in any of the peripheral or central vascular variables measured between all three groups ($P > 0.05$; Table 5 - 1).

5.3.3 Cognitive Function

The young participants performed better than both older groups in a measure of strategy during the spatial working memory (SWM) test at the $P < 0.05$ level ($P < 0.001$; $\eta^2 = 0.43$; Table 5 - 2). Compared to the young cohort older trained participants exhibited more errors (between errors $P = 0.002$; $\eta^2 = 0.33$; total errors $P = 0.001$; $\eta^2 = 0.33$), poorer mean reaction time ($P = 0.018$; $\eta^2 = 0.232$) and first attempt memory performance ($P = 0.027$; $\eta^2 = 0.20$) in the SWM, reaction time (RTI) and paired associates learning (PAL) tests, respectively. The older trained group also scored a greater number of total errors during the PAL test compared to the young and older untrained groups ($P < 0.001$; $\eta^2 = 0.30$). Additionally, higher ICA blood flow was associated with reduced latency during the RVP test ($r = -0.604$, $P = 0.005$), whereas higher FMD was associated with increased total errors during the PAL test ($r = 0.521$, $P = 0.011$).

Table 5 - 1. Participant Characteristics and Vascular Variables.

	Young	Older		P-Value
		Trained	Untrained	
N	9	13	14	-
M/F	7/2	10/3	8/6	-
Age	26 ± 4	65 ± 4 *	68 ± 6 *	< .001
M/F	7/2	10/3	8/6	-
Height (cm)	174.0 ± 6.5	171.0 ± 5.4	167.0 ± 11.0	0.261
Mass (kg)	75.7 ± 8.7	63.3 ± 8.2 *	72.5 ± 14.5 †	0.005
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.9 ± 3.0	21.5 ± 2.2 *	25.7 ± 3.1 †	0.001
Years of Education	17.1 ± 1.9	17.4 ± 3.9	14.2 ± 3.0 †	0.039
Resting HR (b.min ⁻¹)	65 ± 12	48 ± 6 *	61 ± 6 †	< .001
SBP (mmHg)	124 ± 12	131 ± 16	122 ± 13	0.288
DBP (mmHg)	71 ± 6	71 ± 7	70 ± 8	0.987

$\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ (ml.kg.min ⁻¹)	50.2 ± 6.3	49.9 ± 7.2	33.8 ± 7.0 *†	< .001
FMD (%)	8.1 ± 3.9	7.7 ± 5.7	8.6 ± 5.2	0.971
AUC Shear Normalised FMD x10 ⁻⁴ (%)	0.82 ± 1.40	1.24 ± 2.62	1.19 ± 1.63	0.890
Brachial Artery Baseline Diameter (cm)	0.41 ± 0.07	0.45 ± 0.07	0.43 ± 0.07	0.172
Brachial Artery Time to Peak Diameter (s)	139 ± 86	189 ± 146	131 ± 69	0.202
CCA Flow (ml.min ⁻¹)	580 ± 84.3	454 ± 139	570 ± 165	0.074
CCA IMT (mm)	0.50 ± 0.04	0.75 ± 0.17 *	0.73 ± 0.14 *	< .001
ICA Flow (ml.min ⁻¹)	492 ± 133	320 ± 148 *	396 ± 131	0.039

An asterisk (*) represents a difference from the young group, and a cross (†) represents a difference from the older trained group at the P < 0.05 level. M/F, male/female; HR, heart rate; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; FMD, flow mediated dilation; CCA, common carotid artery; ICA, internal carotid artery.

Table 5 - 2. CANTAB Cognitive Assessment Results of all Three Groups.

Cognitive Domain	CANTAB Variable	Young	Older Trained	Older Untrained
Attention and Short-Term Visual Memory	Delayed Matching to Sample (DMS)			
	Mean correct latency (ms)	3234 ± 852	4217 ± 1534	4224 ± 936
	Mean correct latency 12s delay (ms)	3922 ± 1043	4767 ± 1544	5245 ± 1325
	Mean correct latency all delays (ms)	3499 ± 994	4491 ± 1613	4506 ± 1157
	Percent Correct (%)	90.6 ± 7.3	89.2 ± 8.9	83.1 ± 11.5
Sensorimotor Function	Motor Screening Task (MOT)			

	Mean latency (ms)	690 ± 117	805 ± 143	800 ± 180
Visual Episodic Memory / Learning	Paired Associates Learning (PAL)			
	First attempt memory score	14.8 ± 4.1	10.1 ± 3.8 *	12.2 ± 3.8
	Last stage reached	10.0 ± 2.5	9.1 ± 2.5	9.9 ± 2.8
	Total errors	8.8 ± 5.9	17.4 ± 7.6 *	11.9 ± 6.6 †
	Total adjusted errors	11.9 ± 11.4	23.8 ± 14.1	17.3 ± 14.4
Processing and Psychomotor / Processing Speed	Reaction Time (RTI)			
	Mean 5 choice movement time (ms)	224.0 ± 37.9	284.0 ± 79.5	318.0 ± 99.8

	Mean 5 choice reaction time (ms)	391 ± 28	437 ± 48 *	428 ± 23
Sustained Attention and Speed of Response	Rapid Visual Information Processing (RVP)			
	Sensitivity	0.92 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.04	0.91 ± 0.07
	Mean response latency (ms)	469 ± 35	567 ± 127	551 ± 130
Working Memory and Executive Function	Spatial Working Memory (SWM)			
	Between errors 12-box stage	18.1 ± 15.2	39.7 ± 11.0 *	28.8 ± 13.4
	Strategy 12 box stage	8.3 ± 5.3	17.4 ± 2.8 *	15.4 ± 5.0 *
	Total errors 12 box stage	18.4 ± 15.8	42.4 ± 14.2 *	29.8 ± 13.8

Data are presented as means ± standard deviations. An asterisk (*) represents a difference from the young group, and a cross (†) represents a difference from the older trained group at the P < 0.05 level.

5.4 Discussion

The current study aimed to identify whether long-term endurance training positively influenced peripheral (brachial) and central (carotid) vascular structure and function, alongside cognitive performance in healthy older adults. In this cohort, the main findings are: (1) training status in the older participants did not affect any central or peripheral vascular measures; and (2) older trained individuals demonstrated less ICA blood flow in comparison to the young control group. In terms of cognitive function, young participants exhibited superior executive function, however, there were only trivial differences between groups for other measures of cognitive function. Similarly, there were few associations between peripheral or central vascular measures and cognitive function. Consequently, the present findings fail to support the hypothesis that superior central vascular structure, blood flow or peripheral FMD from long-term endurance training would augment cognitive function in the healthy older cohort.

5.4.1 Central Vascular Measures

A number of studies have investigated the effects of long-term endurance training and higher levels of aerobic fitness on central vascular structure, blood flow, and peripheral FMD in cohorts of healthy older adults. For example, healthy older males who are aerobically exercise-trained have been reported to exhibit higher MCA blood velocity profiles compared to their untrained counterparts (Ainslie et al., 2008; Bailey et al., 2013). However, each study reported velocities of $9 \text{ cm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ higher in the ‘trained’ group despite one study including vigorously trained competitors (Ainslie et al., 2008), whereas the other included males who were reported to meet the minimum PA guidelines only ($150 \text{ min}\cdot\text{week}^{-1}$) (Bailey et al., 2013). Although these findings may suggest that adhering to the minimum PA guidelines benefits vascular blood flow, the highly trained participants in the present study did not exhibit superior

ICA flow compared to their untrained peers. However, the present study included untrained participants who participated in some recreational PA, whereas Ainslie et al. and Brown et al. both recruited 'sedentary' participants. Therefore, it may be possible that even small levels of involvement in PA could have preserved ICA flow with age, explaining the lack of differences in ICA flow between the trained and untrained groups. However, as the present study did not measure intracranial physiology, the results are not directly comparable.

In terms of central extracranial arterial blood measures, greater flow within the ICA, but not the vertebral artery has been reported in healthy older trained males compared to their sedentary counterparts, despite not differing from a younger healthy cohort (Braz et al., 2017). These findings contrast with findings from the present study which observed no differences in ICA flow between highly trained and untrained healthy older adults, measured at the $P < 0.05$ level. However, Braz et al. reported higher ICA flow in the trained group despite the trained and untrained participants exhibiting smaller differences in $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ compared to the groups in the present study (mean difference: 9.9 vs. 16.1 ml.kg.min⁻¹). These findings could suggest that higher levels of $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ may be less important for arterial preservation as no differences were observed between groups who exhibited larger differences in $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$. Conversely, the duration of endurance training may have a greater influence on arterial blood flow compared to levels of $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ only. However, Braz et al. did not report the training duration of participants. Although the trained participants in the present study had engaged in endurance programmes for an average of 30 years, whilst speculative, participants who exhibited higher ICA flow may have exercised for a longer duration and possibly preserved ICA blood flow to a greater extent (Braz et al., 2017). Furthermore, methodical differences between the studies include the bilateral and unilateral assessment of the ICA flow by Braz et al. (2017) and the present study, respectively. As handedness has shown to affect ICA flow between the left and

right arteries (Bogren et al., 1994), it is possible that the present study may not have reported true ICA flow as measurements were taken from the right artery only.

5.4.2 Peripheral Vascular Measures

Similar to the cognitive and central vascular findings, the lack of differences in brachial artery FMD between groups contrasts with various reports which have demonstrated decreases with age (Skaug et al., 2013), and improvements with long-term endurance training (Campbell et al., 2019). Moreover, structural differences of the brachial artery were also not present between the trained and untrained group, despite reports suggesting that adaptations can occur from endurance training (Green et al., 2012). Whilst reports have supported the use of long-term endurance training to benefit endothelial vasodilatory capacity, the mean FMD values of the untrained group within the current study are higher than those which have been published within similar cohorts (FMD \leq 5 %) (Eskurza et al., 2004; Walker et al., 2009; Pierce et al., 2011a, 2011b; DeVan et al., 2013; Grace et al., 2015).

One reason which may explain the minimal cognitive and vascular differences observed between groups may be related to the recruitment strategy for the present study. Despite the participants in previous FMD-focused studies also being healthy, unmedicated and free from vascular disease, most studies included ‘untrained’ participants who were sedentary or those who had not participated in regular PA for \geq 2 years. Attempts were made to recruit solely inactive healthy older participants within the current study however, those willing to participate self-reported recreational participation in low to moderate intensity pastimes including walking, golf, indoor bowls, walking football, swimming, and general gym/leisure sessions. Therefore, due to the chosen inclusion criteria for this study, both older groups may represent

a particularly healthy sample of the population. The lack of differences in FMD between the young and older groups further suggests that the older cohort were especially healthy in that they were not dissimilar to individuals on average approximately 40 years younger. Although $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ was lower in the untrained cohort, it is possible that the untrained individuals could have exhibited better FMD compared to completely inactive and sedentary individuals recruited in previous studies. For example, light and moderate levels of walking training have been shown to improve FMD in older adults (Prakhinkit et al., 2014; Suboc et al., 2014). Consequently, both older groups may have demonstrated similar FMD values due to exhibiting generally good health profiles whilst both experiencing preserved endothelial vasodilatory capacity from participating in PA, even at low to moderate intensities.

5.4.3 Cognitive Function

While the present study lacks evidence that long-term exercise training benefits cognitive performance in healthy older adults, previous reports have published contrasting results. Long-term training has been previously shown to benefit several cognitive domains including reaction time (Baylor and Spirduso, 1988; Clarkson-Smith and Hartley, 1989; Ari et al., 2004; Hatta et al., 2005), executive functioning (Tseng et al., 2013), reasoning, and working memory (Clarkson-Smith and Hartley, 1989) in comparison to inactive control groups. However, methodical differences exist between previous reports and the current study. For example, Tseng et al. (2013) reported better executive functioning in healthy older masters athletes compared to their sedentary peers after controlling for global intelligence. Despite long-term exercise also proving beneficial in a separate test of executive function without controlling for intelligence, all participants were screened for dementia prior to participation (Tseng et al., 2013). In contrast, participants in the present study were not screened for

intelligence or dementia. As one in 14 adults over the age of 65 are at risk of developing dementia (Prince et al., 2014), it is possible that some participants may have exhibited traits of dementia, and thus may have confounded upon the potential impact of long-term exercise on cognition within this sample. Participant type also differed from the present report as some studies included a combination of middle-aged and older participants (Baylor and Spirduso, 1988; Clarkson-Smith and Hartley, 1989), all-female (Baylor and Spirduso, 1988) or male (Ari et al., 2004) cohorts, masters athletes training for shorter (Baylor and Spirduso, 1988; Hatta et al., 2005) or longer durations than the current study (Ari et al., 2004), and control groups consisting of solely sedentary and not recreationally active control groups (Ari et al., 2004).

Unlike the effects of exercise on peripheral and central vascular measures, the effects of long-term endurance training on cognitive function remains equivocal as other reports have found little or no evidence to suggest that long-term exercise has a beneficial effect on cognitive function (Winker et al., 2010; Young et al., 2016). One particular study reported no differences in cognitive functions including information processing speed, reaction time, and executive functioning between an initial sample of 27 super-veterans and 23 non-sedentary controls matched for age, sex, education, depression, and intelligence (Young et al., 2016). Although the present study did not control for intelligence or depression, our study, and earlier reports (Winker et al., 2010) have also reported minimal or no differences in cognitive function between highly trained and non-sedentary control groups. A recent meta-analysis reported that various types of PA of at least a moderate intensity could improve cognitive function independent of baseline cognitive status (Northey et al., 2018). Therefore, it may be possible that non-sedentary control groups could gain cognitive benefits from participating in some form of PA, thus reducing the cognitive gap between the two groups.

Although several studies have investigated the effect of long-term exercise training on a number of peripheral or central vascular variables, and on the cognitive function of healthy older adults, a lack of studies has investigated both factors within the same cohort or analysis. Such data would be valuable to determine whether potential long-term exercise-induced adaptations in various vascular and cognitive variables occur independently of each other or occur as part of an integrated central and/or peripheral vascular and neuropsychological response to training. At present, few studies have assessed the effects of long-term exercise training or aerobic capacity on both, vascular variables and cognitive function in healthy middle-aged and older adults. For example, Brown et al. (2010) reported that trained postmenopausal females exhibited superior cerebrovascular conductance and MAP of the MCA, in addition to better cognitive performance compared to their 'sedentary' counterparts. Similarly, healthy middle-aged exercise-trained adults demonstrated better brachial FMD ($P < 0.01$), performance on various cognitive domains ($P < 0.05$), and whilst not at the $P < 0.05$ level, higher CVR (4.69 vs 4.19 %/mmHg; $P = 0.052$) compared to an untrained cohort (Tarumi et al., 2015). The studies also reported positive associations between superior vascular variables and cognitive function when assessed at rest, and during isocapnia, thus suggesting that links between a superior cerebrovascular environment and cognitive performance exist. However, the results from the present study contrast with previous findings as we identified that long-term endurance training of 9 years or more did not benefit vascular variables or cognitive function in the healthy older adults compared to their age-matched untrained counterparts.

It is likely that the possible discrepancies between the present study and that of Brown et al. (2010) and Tarumi et al. (2015) may be due to the number of inter-study methodological differences. Firstly, whilst Tarumi et al. (2015) and the present study both assessed brachial

artery FMD, the two previous reports assessed cerebrovascular function and not central extra-cranial function. Thus, whilst there were no differences in brachial artery FMD between groups in the present study, the results may suggest that exercise may influence intra-cranial vascular variables function to a greater extent than carotid structure and blood flow. Additionally, whilst the training duration of the postmenopausal females was not documented (Brown et al., 2010), Tarumi et al. (2015) included trained participants who exercised at least 4 days.week⁻¹, and sedentary participants who self-reported no regular exercise in the last year. In contrast, the current study included a non-sedentary ‘inactive’ group who reported participating in low levels of unstructured exercise. Furthermore, the present study assessed mostly older males, whereas the other reports focused on mostly middle-aged females (Tarumi et al., 2015), and an exclusively postmenopausal female cohort (Brown et al., 2010). It is possible that females may experience greater benefits of exercise as studies consisting of mostly older females demonstrate greater cognitive improvements after periods of exercise training compared to their male counterparts (Barha et al., 2017a).

5.4.4 Limitations

Despite efforts to reduce the number of limitations in the present study, some limitations exist. Firstly, as the aim of the study was to assess the effects of long-term endurance training on various vascular and cognitive measures on the healthy ageing process, a healthy cohort was targeted for recruitment. As discussed previously, we were unable to recruit a fully sedentary healthy group as those willing to participate self-reported recreational engagement in PA. However, despite the effect of low PA levels on ageing health, the untrained older group remained healthy despite participating in PA less than the WHO’s recommended minimum PA guidelines for older adults (World Health Organisation, 2011). Moreover, both older groups demonstrated a healthy vascular and cognitive profile as little

differences between the older participants and the young ‘active control’ group were observed. Therefore, the generalisability of these findings to the wider ageing population, particularly of the older untrained group, is questionable. Moreover, although participants of both sexes were included, each of the three groups consisted of mostly male participants. Therefore, these findings may not also generalise to a female population.

Secondly, although CANTAB is a widely used method of assessing cognitive function digitally, it has been argued that CANTAB may not be as sensitive as traditional neuropsychological batteries as it has been shown to lack the specificity to differentiate between separate cognitive domains (Lenehan et al., 2016). Furthermore, as various tests within the Alzheimer’s CANTAB battery are designed to measure cognitive function between healthy and cognitively impaired populations, it is possible that the battery was not sensitive enough to determine differences between the three healthy cohorts used. Moreover, an earlier study in young adults identified only weak to moderate associations between the CANTAB and tests within a traditional neuropsychological battery when controlling for factors such as years of education (Smith et al., 2013). As the CANTAB data within the current study was also controlled for by years of education, it is likely that the sensitivity of the test reduced further and could have underestimated the true impact of long-term endurance training and ageing on cognitive function. Additionally, although the CANTAB assessment includes an initial motor screening task to assess the viability of the assessment with each participant, no formal screening for cognitive impairment was conducted. Screening for conditions such as depression and low mental well-being could have highlighted those at risk of cognitive impairment (Lim et al., 2013; Allerhand et al., 2014; Rock et al., 2014), potentially improving the ability of CANTAB to detect differences in cognitive function between groups.

Additionally, although exercise, alcohol and caffeine restrictions were made prior to visits, participants were not asked to fast or abstain from usual daily vitamin consumption. As dietary factors such as the consumption of polyphenols or ascorbic acid are known to affect FMD measurements (Thijssen et al., 2019), consumption prior to participation could have affected true FMD values.

Nonetheless, the present study is the first to assess cognitive performance alongside both, central and peripheral vascular measures in a cohort of long-term endurance-trained and untrained healthy older adults. However, future research including long-term trained and completely sedentary healthy older adults is required to determine whether participation in regular exercise can benefit both, systemic vascular variables, and cognitive function. Such information would be valuable to determine whether better vascular structure and blood flow from endurance training also augments cognitive health, thus helping to delay the ageing process and related comorbidities.

5.5 Conclusion

Overall, the healthy older long-term endurance-trained adults did not exhibit superior central vascular structure and blood flow, or peripheral FMD in comparison to healthy older adults who perform non-structured, but recreational levels of PA. Long-term endurance training also did not appear to benefit cognitive performance in the healthy older cohort, which may be due to the lack of differences in systemic vascular variables between the active and inactive groups.

CHAPTER 6

HABITUAL EXERCISE PROTECTS CAROTID ARTERY COMPLIANCE, BUT NOT COGNITIVE FUNCTION IN HEALTHY MIDDLE-AGED FEMALES: A CROSS-SECTIONAL APPROACH

6.1 Introduction

Ageing females are vulnerable to steep declines in vascular health as a result of falling oestrogen concentrations, and the resulting reduction in cardio-protection (Mendelsohn, 2002). Elevated levels of oxidative stress (Donato et al., 2007), and inflammation (Ungvari et al., 2004) within the peripheral arterial system from advancing age contributes to a decrease in the release of vasoactive substances such as nitric oxide (NO) (Taddei et al., 2001), causing increases vascular tone and intraluminal pressure (Haynes et al., 1993). Consequently, elevated blood pressure (BP) from greater vascular tone may further increase inflammatory responses within the vessel, accelerating the progress of atherosclerosis (Hansson et al., 2005; Savoia and Schiffrin, 2006). Ageing is also associated with stiffening of central conduit vessels such as the carotid artery (CA), which are likely due to increases in arterial adventitial collagen, arterial calcification, and reductions in medial elastin (Fleenor et al., 2010). As a result, the arterial walls are less compliant, limiting Windkessel buffering and increasing vascular pulse pressure (PP) which results in further damage to local and distal vasculature, including micro-vessels (Liao et al., 2004). However, lifestyle modifications such as physical activity (PA) and exercise have also been shown to delay the effects of vascular ageing.

PA and exercise are recognised as effective strategies to help ameliorate age-related vascular decline. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses have shown that middle-aged and older life-long exercisers exhibit superior peripheral endothelial function compared with their sedentary or less aerobically fit counterparts, as assessed by brachial artery flow mediated dilation (FMD) (Montero et al., 2014; Campbell et al., 2019). Central arterial compliance and systemic arterial stiffness have also been reported to improve in postmenopausal females after participation in a 12 week aerobic (Sugawara et al., 2004) or combined aerobic and resistance

exercise intervention (Figuroa et al., 2011), respectively. Furthermore, healthy individuals with higher levels of aerobic fitness demonstrate reductions in systemic arterial stiffness across the life span (Vaitkevicius et al., 1993). Improvements in arterial compliance from exercise may be attributed to reduced calcification and collagen build-up within the CA, in addition to increased elastic tissue within the aorta, as seen in animal studies (Koutsis et al., 1995; Fleenor et al., 2010).

Age-associated declines in central and peripheral vascular health have also been related to changes in cognitive function with conditions such as increasing the risk of cognitive impairment (Debette et al., 2011; Roberts et al., 2015; González et al., 2018). Since a stiffer central vasculature is less able to buffer pulsatile blood flow towards the brain, it increases the potential for microvascular damage, micro-haemorrhages, and tissue ischemia (Mitchell et al., 2011). Stiffer central arteries are therefore believed to impair cerebrovascular function and contribute to cognitive dysfunction (Wong et al., 2002; Hajjar et al., 2016; Thorin-Trescases et al., 2018). Indeed, there is increasing evidence to support this view; a recent systematic review reported that individuals with endothelial dysfunction also experienced impaired cognitive functions in the areas of attention, executive functioning and working memory (Naiberg et al., 2016). More recently, ageing associated declines in brachial artery FMD have been reported to predict cognitive impairments in healthy young and older adults (Csipo et al., 2019). However, healthy older individuals who are active, or who have higher levels of aerobic fitness often exhibit superior cognitive health (Clarkson-Smith and Hartley, 1989; Hillman et al., 2002; Aichberger et al., 2010), possibly due to a number of advantageous vascular variables (Barnes and Corkery, 2018). Moreover, superior cognitive function has been shown to associate with cerebrovascular function and brachial FMD in healthy middle-aged and older cohorts (Brown et al., 2010; Tarumi et al., 2015). Therefore, PA and exercise may not only

improve age-associated declines in central and peripheral vascular health, but this superior vascular health may also help to delay the onset of cognitive decline.

However, current research has been limited to the assessment of cognitive function with either peripheral or central vascular variables. Consequently, no previous study has examined cognitive function with both, central extra-cranial (CA) and peripheral (brachial) vascular variables within the same cohort. Therefore, whilst exercise-induced improvements in arterial stiffness and FMD are believed to influence cognitive health, currently, such associations can only be implied. Cognitive research containing a range of vascular assessments is therefore needed to understand whether central and peripheral vascular variables collectively influence the cognitive health of the active ageing population.

Whilst conventional measures are most commonly used to assess arterial stiffness, it is argued that ultrasound speckle tracking may be a superior method of assessing central arterial compliance (Bjallmark et al., 2010). Greater arterial expansion (peak circumferential strain; PCS) and peak rate of expansion (peak strain rate; PSR) have previously been seen in younger adults (Bjallmark et al., 2010; Talbot et al., 2020), in higher aerobic fitness, and in young exercisers versus non-exercisers (Pugh et al., 2018; Talbot et al., 2020). Additionally, differences in PCS and PSR have occurred during and immediately after an acute bout of resistance exercise when compared to rest in young healthy males (Black et al., 2016). However, no previous study has used this method to measure central arterial compliance within active and inactive healthy middle-aged females during and immediately after acute resistance exercise. As middle-aged females are at a high risk of vascular impairment (Moreau et al., 2012; Hildreth et al., 2014), and possible declines in cognitive function (Georgakis et al., 2016),

it is important to elucidate the potential links between commonly used and novel physiological measures with cognitive performance to better understand how to delay ageing-associated declines in health and well-being.

Therefore, the aims of the study were to 1) identify whether regularly exercising healthy middle-aged females have superior peripheral and central vascular structure, and blood flow alongside cognitive function compared to inactive controls; 2) determine whether CA speckle-tracking derived PCS and PSR measures were superior in the active versus the inactive cohort; 3) establish whether differences in PCS and PSR exist pre, during and immediately after a 3-minute handgrip (HG) exercise; and 4) determine whether associations exist between measured vascular variables and cognitive function. It was hypothesised that physically active healthy middle-aged females would have superior peripheral and central vascular outcomes, including increased PCS and PSR, in addition to greater cognitive function compared to the inactive group. Furthermore, we hypothesised that the HG exercise would influence CA strain by reducing levels during the exercise, and lastly, that associations would be present between superior vascular and cognitive variables.

6.2 Methods

6.2.1 Participants

Twenty active and 32 inactive healthy middle-aged females were initially recruited for the cross-sectional study based on whether they self-reported engaging in regular PA. Each participant received medical clearance via written approval from their general practitioner prior to participation. Eight and 19 participants were subsequently excluded from the active and inactive groups, respectively for reasons outlined in Figure 6 - 1. Participants who exhibited

$\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ levels greater or less than 80 % of their age-predicted maximum aerobic capacity were excluded from the untrained and active groups, respectively. Age predicted $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ levels for each participant were calculated based on a large database of aerobic capacity reference data of healthy individuals aged 20 – 90 years (Loe et al., 2013), and a similar approach to create distinct study groups has been observed previously (Brown et al., 2010). As all participants within the present study were healthy and not all ‘inactive’ females identified as being completely sedentary, the decision to exclude participants based on an aerobic capacity threshold was taken in an attempt to study two distinct groups within the study. It was also for these reasons that the inactive group within this study have not been classified as ‘sedentary’. The final groups therefore consisted of 12 active and 13 inactive participants.

Figure 6 - 1. Schematic of participant recruitment, group allocation and reasons for exclusion within the middle-aged cohort. HRT; hormone replacement therapy, BP; blood pressure.

Prior to participation, participants completed a consent form, medical and information questionnaires as stated in Chapter 4 (section 4.4.3). To the best of our knowledge, all participants were non-smokers and did not suffer from overt medical conditions affecting the cardiovascular system. Medications taken by participants consisted of antihistamines and antidepressants, in addition to medications for treating hypothyroidism, migraines, and osteoporosis (Appendix 4). No participants were using cardioactive medication or hormone replacement therapy (HRT).

6.2.2 Protocol

The study took place during two separate visits in January (active cohort) and February 2019 (inactive cohort) at the University of Wales, Trinity St David. All participants arrived at the laboratory after a 3 hour fast and having not consumed alcohol or caffeine for 24 hours. All participants were also asked to refrain from strenuous PA 24 hours prior to each visit.

During visits, participants were assessed for their height, mass and body fat percentage as discussed in Chapter 4 (sections 4.2.1 and 4.4.4). Following anthropometric assessment, a brachial artery ultrasound scan and FMD assessment was performed as described in Chapter 4 (section 4.2.3). CA ultrasound scans at rest, during and after acute isometric HG exercise was also performed as discussed in Chapter 4 (sections 4.2.2, 4.4.8 and 4.4.9). Additionally, heart rate (HR) and blood pressure (BP) measures were collected during the carotid ultrasound assessment via methods also reported in Chapter 4. Following the vascular ultrasound assessments, the cognitive test battery and $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ test was performed as described in Chapter 4 (Sections 4.4.11 and 4.4.10, respectively).

6.2.3 Statistical Analysis

Data were tested for normality and equal variances using a Shapiro-Wilk and Levene's test, respectively. Variables assessed only at rest were analysed using an unpaired student's t-test or Mann-Whitney U test to identify differences between the active and inactive groups. A 2 way repeated-measures ANOVA (group x time) was used to analyse variables measured between groups at rest, during and immediately after the 3 minute isometric HG exercise. When significance was present, Tukey's posthoc test was used to identify differences between groups/time-points. Pearson's and Spearman's correlation coefficients determined correlations between variables that met, or failed to meet normality assumptions, respectively. Effect sizes for the main resting vascular and cognitive outcome variables were calculated as Cohen's D (d) where values of 0.2, 0.5 and 0.8 represented a small, medium and large effect, respectively (Cohen, 1988). Additionally, the effect sizes of the main vascular variables measured pre, during and post HG exercise was calculated as Eta squared (η^2) where values of 0.01, 0.06 and 0.14 represented a small, medium, and large effect, respectively. All data are displayed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), and a $P < 0.05$ level was chosen. Jamovi statistical software (version 0.9) was used to perform all statistical analysis (The jamovi project, 2019).

6.3 Results

BP data was irretrievable for 1 inactive and 3 active participants and therefore was not included in the overall mean and SDs for haemodynamic and conventional stiffness measurements. Due to poor image quality, CA images for 1 inactive participant were excluded from the analysis. As a result of technical difficulties, 1 active participant did not complete the HG exercise and therefore was not included in the carotid artery PCS and PSR analysis.

Finally, FMD results are missing from 2 active participants due to: 1) poor image quality; and 2) voluntary withdrawal from the FMD assessment.

Table 6 - 1. Participant Characteristics and Resting Variables

Measured Variables	Active	Inactive	P-value
Age (years)	56 ± 5	57 ± 4	0.73
$\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ (ml.kg.min ⁻¹)	34.5 ± 6.1	22.8 ± 2.6	<0.001
Age Predicted $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ (%)	102.6 ± 16.1	67.6 ± 6.4	<0.001
Height (m)	1.62 ± 0.06	1.63 ± 0.06	0.64
Mass (kg)	64.2 ± 8.8	78.5 ± 11.4	0.002
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.6 ± 4.1	29.6 ± 4.7	0.009
Body fat (%)	26.6 ± 7.6	40.1 ± 4.2	<0.001
SBP (mmHg)	126 ± 26	140 ± 17	0.158
DBP (mmHg)	66 ± 16	73 ± 12	0.256
MAP (mmHg)	86 ± 19	94 ± 14	0.30
PP (mmHg)	61 ± 14	65 ± 12	0.399
Common Carotid Artery			
Maximum Longitudinal Diameter (cm)	0.58 ± 0.04	0.60 ± 0.04	0.28
Minimum Longitudinal Diameter (cm)	0.51 ± 0.03	0.53 ± 0.04	0.04
Posterior intima-media thickness (mm)	0.63 ± 0.09	0.62 ± 0.10	0.79
Blood Flow (ml.min ⁻¹)	442.0 ± 71.3	508.9 ± 67.2	0.023
Pulsatility Index	1.98 ± 0.35	1.69 ± 0.21	0.026
Peak Circumferential Strain (%)	5.68 ± 1.73	4.39 ± 0.96	0.044
Peak Strain Rate (s ⁻¹)	0.43 ± 0.15	0.35 ± 0.08	0.097

Peak Recoil rate (s ⁻¹)	-0.15 ± 0.05	-0.14 ± 0.04	0.470
Pulse Transit Time (ms)	54.3 ± 17.4	45.0 ± 13.1	0.158
β ₁ (mm ² ·kPa ⁻¹)	6.6 ± 3.0	7.8 ± 3.4	0.758
E _p (kPa)	77.9 ± 38.3	105.0 ± 43.2	0.169
Internal Carotid Artery			
Maximum longitudinal diameter (cm)	0.42 ± 0.05	0.44 ± 0.06	0.26
Blood Flow (ml.min ⁻¹)	352.8 ± 124.7	416.1 ± 109.5	0.42
Pulsatility Index	1.43 ± 0.39	1.18 ± 0.14	0.055
Brachial Artery			
Baseline diameter (cm)	0.36 ± 0.05	0.35 ± 0.04	0.54
FMD (%)	6.6 ± 2.7	7.0 ± 3.3	0.76
Shear Normalised FMD x10 ⁻⁵ (%)	2.6 ± 13.7	7.6 ± 12.5	0.22
FMD Time to peak (s)	77.6 ± 22.3	120.5 ± 71.8	0.08

Participant characteristics, haemodynamics, vascular structure, blood flow and compliance of the active and inactive groups during resting conditions. Data are presented as means ± standard deviations, and p-values at the P < 0.05 level are displayed in bold. $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$, peak aerobic capacity; BMI, body mass index; HR, heart rate; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; MAP, mean arterial pressure; PP, pulse pressure; E_p, Peterson's Elastic Modulus; FMD, flow-mediated dilation.

6.3.1 Participant Characteristics

The characteristics of the active and inactive groups are contained within Table 6 - 1. There were no differences in age or haemodynamic variables between the active and inactive

groups ($P > 0.05$). However, the active participants exhibited higher $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ and age predicted $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ percentage, and lower body mass, fat percentage and body mass index (BMI) compared to the inactive middle-aged females (Table 6 - 1).

6.3.2 Vascular Measures at Rest

The active group demonstrated higher levels of common carotid PCS ($P = 0.044$; Cohen's $d = 0.93$), and a smaller minimum common carotid diameter in comparison to the inactive group ($P=0.040$; Cohen's $d = 0.95$) at the $P < 0.05$ level. Conversely, the inactive females exhibited lower pulsatility index (PI) of the common carotid artery ($P = 0.026$; Cohen's $d = 0.83$). No other differences in carotid or brachial artery measures were observed between the two groups (Table 6 - 1).

6.3.3 Vascular Measures During and After Handgrip Exercise

All haemodynamic variables were increased at the $P < 0.001$ level during and immediately after the 3 minute isometric HG exercise compared to resting conditions (SBP $\eta^2 = 0.162$; DBP $\eta^2 = 0.100$; MAP $\eta^2 = 0.151$; PP $\eta^2 = 0.136$; Table 6 - 3). However, only HR differed between groups at the $P < 0.05$ level; with the active group exhibiting lower HR ($P = 0.002$; $\eta^2 = 0.3$; mean difference (MD) = $11.9 \text{ b}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$).

Between-group effects at the $P < 0.05$ level were observed for PCS ($P = 0.003$; $\eta^2 = 0.30$; MD = 1.91 %) and PSR ($P = 0.004$; $\eta^2 = 0.26$; MD = 0.13 s^{-1}), whereby the active cohort exhibited superior values than the inactive group. However, there were no other between or within-group differences for the remaining ultrasound strain-derived variables (peak recoil rate

between groups $\eta^2 = 0.068$; $P = 0.141$; peak recoil rate within groups $\eta^2 = 0.009$; $P = 0.556$; pulse transit time between groups $\eta^2 = 0.022$; $P = 0.370$; pulse transit time within groups $\eta^2 = 0.015$; $P = 0.473$; Table 6 - 3). While no between-group differences existed in conventional stiffness measures Peterson's Elastic Modulus (E_p) ($\eta^2 = 0.121$; $P = 0.069$) and beta-1 stiffness index (β_1) ($\eta^2 = 0.097$; $P = 0.111$), E_p was elevated post HG compared to pre-HG measures in each group ($\eta^2 = 0.072$; $P = 0.01$). A time ($\eta^2 = 0.004$; $P = 0.026$), group ($\eta^2 = 0.007$; $P = 0.716$), and an interaction effect ($\eta^2 = 0.006$; $P = 0.008$) was observed for minimum short axis (SAX) diameter, whereby diameter decreased from rest to HG exercise ($P = 0.036$), and between rest to HG ($P = 0.002$) and post HG ($P = 0.020$) within the inactive group (Table 6 - 3).

Associations were present between $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ with PCS HG ($r = 0.502$, $P = 0.017$), PCS post HG ($r = 0.515$, $P = 0.012$), and PSR HG ($r = 0.459$, $P = 0.028$; Figure 6 - 3). Similarly, associations between age predicted $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ and PCS HG ($r = 0.515$, $P = 0.014$), PCS post HG ($r = 0.536$, $P = 0.008$), PSR HG ($r = 0.476$, $P = 0.022$) and PSR post HG ($r = 0.430$, $P = 0.040$) also existed. However, no associations between conventional stiffness measures and $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ were observed ($P > 0.05$; Figure 6 - 3). Finally, inverse correlations were present between PCS with E_p ($r = -0.283$, $p = 0.026$) when collated across all three timepoints.

Figure 6 - 2. Active and inactive group differences in corrected peak circumferential strain (%; A) and peak strain rate (s⁻¹; B) at rest, during and immediately after the 3 minute handgrip (HG)

exercise. Data are presented as individual data points with means \pm standard deviations. A main group effect in favour of the active cohort is presented as a cross ($\dagger = P < 0.01$).

Figure 6 - 3. Correlation analysis between measured $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ values and peak circumferential strain (A), peak strain rate (B), beta-1 stiffness index (β_1 ; C) and Peterson's elastic modulus (E_p ; D) when measured during the 3 minute HG exercise. Correlation coefficients and their respective p-values are displayed in bold.

6.3.4 Cognitive Assessment

Three inactive individuals were removed from the cognitive analysis as they identified at risk of depression and low well-being after completing the Centre for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (CES-D) and the Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale (WEMWBS) tests, respectively. In addition, three active individuals were removed as two also identified as at risk of depression, and one for low well-being. The only cognitive variable to differ between groups at the $P < 0.05$ level was animal fluency which was higher in the untrained cohort ($P = 0.002$; Cohen's $d = 1.7$; MD = 5.7 words; Table 6 - 2).

An inverse association existed between animal fluency performance with both, measured ($r = -0.533$; $P = 0.016$) and age predicted $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ ($r = -0.576$; $P = 0.008$). However, superior cognitive function during the animal verbal fluency test of the untrained cohort was not associated with any of the vascular variables which met the $P < 0.05$ level.

Table 6 - 2. Cognitive Test Battery Results

Cognitive Test	Active	Inactive	P-value
Trail Making			
Trail A (s)	26.5 ± 6.9	26.0 ± 7.9	0.90
Trail B (s)	55.9 ± 12.8	63.6 ± 21.4	0.36
Stroop Test			
Stroop 1 (s)	4.7 ± 0.8	4.8 ± 1.2	0.82

Stroop 2 (s)	4.9 ± 0.9	4.6 ± 0.8	0.45
Stroop 3 (s)	5.6 ± 0.9	6.4 ± 1.1	0.101
Stroop 4 (s)	11.8 ± 3.2	9 ± 3.5	0.075
Verbal Fluency			
Animals (n)	12 ± 3	18 ± 4	0.002
Words beginning with 's' (n)	11 ± 4	11 ± 4	0.701
Digit Span			
Forwards (n)	7 ± 2	7 ± 1	0.844
Backwards (n)	5 ± 1	4 ± 2	0.492

Data is presented as means ± standard deviations, and P-values at the $P < 0.05$ level are displayed in bold.

Table 6 - 3. Haemodynamic and Common Carotid Artery Variables

Variable	Active			Inactive			Main Effect P-Value		
	Rest	Handgrip	Post-Handgrip	Rest	Handgrip	Post-Handgrip	Time	Group	Interaction
Haemodynamics									
HR (b.min ⁻¹)	55 ± 6	57 ± 8	57 ± 7	64 ± 8	70 ± 10	70 ± 10	<0.001	0.002	0.102
SBP (mmHg)	126 ± 26	150 ± 19	147 ± 15	140 ± 17	160 ± 26	154 ± 24	<0.001	0.267	0.576
DBP (mmHg)	66 ± 16	78 ± 11	74 ± 9	73 ± 12	82 ± 16	79 ± 15	<0.001	0.342	0.676
MAP (mmHg)	86 ± 19	102 ± 12	98 ± 9	94 ± 14	108 ± 18	104 ± 17	<0.001	0.333	0.872
PP (mmHg)	61 ± 14	72 ± 14	73 ± 14	65 ± 12	77 ± 15	75 ± 13	<0.001	0.475	0.683
Common Carotid Artery									
Peak Circumferential Strain (%)	5.68 ± 1.73	5.73 ± 1.66	6.37 ± 1.42	4.39 ± 0.96	3.67 ± 1.49	3.99 ± 1.52	0.112	0.003	0.064
Peak Strain Rate (s ⁻¹)	0.43 ± 0.15	0.44 ± 0.11	0.48 ± 0.12	0.35 ± 0.08	0.28 ± 0.12	0.32 ± 0.12	0.130	0.004	0.172
Peak recoil rate (s ⁻¹)	-0.15 ± 0.05	-0.16 ± 0.06	-0.17 ± 0.04	-0.14 ± 0.04	-0.14 ± 0.05	-0.14 ± 0.04	0.556	0.141	0.587
Pulse Transit Time (ms)	54.3 ± 17.4	49.4 ± 17.5	46.9 ± 14.9	45.0 ± 13.1	48.1 ± 18.4	43.8 ± 12.7	0.473	0.370	0.530
Maximum SAX Diameter (cm)	0.60 ± 0.09	0.60 ± 0.08	0.60 ± 0.08	0.60 ± 0.05	0.62 ± 0.05	0.61 ± 0.06	0.581	0.789	0.053
Minimum SAX Diameter (cm)	0.55 ± 0.08	0.54 ± 0.07	0.55 ± 0.07	0.55 ± 0.05	0.56 ± 0.04 *	0.57 ± 0.05 *	0.026	0.716	0.008

Conventional Stiffness Indices

β_1 stiffness index ($\text{mm}^2 \cdot \text{kPa}^{-1}$)	6.6 ± 3.1	7.3 ± 3.0	8.4 ± 3.5	7.8 ± 3.4	9.7 ± 3.0	11.0 ± 6.8	0.072	0.111	0.444
E_p (kPa)	77.9 ± 38.3	107.0 ± 48.4	119.0 ± 53.9	105.0 ± 43.2	149.0 ± 57.0	167.0 ± 114.0	0.013	0.069	0.486

Data are presented as means \pm standard deviations at rest, during and immediately after the 3 minute isometric hand-grip exercise. P-values for the main effects of time point (rest, during the 3 minute HG and post HG), visit, and a time * visit interaction are reported, and values at the $P < 0.05$ level are displayed in bold. An asterisk (*) represents a posthoc difference from inactive resting conditions at the $P < 0.05$ level, as calculated by a time * group interaction. HR, heart rate; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; MAP, mean arterial pressure; PP, pulse pressure; SAX, short-axis; E_p , Peterson's Elastic Modulus; FMD, flow-mediated dilation.

6.4 Discussion

While previous studies have assessed either cognitive function, peripheral (brachial) or central (carotid) vascular variables in aerobically fit and unfit middle-aged and older adults, this study is the first to investigate whether differences existed in carotid arterial compliance, brachial FMD, and cognitive function between physically active versus inactive healthy middle-aged females. We also aimed to identify whether the novel ultrasound method speckle tracking could identify differences in CCA compliance in middle-aged females with different levels of aerobic fitness. The main findings of the present study are that active middle-aged females exhibit superior central vascular compliance by demonstrating greater levels of PCS and PSR compared to their inactive counterparts. However, except for higher CCA PI and blood flow in the inactive group at rest, few other differences in central or peripheral vascular variables were observed between groups. Furthermore, differences in cognitive function between groups were observed by a single test only, whereby the inactive cohort demonstrated better executive functioning via the animal verbal fluency assessment. Consequently, regular participation in PA and exercise appears to have a positive impact on certain central vascular measures within our cohort of healthy middle-aged females, yet minimal influences on peripheral vascular measures or cognitive function.

6.4.1 Central Vascular Measures

The current study is also the first to investigate the ability of ultrasound speckle tracking in identifying differences in CCA compliance of middle-aged females with different levels of aerobic fitness. The active middle-aged females demonstrated superior PCS and PSR levels compared to their inactive counterparts, as indicated by a between-group effect. Given that ageing is associated with reduced CCA PCS and PSR compared to younger individuals

(Bjallmark et al., 2010; Rosenberg et al., 2018; Talbot et al., 2020), and since PCS has been shown to be inversely correlated with age (Yuda et al., 2011; Park et al., 2012), the findings of the present study suggest that participation in regular exercise may ameliorate declines in CA structural integrity in middle-aged females. Furthermore, the associations between measured and age predicted $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ with measures of PCS and PSR during the HG exercise further support that central arterial elasticity and compliance may be influenced by cardiorespiratory fitness (CRF) levels, as reported previously (Pugh et al., 2018).

A reduction in central arterial compliance has been linked with arterial stiffening from increased arterial collagen and calcification, reduced elastin content, and stiffening of vascular smooth muscle cells (Fleenor et al., 2010; Qiu et al., 2010). However, maintaining PA and exercise participation into later life may help to preserve the arterial wall from the common symptoms of arterial ageing. For example, it has been argued that regular exercise can influence central arterial remodelling as exercise-induced increases in PP and arterial distension could realign collagen fibres within the arterial wall, which may alleviate arterial stiffening and improve arterial distension (Tanaka et al., 2000). Moreover, elastin content has also been shown to increase, and collagen content decrease in the large central arteries of exercise-trained aged rats (Gu et al., 2014). As a result, the greater levels of CCA PCS and PSR within the active group could help to buffer CA blood flow, and possibly protect the cerebral vasculature and tissue from damage caused by high pulsatile carotid blood flow (Mitchell et al., 2011). Such adaptations may better protect the artery during periods of physiological stress as an efficient buffering capacity is likely to be important during temporary increases in PP, including during and immediately after the isometric HG exercise. Consequently, enhanced buffering of PP may improve the blood flow profile within the CCA and ICA during exercise within the active compared to the inactive participants. However, as

measures of blood flow were not collected during or after the exercise protocol, it is not possible to determine if differences in CA blood flow profiles or PI occurred between groups during physiological stress. Nevertheless, these results emphasise the importance of remaining physically active in later life to help preserve aspects of vascular health.

Only two previous studies have investigated how PCS and PSR are affected by physiological stress. Both studies included young healthy male participants in which one assessed CA compliance before and after 5 minutes of endurance exercise (Pugh et al., 2018), whilst the second captured data before, during and immediately after an isometric leg-press exercise (Black et al., 2016). The results were similar between the two studies, in which the males experienced an increase in PCS and PSR above resting levels after the exercise, whilst Black et al. (2016) also identified a reduction in PCS and PSR during the double leg press compared to rest. It was suggested that the reduction in PCS and PSR during the leg press may have protected the artery from potential damage from excessive arterial stretching during the period of physiological stress (Black et al., 2016). Furthermore, the increase in PCS and PSR previously reported was thought to occur in order to buffer the elevated blood flow and alleviate pressure experienced immediately after acute physiological stress (Black et al., 2016; Pugh et al., 2018). In contrast, the results of the present study suggest that the ageing elastic artery may respond to physiological stress differently than younger cohorts, as no changes in PCS or PSR measures were observed between time points at the $P < 0.05$ level.

Although BP within each group of the present study increased during and after the isometric HG exercise, it is possible that the middle-aged females experienced lower exertions of physiological stress during the HG exercise in comparison to previous studies. For example,

an isometric double leg press exercise at both 30 % and 60 % of maximal effort was implemented by Black et al. (2016), which not only consisted of a higher load (60 % leg press vs 40 % HG) but also involved larger muscle groups compared to the present study. Consequently, the participants performing the double leg press experienced a much greater change in mean arterial pressure (MAP) during the exercise compared to the participants in the current study. Larger increases in MAP may have facilitated the declines reported in PCS and PSR within the males during the double leg-press exercise (Black et al., 2016), as engagement of collagen fibres are known to increase during periods of high pressure (Holzapfel et al., 2000). Conversely, the results of the present study contrast with previous reports as neither group experienced changes in compliance between time points. However, the exact mechanisms underlying decreases in compliance in response to physiological stress are yet to be understood.

Conventional measures of arterial stiffness increase with advancing age, which is believed to be attributed in part to a shift in the arterial wall collagen and elastin ratio (Arnett et al., 1994; Thiebaud et al., 2016). However, physically active postmenopausal females have demonstrated similar augmentation index and pulse wave velocity (PWV) values to an active premenopausal cohort, despite exhibiting higher BP (Tanaka et al., 1998). Furthermore, Shibata et al. (2018) identified that central PWV was slower in committed or competitive healthy older adults compared to their sedentary or casual exercising age-matched counterparts. β_1 was also lower in all exercise groups compared to the sedentary healthy older adults (Shibata et al., 2018). Our results contrast with previous reports as neither conventional stiffness measure differed between the active and inactive cohorts, despite differences in PCS and PSR occurring. Previous reports have also stated that CA circumferential strain imaging has a stronger association and greater sensitivity than conventional stiffness measures in identifying

differences in arterial elasticity with age (Oishi et al., 2008; Bjallmark et al., 2010). As exercise has shown to reduce arterial collagen and improve elastin content within central arteries (Koutsis et al., 1995; Fleenor et al., 2010; Gu et al., 2014), the present results suggest that PCS and PSR measures have greater sensitivity in identifying possible aerobic fitness derived differences in the intrinsic properties of CA.

6.4.2 Peripheral Vascular Measures

Our finding that brachial artery FMD did not differ between active and inactive middle-aged females contrasts with previous studies reporting higher relative FMD values in healthy active cohorts. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses have shown that long-term endurance-based exercise training benefits BA FMD when compared to sedentary aged-matched individuals (Montero et al., 2014; Campbell et al., 2019). Such improvements are a result of a healthier endothelial profile; including lower levels of oxidative stress, and the preservation of nitric oxide (Taddei et al., 2000). While the active females in the present study displayed greater aerobic capacity and performed higher levels of physical activity than the inactive group, unlike the cohorts included within the meta-analyses, they were not profiled as long-term endurance trained or athletes. Rather, our study has included ‘real-world’ study groups which are more relatable to the general population, thus providing greater ecological validity. Nevertheless, whilst long-term endurance training enhances brachial artery FMD, benefits may not occur when non-athletic middle-aged populations with lower levels of aerobic capacity are compared to their inactive counterparts.

As reductions in FMD with ageing are partly caused by rising inflammation and levels of oxidative stress (Cai and Harrison, 2000; Zhang, 2008), our results may suggest that levels of

oxidative stress and consequently, NO bioavailability may have been similar between the active and inactive groups. Nevertheless, FMD and thus, endothelium-dependent function was unaffected by regular participation in physical activity. These data could support the argument that differences in carotid artery PCS and PSR between groups may have been driven by exercise induced arterial wall adaptations, rather than differences in redox status which are observed alongside greater FMD (Taddei et al., 2000). However, as direct measures of oxidative stress or reactive oxygen species was beyond the scope of this research, it cannot be confirmed whether redox status was similar between groups.

6.4.3 Cognitive Function

Increased exercise levels and aerobic capacity have been associated with improved cognitive function in middle-aged and older adults within a number of studies (Clarkson-Smith and Hartley, 1989; Barnes et al., 2003; Aichberger et al., 2010). However, within the present study, the inactive middle-aged females performed better in a single test of executive function, and no other differences were observed between groups. Inactive participants also exhibited superior CCA flow and lower PI in comparison to the active participants, however, such variables demonstrated no association with superior executive functioning. Existing studies report improved cerebral blood flow (CBF) and brain volumes in older adults who have greater levels of CRF (Ainslie et al., 2008; Zimmerman et al., 2014), and PA (Colcombe et al., 2006) respectively. However, the results of the present study do not support these findings as ICA flow was similar between groups and $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ shared an inverse association with executive function when measured via animal fluency.

These results may suggest that increased compliance of the central vasculature may not be as critical for cognitive function as initially hypothesised, whereas other factors such as superior brain blood flow could be fundamental in the regulation of cognitive function. On the other hand, the detrimental effects of impaired vascular compliance within the inactive cohort could take longer to influence cognitive function and may not become apparent until an older age. A longitudinal assessment is therefore needed to better understand whether lower central vascular compliance is seen within the inactive middle-aged females negatively impacts cognitive health into old age.

While other studies have mostly focused on the influence of exercise on either vascular or cognitive measures, none have investigated the effects of exercise alongside carotid PCS, PSR, and cognitive function. It was initially hypothesised that increased PCS and PSR would benefit cognitive function by buffering high pressured blood flow and maintaining a constant steady flow toward the brain. However, the results suggest that enhanced distension and speed of motion of the arterial wall does not impact cognitive function in a group of physically active healthy middle-aged females. As there was a lack of differences within many of the physiological characteristics measured, the results may indicate that increased distension and arterial wall elasticity alone cannot positively affect cognition, and improvements may only be seen when in combination with other physiological factors, such as increased blood flow, improved FMD, and potential reductions in oxidative stress. However, further research is required to better understand the influence of carotid PCS and PSR variables on cognitive function.

6.4.4 Limitations

The present study contained some limitations. Firstly, as the study consisted of a non-experimental cross-sectional design, it cannot be guaranteed that the differences identified in CCA compliance and endothelial response times are exclusively due to differences in PA levels and/or aerobic fitness between the groups. Furthermore, we did not collect information about the duration of PA engagement of the active cohort. Thus, we cannot determine the duration of regular PA required to achieve the superior arterial compliance observed within the active cohort of this study.

We also did not collect measurements of CA blood flow during and immediately after the acute HG exercise. Measurement of these data and the calculation of PI during and after the HG exercise may have helped to identify whether the differences in CCA compliance between groups affected blood flow directed towards the cerebrovascular system. Additionally, whilst initially hypothesised that the vascular measures would influence cognitive performance, all vascular measures were collected separately from the cognitive assessment. Measurement of vascular variables and BP during the cognitive assessment may provide information of whether vascular dynamics influence cognitive performance when neurovascular coupling is elevated. However, the feasibility of these measurements may rely on the use of a non-verbal cognitive assessment, particularly when assessing the CA.

We have also reported that different ultrasound machines were used to collect brachial artery FMD data from the active and inactive participants. Whilst this was unavoidable due to equipment availability at the time of testing, attempts were made to

standardise ultrasound image acquisition and data collection by following a number of guidelines from the most recent FMD expert consensus publication (Thijssen et al., 2019).

Future studies should consider including a young female comparison group in an attempt to identify if active middle-aged healthy females preserve vascular measures and cognitive function, even in the absence of observed differences with inactive or fully sedentary counterparts.

6.5 Conclusion

This study is the first to report that active healthy middle-aged females possess greater CCA PCS, and PSR compared to their inactive counterparts, as assessed by ultrasound speckle tracking. However, other than higher CCA flow and PI in the inactive group, there were no other observed differences in carotid or brachial artery measures, or most cognitive outcomes between the groups. Therefore, although regular participation in PA and exercise can reduce selective areas of vascular ageing, such preservations do not always benefit cognitive function. Nonetheless, as middle-aged, and postmenopausal females are at a high risk of vascular dysfunction, regular participation in PA and exercise is encouraged to help delay the progress of central arterial ageing.

CHAPTER 7

12-WEEKS OF RESISTANCE TRAINING IMPROVES CAROTID ARTERY COMPLIANCE AND INFORMATION PROCESSING SPEED IN HEALTHY MIDDLE- AGED FEMALES

7.1 Introduction

Middle-aged and older females are vulnerable to a number of health conditions after menopause including vascular impairments, cognitive dysfunction, osteoporosis, and sarcopenia (Lindsay, 1996; Maltais et al., 2009; Brislane et al., 2020). Physical activity (PA) and exercise have been widely researched as an effective means of improving various aspects of health with ageing, however, levels of physical inactivity are currently high, with 1 in 4 adults not meeting PA guidelines for health (World Health Organisation, 2018). Moreover, PA levels are reported to decline further with advancing age and are generally lower in females compared to males across the lifespan (World Health Organisation, 2019). While current PA guidelines recommend regular participation in endurance and resistance-based exercise, a greater percentage of the population do not meet the resistance exercise recommendations (Skelton et al., 2018). Participation in resistance exercise is especially important in middle-aged and postmenopausal females as this particular weight-bearing mode of activity has been shown to protect against conditions associated with menopause, such as sarcopenia (Law et al., 2016). Thus, postmenopausal females are at an elevated risk of age-related health declines not only from ageing and reductions in oestrogen levels, but also from a lack of participation in PA. Although the health benefits of endurance exercise have been widely researched, a smaller number of studies have focused specifically on the effects of resistance exercise on healthy ageing.

Vascular health declines gradually with advancing age (Benjamin et al., 2004; Skaug et al., 2013; Laurent and Boutouyrie, 2020), and although aerobic exercise has been shown to improve various measures of central (carotid) and peripheral (brachial) vascular health, research surrounding the use of resistance exercise on vascular measures have had conflicting

results. For example, central carotid artery (CA) compliance has been negatively affected after resistance training in young individuals (Miyachi et al., 2004), yet no changes in other central arterial measures were reported in healthy middle-aged and older cohorts (Maeda et al., 2006; Casey et al., 2007; Cortez-Cooper et al., 2008). Furthermore, resistance training has also improved peripheral brachial flow-mediated dilation (FMD) in young overweight females (Olson et al., 2006), whereas healthy middle-aged and older cohorts have either experienced improvements (Anton et al., 2006), or no changes to FMD after resistance training (Casey et al., 2007). The results from previous studies could suggest that resistance training may impact arterial variables in young females to a greater extent than within their older counterparts. However, direct comparisons of the previous studies are difficult as the majority either recruited males and females separately or combined both sexes within the analysis. As few studies have investigated the effects of resistance training in middle-aged females, and as vascular health differs between the sexes (Allan et al., 1997; Garipey et al., 1998; Ando et al., 2000; Benjamin et al., 2004; Skaug et al., 2013), it is unclear whether resistance exercise can improve both central and peripheral vascular measures within an exclusively healthy middle-aged female cohort.

Declines in cognitive function are understood to occur from functional and structural changes within cerebral tissue as a result of ageing, and evidence suggests that cognitive decline may also accelerate after menopause (Georgakis et al., 2016). Again, although endurance exercise has been extensively researched as a method to reduce cognitive decline, a number of studies have also researched the effectiveness of resistance exercise in delaying cognitive impairments associated with ageing. However, results from studies including middle-aged and older individuals with no pre-existing cognitive impairments are inconsistent, as some reported that cognitive function improved (Cassilhas et al., 2007; Liu-Ambrose, 2010;

Best et al., 2015), whilst others detected no change after resistance training (Tsutsumi et al., 1997; Kimura et al., 2010; Komulainen et al., 2010). Similar to the vascular research discussed earlier, the majority of studies investigating the effects of resistance training on cognitive function have also included male and female participants within the same analysis. As cognitive adaptations from exercise training also differ between sexes (Kramer and Colcombe, 2018), it is currently difficult to understand how resistance exercise affects cognitive and vascular function in middle-aged females alone.

Currently, it is not known whether the reported peripheral and central vascular changes from resistance exercise are also associated with changes in cognitive function. Furthermore, no previous research has investigated if both, peripheral and central vascular measures improved as a result of resistance training in healthy middle-aged females and whether enhancements could translate into the improvements previously seen within cognitive function. Moreover, identifying whether central vascular compliance improves after a period of resistance training using the novel ultrasound method speckle tracking may provide a more detailed account of potential changes to the elastic arteries compared to 1-dimensional conventional methods used in previous studies (Bjallmark et al., 2010). As conventional measures of arterial stiffness may underestimate the motion and elasticity of an artery by assuming the vessel is homogeneous (Bjallmark et al., 2010), the use of speckle tracking may detect potential changes from resistance training with greater detail by assessing various segments of the arterial wall and measuring rate of change during each cardiac cycle (Bjallmark et al., 2010). Furthermore, as it has been shown that arterial compliance differs during and immediately after acute resistance exercise compared to resting conditions (Black et al., 2016), assessing arterial compliance during and after a bout of acute isometric handgrip (HG) exercise

may provide additional information regarding exercise-induced adaptations within the arterial wall.

Therefore, the aims of the study were to 1) assess the influence of 12 weeks of low-frequency, high intensity resistance training on FMD, and CA structure and blood flow of previously sedentary healthy middle-aged females; 2) identify whether the resistance training intervention could positively influence cognitive function; 3) determine whether speckle tracking-derived CA compliance measures were superior after the resistance training intervention; 4) establish whether any differences in CA compliance exist pre, during and immediately after a 3-minute handgrip (HG) exercise; and 5) identify whether potential changes in vascular and cognitive function are linked. It was hypothesised that the measured vascular variables would improve after the intervention, which may positively impact cognitive function within the middle-aged female cohort. Furthermore, it was hypothesised that the isometric HG exercise would influence CA compliance by decreasing levels during the exercise.

7.2 Methods

7.2.1 Participants

Twenty-three healthy middle-aged females who did not participate in regular structured exercise were initially recruited to participate within the present study. However, after the intervention, six participants were excluded due to failure to attend the post-intervention laboratory visit. A separate participant was also excluded as a result of poor image quality of the carotid and brachial ultrasound scans collected post intervention. Consequently, 16 participants were included in the interventional analysis (Figure 7 – 1).

Prior to participation, participants completed a consent form, Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q), and a medical questionnaire as mentioned in Chapter 4.4.3. Participants self-reported having no medical conditions, with the exception of one participant who documented exhibiting hypothyroidism and migraines. No participants documented using hormone replacement therapy (HRT) or being current smokers, and only one participant documented using cardioactive medication (Appendix 5). The inclusion of the participant taking cardioactive medication was permitted as the nature of this study was to conduct intra-participant analysis, and not inter-participant assessment. Therefore, any changes in measured variables would be relative to pre-visit data of each participant.

Figure 7 - 1. Schematic of pre and post intervention participant numbers, and reasons for exclusion.

7.2.2 Protocol

The study took place during two separate visits in February and June 2019 at the University of Wales, Trinity St David. Data were therefore collected before and after the completion of the resistance intervention. All participants arrived at the laboratory after a 3 hour fast and having not consumed alcohol or caffeine for 24 hours. All participants were also asked to refrain from strenuous PA 24 hours prior to each visit.

Details of all of the below procedures are detailed within various sections of Chapter 4. During each visit, participants were assessed for their height, mass, and body fat percentage (Sections 4.2.1 and 4.4.4). Following anthropometric assessment, a brachial artery ultrasound scan and FMD assessment was performed (Sections 4.2.3 and 4.4.7), followed by CA ultrasound scans at rest, during and immediately after a 3 minute isometric HG exercise at 40 % of maximum voluntary contraction (Sections 4.2.2, 4.4.8 and 4.4.9). Peak circumferential strain (PCS) was also corrected for pulse pressure (PP) using the following equation as reported in Yuda et al. (2011):

$$\text{Corrected PCS} = \text{PCS}/\text{PP}$$

Additionally, heart rate (HR) and blood pressure (BP) measures were collected during the CA ultrasound assessments (Section 4.4.5). After completion of the ultrasound assessments, a cognitive test battery was used to measure cognitive function (Section 4.4.11), followed by an assessment of peak aerobic capacity ($\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$) (Section 4.4.10).

7.2.3 Resistance Exercise Training Intervention

A low frequency resistance training intervention was chosen for the current study as middle-aged and older adults have been reported to require longer periods of recovery following resistance-based exercise (Hvid et al., 2014). Furthermore, it has been previously shown that older adults who perform one session of high intensity resistance exercise per week achieve the same improvements in strength as training twice per week (DiFrancisco-Donoghue et al., 2006). The intervention therefore consisted of once-weekly high-intensity resistance training sessions over 12 weeks. All visits took place at the university campus gym and were

supervised by a qualified personal trainer/gym instructor. Prior to the 12 week intervention, participants were assessed for their 1 repetition maximum effort on the Technogym leg press, chest press, and seated pull ergometers. Two sets of 10 repetitions at 50 % of maximal effort was then completed with a 2 minute rest period between to familiarise the participants with the training protocol.

The first training session consisted of a 6 minute self-paced warm-up on a cross-trainer prior to 3 sets of 10 repetitions at 65 % maximum effort during the following exercises: chest press, seated leg press, and seated chest pull. Each set was separated by 2 minutes of rest, followed by a 6 minute self-regulated cool down at the end of the session performed on any of the available cardiovascular equipment. Sessions 2 to 12 consisted of the same warm-up, cool-down, exercises, and breaks as session one, although participants were instructed to perform 3 sets of repetitions at 85 % maximum effort to fatigue within 2 minutes (typically 6 – 10 repetitions each). The intensities of each exercise were increased when participants could complete a minimum of three sets of 10 repetitions. Each session lasted approximately 30 minutes.

7.2.4 Statistical Analysis

Data were tested for normality and equal variances using a Shapiro-Wilk and Levene's test, respectively. A Student's or Wilcoxon Rank paired t-test was used to assess whether there were differences in resting measures between pre- and post-intervention visits. A two-way repeated-measures ANOVA was also used to determine whether differences in compliance, stiffness, or haemodynamic variables were affected at rest, during, and after the 3 minute isometric HG exercise within each visit. When the $P < 0.05$ threshold level was met, Tukey's

posthoc test was used to identify where differences occurred, again using the $P < 0.05$ level. Effect sizes for the main resting vascular and cognitive outcome variables were calculated as Cohen's D (d) where values of 0.2, 0.5, and 0.8 represented a small, medium, and large effect, respectively (Cohen, 1988). Additionally, the effect sizes of the main vascular variables measured pre, during, and post HG exercise was calculated as Eta squared (η^2) where values of 0.01, 0.06, and 0.14 represented a small, medium and large effect, respectively. Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients were used to assess if correlations existed between the delta (Δ) of pre to post variables. All data are displayed as means \pm standard deviations (SD), and a $P < 0.05$ level was chosen. Jamovi statistical software (version 0.9) was used to perform all statistical analysis (The jamovi project, 2019).

7.3 Results

Participant compliance was high with 50 % of participants completing all 12 weeks of training. The mean number of sessions completed throughout the whole cohort was 11.

One participant did not complete the 3 minute isometric HG exercise and therefore was not included in the carotid PCS, peak strain rate (PSR), or stiffness analysis. BP data for one participant could not be retrieved post-intervention, and therefore is not included in the haemodynamic and stiffness analysis. Additionally, one participant did not complete the FMD protocol, and a separate participant was not included in the CA blood flow analysis due to technical difficulties in extracting flow velocity data from EchoPac. Furthermore, two participants were identified as being at risk for depression, and another for low mental well-being. As a result, these three participants were removed from the cognitive test analysis.

Table 7 - 1. Participant Characteristics and Resting Vascular Variables.

Measured Variables	Pre-Intervention	Post- Intervention	P-value
Age (years)	57 ± 3	-	-
$\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ (ml.kg.min ⁻¹)	25.3 ± 5.3	26.8 ± 5.0	0.03
Age Predicted $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ (%)	74.8 ± 14.4	79.4 ± 13.8	0.03
Height (m)	1.64 ± 0.05	-	-
Mass (kg)	72.2 ± 10.6	72.1 ± 10.1	0.76
BMI (kg.m ⁻¹)	26.8 ± 3.8	26.8 ± 3.7	0.80
Body fat (%)	36.5 ± 5.9	35.6 ± 6.1	0.32
Strength Measures			
Leg Press (kg)	88.8 ± 24.0	156.9 ± 39.3	<.001
Seated Pull (kg)	55.9 ± 12.5	90.9 ± 10.5	<.001
Chest Press (kg)	23.4 ± 4.6	36.3 ± 5.7	<.001
Haemodynamics			
SBP (mmHg)	144 ± 19	140 ± 14	0.32
DBP (mmHg)	74 ± 13	75 ± 8	0.78
MAP (mmHg)	96 ± 14	100 ± 10	0.25
PP (mmHg)	69 ± 14	66 ± 9	0.19
Common Carotid Artery			
Maximum Longitudinal Diameter (cm)	0.60 ± 0.05	0.60 ± 0.05	0.53

Minimum Longitudinal Diameter (cm)	0.55 ± 0.05	0.55 ± 0.05	0.64
Posterior intima-media thickness (mm)	0.63 ± 0.10	0.64 ± 0.10	0.33
Blood Flow (ml.min ⁻¹)	491.4 ± 73.8	430.0 ± 94.2	0.008
Pulsatility Index	1.73 ± 0.31	1.89 ± 0.30	0.029
Peak Circumferential Strain (%)	4.67 ± 0.87	4.87 ± 1.42	0.64
Corrected Peak Circumferential Strain (%)	0.07 ± 0.02	0.08 ± 0.03	0.517
Peak Strain Rate (s ⁻¹)	0.365 ± 0.078	0.394 ± 0.101	0.38
Corrected Peak Strain Rate (s ⁻¹)	0.005 ± 0.002	0.006 ± 0.002	0.20
Peak Recoil Rate (s ⁻¹)	-0.149 ± 0.041	-0.151 ± 0.035	0.72
Pulse Transit Time (ms)	49.9 ± 10.4	43.2 ± 6.0	0.03
β ₁ (mm ² ·kPa ⁻¹)	8.01 ± 2.92	8.36 ± 2.45	0.80
E _p (kPa)	112.0 ± 40.6	117.0 ± 38.2	0.80

Internal Carotid Artery

Maximum longitudinal diameter (cm)	0.44 ± 0.06	0.43 ± 0.08	0.89
Blood Flow (ml.min ⁻¹)	375.3 ± 96.6	375.9 ± 155.1	0.87
Pulsatility Index	1.2 ± 0.3	1.2 ± 0.3	0.65

Brachial Artery

Baseline diameter (cm)	0.34 ± 0.05	0.34 ± 0.05	0.92
FMD (%)	6.4 ± 3.5	6.2 ± 3.2	0.88
Shear Normalised FMD x10 ⁻⁵ (%)	4.9 ± 10.9	8.2 ± 7.6	0.44
FMD Time to peak (s)	140.0 ± 75.1	88.6 ± 72.4	0.02

Data are presented as means ± standard deviations. P-values at the P < 0.05 level are displayed in bold. $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$, peak aerobic capacity; BMI, body mass index; HR, heart rate; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; MAP, mean arterial pressure; PP, pulse pressure; E_p, Peterson's Elastic Modulus; FMD, flow-mediated dilation.

Table 7 - 2. Cognitive Test Battery Results.

Cognitive Test	Pre-Intervention	Post Intervention	P-value
Trail Making			
Trail A (s)	25.6 ± 6.5	23.3 ± 6.0	0.047
Trail B (s)	62.6 ± 21.9	56.5 ± 20.3	0.27
Stroop Test			
Stroop 1 (s)	4.4 ± 0.7	4.1 ± 0.6	0.01
Stroop 2 (s)	4.6 ± 0.7	4.3 ± 0.7	0.19
Stroop 3 (s)	6.2 ± 1.2	5.6 ± 1.0	0.03
Stroop 4 (s)	8.7 ± 3.9	10.9 ± 3.9	0.20
Verbal Fluency			
Animals (n)	19 ± 3	19 ± 4	0.36
Words beginning with 's' (n)	10 ± 4	12 ± 3	0.48
Digit Span			
Forwards (n)	7 ± 1	6 ± 1	0.12
Backwards (n)	4 ± 2	5 ± 1	0.23

Data for n = 13 participants is presented as means ± standard deviations, and P-values at the P < 0.05 level are displayed in bold.

7.3.1 Participant Characteristics

The characteristics of the participants before and after the 12 week resistance training intervention are displayed in Table 7 - 1. Anthropometric and haemodynamic variables were unchanged between visits (P > 0.05), although improvements in $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ and a number of functional strength tests were recorded (P < 0.05; Table 7 - 1).

7.3.2 Vascular Measures at Rest

Although no differences in structural measures of the CA were identified after the intervention, mean resting common CA (CCA) blood flow declined by an average of 61.4 ml.min⁻¹ after the resistance training intervention ($P = 0.008$; Cohen's $d = 0.84$). CCA pulsatility index (PI) increased after the intervention ($P = 0.029$; Cohen's $d = -0.12$), whereas internal CA (ICA) PI remained unaffected ($P = 0.650$; Cohen's $d = -0.63$). PCS, PSR, and conventional stiffness measures were unaffected at rest between visits while pulse transit time (PTT) was faster by 6.7ms ($P = 0.033$, Cohen's $d = 0.61$). Furthermore, while FMD did not differ between visits ($P = 0.890$), a reduction in time to peak brachial artery diameter by 51.4s was identified during the FMD assessment after the intervention ($P = 0.018$; Cohen's $d = 0.7$). The correlation analysis revealed an association between greater improvements in chest press performance with slower PTT at rest ($r = 0.651$, $P = 0.009$).

7.3.3 Vascular Measures During and After Handgrip Exercise

All haemodynamic variables increased at the $P < 0.05$ level as a result of the isometric HG exercise ($P < 0.001$), and PP and systolic BP (SBP) remained increased immediately after the HG exercise ($P < 0.001$). Diastolic BP (DBP) ($P = 0.015$) and MAP ($P = 0.021$) was reduced at the $P < 0.05$ level immediately after completing the isometric HG exercise when compared to rest. PP was also reduced after the resistance training intervention ($P = 0.018$; $\eta^2 = 0.06$; Table 7 - 3).

A main effect for time identified that PCS was reduced at the $P < 0.05$ level during ($P < 0.001$) and immediately after the isometric HG exercise ($P = 0.020$) in comparison to resting

conditions. PCS also increased at the $P < 0.05$ level after the resistance training intervention as indicated by a main effect for visit ($P = 0.018$; $\eta^2 = 0.08$; Table 7 - 3; Figure 7 - 2). Similar results were also reported for PCS corrected for PP as both a main effect for time and visit was identified. Corrected PCS was also reduced during and immediately after the isometric HG exercise (both $P < 0.001$; $\eta^2 = 0.11$), however corrected PCS was also increased after the intervention ($P = 0.009$; $\eta^2 = 0.07$; Table 7 - 3; Figure 7 - 2).

PSR and peak recoil rate did not demonstrate main effects for time or visit, although interaction effects were observed ($P < 0.001$ and 0.04 , respectively), and are highlighted within Table 7 - 3. These identify that post-intervention PSR was faster immediately before ($P = 0.019$) and during the isometric HG exercise ($P = 0.003$) when compared with pre-intervention PSR. However, despite there being an interaction effect for peak recoil rate ($P = 0.038$), no interaction was identified from the Tukey's posthoc test ($P > 0.05$). Reductions in PTT were observed after the resistance training intervention ($P = 0.025$; $\eta^2 = 0.09$), however, β_1 and E_p was unaffected by the resistance training intervention and the isometric HG induced physiological stress experienced during each visit ($P > 0.05$).

Figure 7 - 2. Peak circumferential strain (%; A) and peak strain rate (s^{-1} ; B) at rest, during, and immediately after the 3 minute handgrip (HG) exercise measured before and after the 12

week resistance training intervention. Data are presented as individual data points with means \pm standard deviations. Between time-point differences at the $P < 0.05$ level are presented as an asterisk (**, $P < 0.001$ between rest and during handgrip (HG); *, $P < 0.05$ between rest and post HG), and a main effect of visit is presented as a cross (\dagger , $P < 0.05$) in Figure 7 - A. Time * visit interactions at the $P < 0.05$ level are identified by the following symbols in Figure 7 - B: ¶, $P < 0.05$; #, $P < 0.010$; §, $P < 0.001$.

7.3.4 Cognitive Assessment

Time taken to complete the Trail A, Stroop 1, and Stroop 3 tests decreased by 2.3s ($P = 0.047$; $d = 0.61$), 0.38s ($P = 0.014$; $d = 0.8$), and 0.65s ($P = 0.031$; $d = 0.68$), respectively after the resistance intervention (Table 7 - 2; Figure 7 - 3). Greater changes in $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ between each visit was associated smaller improvements in Stroop 1 performance ($r = 0.606$, $P = 0.028$). Associations were also present between smaller improvements in Stroop 3 performance with slower PTT during the isometric HG ($r = 0.806$, $P = 0.002$), and greater increases in seated chest pull performance ($r = 0.642$, $P = 0.018$). ΔPSR measured post isometric HG was also directly correlated with $\Delta\text{Trail A}$ performance ($r = 0.583$, $P = 0.046$). Additionally, a positive correlation was present between smaller improvements in Trail A performance and greater increases in corrected PCS during ($r = 0.657$, $P = 0.020$) and after the isometric HG exercise ($r = 0.674$, $P = 0.016$).

Figure 7 - 3. Mean (\pm SD) and individual completion times (s) of the cognitive tests Stroop 1 (A), Stroop 3 (B), and Trail A (C) of participants pre and post 12 weeks of resistance training. An asterisk (*) represents a difference at the $P < 0.05$ level.

Table 7 - 3. Haemodynamic and Common Carotid Artery Variables

Variable	Pre-Intervention			Post-Intervention			Main Effect P-Values		
	Rest	Handgrip	Post-Handgrip	Rest	Handgrip	Post-Handgrip	Time	Visit	Interaction (Time * Visit)
Haemodynamics									
HR (b.min ⁻¹)	64 ± 8	69 ± 8 *	68 ± 8 *	63 ± 8*	66 ± 11*	63 ± 7 †	<0.001	0.091	<0.001
SBP (mmHg)	144 ± 19	165 ± 26	159 ± 26	140 ± 14	158 ± 21	148 ± 18	<0.001	0.118	0.189
DBP (mmHg)	74 ± 13	84 ± 17	80 ± 17	75 ± 8	83 ± 11	76 ± 11	<0.001	0.800	0.224
MAP (mmHg)	96 ± 14	111 ± 19 *	106 ± 19 *	100 ± 10	108 ± 14 #	100 ± 13	<0.001	0.708	0.013
PP (mmHg)	69 ± 14	81 ± 16	79 ± 15	66 ± 9	75 ± 13	72 ± 11	<0.001	0.018	0.135
Common Carotid Artery									
Peak Circumferential Strain (%)	4.67 ± 0.87	3.62 ± 1.40	3.78 ± 1.29	4.87 ± 1.42	4.48 ± 1.17	4.87 ± 1.24	<0.001	0.012	0.091
Corrected Peak Circumferential Strain	0.07 ± 0.02	0.05 ± 0.02	0.05 ± 0.02	0.08 ± 0.03	0.06 ± 0.02	0.07 ± 0.02	<0.001	0.009	0.092
Peak Strain Rate (s ⁻¹)	0.365 ± 0.078	0.294 ± 0.109 ¶#	0.329 ± 0.089	0.280 ± 0.107*¶#	0.394 ± 0.101	0.371 ± 0.095	0.230	0.190	<0.001
Peak recoil rate (s ⁻¹)	-0.149 ± 0.041	-0.136 ± 0.045	-0.147 ± 0.029	-0.125 ± 0.039	-0.151 ± 0.035	-0.147 ± 0.037	0.510	0.550	0.04

Pulse Transit Time (ms)	49.9 ± 10.4	56.2 ± 18.1	47.3 ± 11.6	43.2 ± 6.4	43.1 ± 11.0	41.7 ± 8.9	0.235	0.025	0.212
Maximum SAX Diameter (cm)	0.61 ± 0.06	0.61 ± 0.06	0.61 ± 0.06	0.60 ± 0.05	0.61 ± 0.06	0.61 ± 0.06	0.016	0.860	0.423
Minimum SAX Diameter (cm)	0.56 ± 0.05	0.57 ± 0.06	0.56 ± 0.06	0.56 ± 0.05	0.57 ± 0.05	0.56 ± 0.06	0.007	0.971	0.749

Conventional

Stiffness Indices

β ₁ stiffness index (mm ² .kPa ⁻¹)	8.01 ± 2.92	8.94 ± 2.78	9.34 ± 3.83	8.36 ± 2.45	9.2 ± 3.97	7.9 ± 2.23	0.519	0.304	0.360
E _p (kPa)	112 ± 40.6	139 ± 41	142 ± 64.8	117 ± 38.2	145 ± 73.9	113 ± 34.1	0.079	0.075	0.273

Data are presented as means ± standard deviations at rest, during, and immediately after the 3 minute isometric hand-grip exercise. P-values for the main effects of time point (rest, during the 3 minute HG and post HG), visit (pre to post-intervention), and a time * visit interaction are reported, and P-values < 0.05 are displayed in bold. The following symbols identify where time * visit interaction occurred (P<0.05) with (visit and time): * = Pre-visit at rest; † = Pre-visit during HG exercise; ¶ = post-visit during HG exercise; and # = post visit immediately after the HG exercise. HR,

heart rate; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; MAP, mean arterial pressure; PP, pulse pressure; SAX, short axis; E_p , Peterson's Elastic Modulus.

7.4 Discussion

The aim of the study was to determine whether 12 weeks of once-weekly high-intensity resistance training could improve measures of central (carotid) and peripheral (brachial) vascular health, in addition to cognitive function in previously inactive, middle-aged healthy females. The results of the study identify that central vascular compliance was improved at the $P < 0.05$ level after resistance training as PCS and certain measurements of PSR increased post-intervention, although only when measured alongside acute periods of physiological stress. Whilst peripheral endothelial function measured via FMD was not affected by the 12 week intervention, the responsiveness of the brachial endothelium to shear stress improved at the $P < 0.05$ level. Furthermore, various assessments of information processing speed also improved after the intervention. Consequently, 12 weeks of low frequency resistance training appears to have had the capacity to improve certain vascular and cognitive variables in previously inactive healthy middle-aged females.

Despite numerous reports investigating the effects of resistance training on vascular measures and cognitive function in a wide range of individuals, to our knowledge, no previous study has assessed both central and peripheral vascular function alongside cognitive function within the same cohort. As females experience an escalating risk of vascular decline and possibly also cognitive decline after menopause (Benjamin et al., 2004; Georgakis et al., 2016), it is important to assess both systems within the same cohort. Understanding whether physiological and neuropsychological adaptations from resistance training work together or as independent systems may provide valuable information regarding the mechanisms behind improvements in vascular and cognitive health from resistance exercise. Previously, evidence for any interdependence of the two systems has been inferred from different studies which have

demonstrated correlations between improved cerebral blood flow (CBF), cognitive function, and vascular stiffness (Chapman et al., 2013; Okamoto et al., 2019). However, the lack of association between vascular and cognitive variables improved at the $P < 0.05$ level within the current study suggest that 12 weeks of low-frequency high-intensity resistance training may exert its effects on central vascular and cognitive functions via separate mechanisms.

7.4.1 Central Vascular Measures

The present study is also the first to investigate the impact of resistance training on the central vascular compliance of healthy middle-aged females using the novel ultrasound speckle tracking method. Previously, speckle tracking has demonstrated the ability to differentiate between the compliance of the CCA in young and older adults (Bjallmark et al., 2010), healthy and unhealthy adults (Park et al., 2012), and between moderate with high levels of cardiorespiratory fitness (Pugh et al., 2018). As greater levels of PCS and PSR are thought to result from superior elastic properties of the arterial wall (Bjallmark et al., 2010), improvements in PCS and PSR measures seen in the present study could indicate that low-frequency resistance training may improve arterial compliance via improvements in the intrinsic profile of the CCA walls in middle-aged females.

Previous reports have stated that conventional measures of arterial compliance were unaffected after 13 weeks of resistance training in middle-aged and older males and females (Cortez-Cooper et al., 2008), yet others reported that compliance was reduced in chronic resistance-trained middle-aged males compared to their sedentary counterparts (Miyachi et al., 2003). Whilst local carotid compliance improved at the $P < 0.05$ level after the resistance training in the present study, reductions in PTT at rest and during the isometric HG exercise

may indicate that regional stiffness increased after resistance training. However, a lack of change in most conventional stiffness measures within the present study is in agreement with previous studies which reported no changes in arterial stiffness via pulse wave velocity PWV in middle-aged adults, including postmenopausal females after moderate and high-intensity resistance training (Miyachi et al., 2003; Rossow et al., 2014). Therefore, the differences in findings between the present study and previous reports could result from the different effects which resistance training may have on arterial mechanics between the sexes, in addition to the differences in training protocols.

Additionally, the discrepancies observed between arterial compliance and stiffness within the present study could be attributed to the different techniques used to measure arterial these variables. For example, ultrasound speckle tracking has been shown to possess greater sensitivity than conventional measures when assessing differences in CCA function with age (Bjallmark et al., 2010), and with aerobic capacity levels in healthy middle-aged females (Chapter 6). Furthermore, the present study has also highlighted the sensitivity of speckle tracking for identifying improvements in arterial compliance when measured alongside an acute period of physiological stress. As many previous studies investigating the influence of resistance training on arterial stiffness and compliance have only done so at rest, such differences in methodology may also explain the differences between the results of this study and others.

Whilst the mechanisms underlying improvements in PCS and PSR are not yet fully understood, previous reports using animal models have examined the intrinsic properties of the arterial wall after different training interventions. Although arterial stiffness and collagen

content decline in mice after 10 - 14 weeks of endurance training (Fleenor et al., 2010), 14 weeks of resistance training has shown improve aortic elastic lamellae content, whilst having no effect on collagen content in elderly ovariectomised rats (Lima et al., 2012). Although not directly translatable to humans, it is possible that similar adaptations in the CCA of the participants in the current study may have caused improvements in compliance from increases in elastin after resistance training. Additionally, the unchanged local stiffness variables also observed after the 12 week intervention could have been due to a lack of changes in collagen content between visits.

As PP has been shown to be an important determinant of arterial PCS (Yuda et al., 2011), PCS was also corrected for this variable as PP levels were lower at the $P < 0.05$ level in the post-intervention trial during and after the isometric HG exercise. However, the differences in corrected and uncorrected PCS values and PSR in the present study were only apparent when measured alongside an acute period of physiological stress, and not when measured during resting conditions only. These findings contrast with a recent study involving young males with moderate and high levels of cardiorespiratory fitness (CRF), where differences in compliance were observed between groups both at rest and after an acute bout of endurance exercise (Pugh et al., 2018). Moreover, a separate cohort of young males demonstrated reductions in PCS and PSR during, and increases immediately after a double leg press exercise at 30 % and 60 % 1RM, respectively, possibly as a protective and buffering response, respectively (Black et al., 2016).

The present study demonstrates similarities with Black et al., as PCS, PSR and corrected PCS declined during the 3-minute isometric HG exercise. Although uncertain,

increases in haemodynamic pressures induced by acute exercise may enhance CCA collagen fibre recruitment (Wagenseil and Mecham, 2009), thus resulting in decreased compliance which is believed to prevent damage caused by excessive arterial expansion (Black et al., 2016). Though reductions in physiological stress were similar to findings reported by Black et al. (2016) and may also demonstrate a protective response to increased physiological stress, compliance levels remained lower than resting levels immediately after completion of the isometric HG exercise. These results could suggest that the CCA of healthy middle-aged females may take longer to recover from acute exercise than younger male cohorts who demonstrate elevations in PCS immediately after acute physiological stress. Nonetheless, the elevated CCA compliance observed after 12 weeks of resistance training may help to protect distal vasculature in the middle-aged females during exercise by augmenting buffering capacity via the Windkessel effect (Safar and Struijker-Boudier, 2010). Additionally, the lower post-intervention PP observed during the same isometric HG exercise may also indicate that 12 weeks of resistance training elicited vascular adaptations within the healthy middle-aged females.

In comparison to compliance, the central arterial structure was unaffected by the 12 week resistance intervention. Despite a limited array of research focusing on the impact of resistance training on vascular structure, 6 months of Olympic style lifting reduced intima-media thickness (IMT) in young males (Spence et al., 2013). However, IMT was unaffected after 1 year of traditional resistance training in overweight premenopausal participants (Olson et al., 2006), and also after 8 months of concentric versus eccentric resistance training in young females (Okamoto et al., 2006). As CCA IMT is a predictor vascular risk (Lorenz et al., 2007), these data may suggest that resistance training may not influence carotid IMT, and thus vascular risk, at least in females. However, a previous study has shown that lower PCS values

are associated with increased Framingham risk score (Park et al., 2012). Although associations between PCS and Framingham risk score were within a patient population, superior PCS observed within the present study could suggest that resistance training may reduce CV risk, despite no differences in IMT. Furthermore, data from the present study could highlight that arterial compliance, as assessed by PCS, may be more susceptible to change than CCA IMT after 12 weeks of low frequency resistance training in healthy middle-aged females. However, further research would be required to increase the confidence in these findings.

7.4.2 Peripheral Vascular Measures

Similar to central arterial structure, resistance training appeared to have no effect on peripheral endothelial function via brachial artery FMD in the healthy middle-aged cohort. The results of the current study agree with other resistance training studies which found no improvements in young (McGowan et al., 2006b), older mixed-sex (O'Brien et al., 2020), and exclusively postmenopausal females (Casey et al., 2007), although increases in FMD have been reported in young, hypertensive, and overweight cohorts (McGowan et al., 2006b; Olson et al., 2006; Spence et al., 2013). The cause of this variation in FMD response to resistance training is not clear. However, the oxidative environment of the endothelium may be influenced differently by either the duration of resistance training completed, or by the sex of the participants. For example, 12 weeks of twice-weekly resistance training increased nitric oxide (NO) levels in older males (Maeda et al., 2006), whereas 8 weeks of thrice-weekly resistance training failed to elevate NO in older females (Ribeiro et al., 2017). As increases in NO are known to enhance FMD by signalling relaxation of the tunica media smooth muscle cells (Ignarro et al., 1982), these data could suggest that resistance training may not improve NO bioavailability in middle-aged females, thus possibly helping to explain the lack of

improvement in FMD in the present study and in postmenopausal females elsewhere (Casey et al., 2007).

Despite this, the time to peak FMD was shorter post-training at the $P < 0.05$ level. Faster time to peak brachial artery diameters have been identified in young versus older (Black et al., 2008), and healthy compared to unhealthy populations (Fernandes et al., 2014). Factors such as impaired endothelium enzyme availability and reductions in the responsiveness of smooth muscle cells have been believed to increase time to peak diameter in old versus young females. Although speculative, resistance training may have improved similar factors which in turn, reduced time to peak brachial artery diameter. If correct, these data could demonstrate that resistance training may improve certain aspects of brachial artery health after resistance training, although not specifically endothelial-dependent vasodilation. However, such findings should be interpreted with caution as the time to peak diameter has been described as a highly heterogenous measurement when measured in healthy young and middle-aged individuals (Liuni et al., 2010). For example, time to peak FMD has ranged from 17 – 143s and 30 – 143s in healthy young and middle-aged females, respectively (Liuni et al., 2010). These data therefore decrease the confidence in using this measure as an outcome variable alone.

7.4.3 Cognitive Function

In terms of cognitive function, resistance training appeared to influence exclusively information processing speed. Research surrounding the benefits of resistance training on cognitive function is conflicting, with a meta-analysis of cognitively healthy adults reporting that there was little evidence that resistance exercise alone improved cognitive function (Kelly et al., 2014). However, two recent meta-analyses identified that resistance training in adults

aged mainly > 50 years improved cognitive function regardless of baseline cognitive status, particularly within the domain of executive function (Northey et al., 2018; Landrigan et al., 2019). Furthermore, it was suggested that resistance training was most effective for cognitive function in older males and females when at least moderate intensities were performed (Northey et al., 2018), which is supported by the present study. Previous studies have mostly demonstrated improvements in cognitive function when resistance interventions longer than 12 weeks have been completed (Cassilhas et al., 2007; Liu-Ambrose, 2010; Tsai et al., 2015), with the exception of a 6 and 10 week intervention in a mixed-sex cohort (Fragala et al., 2014; Eckardt et al., 2020). However, as it is understood that cognitive function within each sex can be affected differently by exercise training (Barha et al., 2017b), the present study is the first to show that once-weekly resistance training for 12 weeks can have a positive impact on information processing speed in exclusively healthy middle-aged females. Moreover, a dose-response relationship between resistance training and cognitive improvements has been reported in older adults (Li et al., 2018). Therefore, it could be possible that further improvements in cognitive function may have occurred in the present study if either a greater duration or frequency of training was performed.

There are limited explanations from this analysis to elucidate the reasons which resistance training may have improved cognitive function. ICA flow has been previously shown to associate with CBF (Soustiel et al., 2003), and was measured to determine whether CRF increased CBF, as associations between the two have been previously reported (Ainslie et al., 2008; Zimmerman et al., 2014). However, despite reductions in CCA flow post-training, a similar ICA flow profile existed between time points. Secondly, as the cerebrovascular system is susceptible to damage from highly pulsatile blood flow (O'Rourke and Safar, 2005), it was hypothesised that elevations in arterial compliance may improve cerebrovascular health

by buffering high pulsatile blood flow through the CCA via the Windkessel effect (Safar and Struijker-Boudier, 2010). However, increases in uncorrected PCS were not associated with improved cognitive function, whereas slower PSR were correlated with improved Trail A performance. Moreover, greater changes in corrected PCS during and after the isometric HG exercise was associated with smaller improvements in Trail A performance. However, as lower PCS and PSR have been observed in older and less physically fit cohorts (Bjallmark et al., 2010; Pugh et al., 2018; Rosenberg et al., 2018), the findings from the current study may suggest that a greater and faster rate of CA compliance may not be required for improvements in cognitive function to occur. Similarly, reductions in regional stiffness measure PTT were also associated with improved processing speed within the Stroop 3 test. Therefore, whilst resistance-training induced increases in regional stiffness are disadvantageous for arterial health, for unknown reasons, cognitive health may benefit from such adaptations.

Aside from vascular moderators, there are an array of other variables also known to change with resistance training including improved white matter integrity and volume, reduced whole brain volume, and increased insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) levels (Cassilhas et al., 2007; Liu-Ambrose, 2010; Best et al., 2015; Bolandzadeh et al., 2015; Tsai et al., 2015; Herold et al., 2019). Such adaptations may be responsible for the improvements in cognitive function by providing a superior cerebrovascular environment, in addition to augmenting neurogenesis and angiogenesis (Carro et al., 2001; Trejo et al., 2001; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2004). As previously shown that white matter volume, integrity, and increased IGF-1 are associated with information processing speed (Aleman et al., 1999; Gunning-Dixon and Raz, 2000; Kerchner et al., 2012; Magistro et al., 2015), although speculative, potential resistance training-induced improvements in cerebral white matter and/or IGF-1 may have facilitated the improvements seen in cognitive function. However, as these particular measures were not accounted for in

the present study, it cannot be confirmed whether such variables were responsible for the reported cognitive improvements.

7.4.1 Limitations

This study contained various limitations. The absence of an inactive control group reduces the certainty that observed improvements in carotid compliance and information processing speed occurred from resistance training alone. Also, participation within additional activity alongside the intervention was not prohibited. Therefore, it could be possible that participants may have benefited from another activity other than the prescribed resistance-training intervention if additional activity was performed.

Similar to the limitations expressed in Chapter 6, the present study also did not collect CA blood flow measurements during and immediately after the acute HG exercise. As similar benefits in PCS and PSR were observed in Chapter 6, measurements of CA blood flow during physiological stress may have also helped identify whether any blood flow or PI adaptations occurred after training. As there were no changes in ICA PI after the intervention when measured at rest, measuring ICA PI during the HG exercise would identify whether improved CCA compliance during physiological stress would translate to reduced pulsatility of blood directed to the delicate cerebral vessels. Furthermore, another limitation similar to Chapter 6 includes not assessing cognitive function during periods of physiological stress-induced increases in CA compliance. Future research should consider including these particular variables to better understand the influence of resistance exercise on the interaction between vascular and cognitive measures during increased neurovascular demand.

7.5 Conclusion

The present study has identified that 12 weeks of once-weekly high-intensity resistance training successfully improved central arterial compliance and information processing speed in previously inactive healthy middle-aged females. However, the improved cognitive function does not appear to be affected by the improvement seen in CA compliance. The results suggest that resistance exercise improves central vascular compliance and cognitive function separately in middle-aged females.

CHAPTER 8

GENERAL DISCUSSION

8.1 Introduction

The aims of this thesis were to investigate the influence of physical activity (PA) and exercise on both, vascular measures and cognitive function within healthy older adults. This thesis also investigated whether links were present between potential exercise-induced adaptations in vascular measures and cognitive function. In order to assess the benefits of exercise on vascular measures, cognitive function, and potential links between the two, a series of investigations were conducted. Within Study 1, a meta-analysis was performed to assess the influence of long and short-term endurance training on brachial artery endothelial function within healthy older adults, as assessed via flow mediated dilation (FMD). A meta-regression analysis was also performed to assess whether a relationship between increasing age and endothelial benefit from long-term endurance training existed. Study 2 assessed brachial artery FMD, carotid structure and blood flow, and cognitive function via the Cambridge Autonomic Neuropsychological Automated Test Battery (CANTAB) in healthy older masters athletes and their inactive counterparts, in addition to a young healthy inactive control group. During Study 3, brachial artery FMD and carotid structure, blood flow and compliance were assessed alongside a traditional cognitive assessment within healthy active and inactive middle-aged females. Finally, Study 4 assessed the effects of 12 weeks of low-frequency high-intensity resistance training within previously inactive healthy middle-aged females using the same vascular and cognitive measures as Study 3.

8.2 Summary of Findings

8.2.1 Study 1 - *Long-Term Aerobic Exercise Improves Vascular Function into Old Age: A Systematic Review, Meta-Analysis and Meta Regression of Observational and Interventional Studies*

The aims of Study 1 included collating studies which 1) assessed the influence of long-term endurance training on brachial artery endothelial function via FMD in long-term endurance-trained healthy older adults compared to their sedentary counterparts; and 2) assessed the influence of short-term endurance training on brachial artery FMD within previously sedentary healthy older adults.

Hypothesis 1 = Accepted

- Long-term trained healthy older adults exhibit superior FMD compared to their sedentary counterparts

Hypothesis 2 = Rejected

- Short-term endurance training did not improve FMD in previously sedentary healthy older adults

FMD was higher within the long-term endurance trained older adults at the $P < 0.05$ level compared to their sedentary counterparts. Moreover, the meta-regression analysis identified that increasing age from 62 to 75 years did not impact the extent of brachial artery endothelial benefit exhibited by the endurance-trained cohorts. However, studies that had assessed endothelial independent vasodilation had collectively identified no differences between the long-term trained versus sedentary cohorts. Moreover, no differences in brachial artery

diameter were observed between long-term trained and inactive or recreationally active groups, suggesting that no structural adaptations limited the FMD response to hyperaemic shear. Therefore, these results show that superior FMD was due to better endothelial vasodilatory capacity and not smooth muscle function within the long-term trained individuals

However, short-term endurance training ranging from 2 to 12 weeks failed to improve FMD in previously sedentary healthy older adults at the $P < 0.05$ level. Furthermore, studies that had assessed endothelial independent vasodilation had collectively identified no differences after short endurance training interventions. Consequently, FMD nor smooth muscle cell function improved after short-term endurance training. However, brachial artery baseline diameter was larger after short-term training compared to baseline values. It has been reported that short term periods of exercise training may cause increases in FMD after a couple of weeks before structural adaptations occur (Green et al., 2017). As baseline brachial artery diameter influences FMD (Thijssen et al., 2008; Green et al., 2013; Atkinson, 2014; Atkinson and Batterham, 2015), increases in diameter from structural adaptations may explain the lack of improvement in FMD observed after interventions ranging 2 to 12 weeks. Therefore, the commencement of endurance training may have initially improved FMD prior to the onset of structural adaptations possibly as a result of elevations in intraluminal shear stress.

8.2.2 Study 2 – Absence of Vascular and Cognitive Benefit from Long-Term Endurance Exercise Compared to Recreational Exercise in Healthy Older Adults

The aims of Study 2 included 1) assessing brachial artery endothelial and carotid structure and blood flow between healthy older masters athletes and recreationally active controls; 2) identifying potential associations between vascular and cognitive measures, and 3)

measuring vascular and cognitive variables within healthy older masters athletes and inactive cohorts compared to a young inactive control group.

Hypothesis 1 = Rejected

- Healthy masters athletes did not demonstrate superior vascular variables or cognitive function compared to their age-matched recreationally active counterparts

Hypothesis 2 = Rejected

- Vascular structure, blood flow or FMD was not positively linked with cognitive performance within the older groups

Hypothesis 3 = Rejected

- Young inactive individuals performed better in some, but not all cognitive domains compared to healthy older adults, and did not demonstrate superior measures of vascular health

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Despite higher $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ in the masters athletes compared to their recreationally active counterparts, there were no differences in brachial artery endothelial, common carotid artery (CCA), or internal carotid artery (ICA) structure and blood flow between the groups. Such findings contrast with previous studies reporting higher CCA, ICA, middle cerebral artery blood flow, and velocity in regularly active older adults (Azhim et al., 2007b; Ainslie et al., 2008; Braz et al., 2017). Additionally, at the $P < 0.05$ level there was no differences in $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ between the masters athletes and young inactive group, yet ICA flow was lower in the masters athletes. However, although there were no differences in the majority of cognitive domains assessed between the two older groups, the recreationally active older group performed better

during a test of memory compared to the masters athletes. Such results were not as hypothesised as cognitive function has typically been shown to benefit from regular exercise training (Spirduso, 1975; Tseng et al., 2013; Zhao et al., 2016).

As expected, both older cohorts exhibited larger CCA intima-media thickness (IMT) compared to the young group. A larger CCA IMT in the older cohort was expected as it is commonly observed due to age-associated increases in arterial IMT (Allan et al., 1997; Garipey et al., 1998; Ando et al., 2000; Depairon et al., 2000; Homma et al., 2001; Brislane et al., 2020). Such findings therefore demonstrate that age-related increases in CCA IMT cannot be avoided by long-term participation in endurance exercise. However, a lack of differences in CCA blood flow, and blood pressure existed between the young and older groups; a finding which contrasts with previous studies showing reductions in CCA and middle- cerebral artery blood flow with increasing age (Schmidt-Trucksäss et al., 1999; Azhim et al., 2007b; Brislane et al., 2020). Additionally, brachial artery FMD did not differ between the young and two older cohorts; a finding which was also not expected due to the ageing associated endothelial impairment widely reported (Eskurza et al., 2005; Franzoni et al., 2005; Yavuz et al., 2008; Black et al., 2009; Walker et al., 2009; Pierce et al., 2011a; DeVan et al., 2013; Brislane et al., 2020). Furthermore, as expected, the young group performed better within a number of the cognitive domains compared to the masters athletes or both older groups including executive functioning, memory and reaction time.

Overall, Study 2 demonstrated little vascular decline with ageing, and no protection from long-term participation in endurance-based exercise training. Additionally, whilst some cognitive decline was evident from ageing, masters athletes did not exhibit protection from

cognitive decline, and actually performed worse in one assessment of memory compared to their recreationally active age-matched counterparts. Moreover, as long-term exercise training did not augment vascular or cognitive health compared to the recreationally active cohorts, no associations could be made between the physiological and neuropsychological variables. Therefore, there is a lack of evidence to demonstrate whether differences in cognitive performance, as reported elsewhere, are influenced by measures of vascular health.

8.2.3 Study 3 – *Habitual Exercise Protects Carotid Artery Compliance, but not Cognitive Function in Healthy Middle-Aged Females: A Cross-Sectional Approach*

The aims of Study 3 were to 1) investigate whether physically active healthy middle-aged females exhibited superior vascular FMD, structure, blood flow, and cognitive function compared to their age-matched inactive counterparts; 2) determine whether CCA speckle tracking-derived compliance measures were superior in the active versus the inactive cohort; 3) establish whether differences in CCA strain exist pre, during and immediately after a 3-minute isometric hand-grip (HG) exercise; and 4) assess whether associations were present between vascular and cognitive variables.

Hypothesis 1 = Rejected

- The active females did not demonstrate any benefits in cognitive performance, FMD, carotid structure, or ICA blood flow compared to the inactive cohort.

Hypothesis 2 = Accepted

- The active cohort demonstrated better CCA compliance as assessed via speckle-tracking compared to the inactive group.

Hypothesis 3 = Rejected

- Differences in CCA strain did not occur between measurements taken pre, during and immediately after a 3-minute isometric HG exercise

Hypothesis 4 = Rejected

- No associations were observed between vascular and cognitive variables.

Within this study, it was found that participation in regular PA positively influenced peak circumferential strain (PCS) and peak strain rate (PSR) of the CCA; a finding supported by a recent study conducted in healthy middle-aged and older trained and untrained adults (Talbot et al., 2020). However, other than the CCA pulsatility index (PI) and blood flow which was higher in the inactive cohort, no other structural or functional measures of the central or peripheral vascular system were observed. Similar to study 2, such results were not expected as regular PA and exercise has previously been shown to benefit arterial blood flow and velocity in older adults (Azhim et al., 2007b; Ainslie et al., 2008; Braz et al., 2017), and FMD based on the results from Study 1 (Campbell et al., 2019). Additionally, it was found that measures of PCS and PSR, but not conventional stiffness measures, shared positive associations with $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$.

Cognitive function was largely unaffected by regular participation in exercise, and the inactive group displayed superior executive function in a single cognitive test compared to the active group. Again, similar to Study 2, such results were not as hypothesised as previous work has reported benefits from regular PA and exercise training on various domains of cognitive functioning (Spiriduso, 1975; Tseng et al., 2013; Zhao et al., 2016). Furthermore, the results also demonstrated that superior executive function measured via animal fluency shared an

inverse association with $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$, and no association with any of the vascular variables which demonstrated differences between groups at the $P < 0.05$ level.

Overall, Study 3 demonstrated that regularly active middle-aged females demonstrate superior CCA compliance when compared to their inactive counterparts, although only when measured using novel speckle tracking technology. These data could suggest that the speckle-tracking method of assessment could be a more sensitive method of measuring CCA compliance; a finding which has also been reported previously (Bjallmark et al., 2010; Pugh et al., 2018). However, central vascular structure and peripheral FMD appeared unaffected by such lifestyle choices. Furthermore, participation in regular exercise had no positive influence on various cognitive domains and possibly impaired the ability to complete executive functioning tasks compared to those who are inactive. Finally, no links between vascular and cognitive variables existed within this cohort.

8.2.4 Study 4 – 12-weeks of Resistance Training Improves Carotid Artery Compliance and Information Processing Speed in Healthy Middle-Aged Females

The aims of study 4 were to 1) assess the influence of 12 weeks of low-frequency, high-intensity resistance training on FMD, and the vascular structure and blood flow of previously sedentary healthy middle-aged females; 2) identify whether the resistance training intervention could positively influence cognitive function; 3) determine whether CCA speckle tracking-derived compliance measures were superior after the resistance training intervention; 4) establish whether differences in CCA strain exist pre, during and immediately after a 3-minute isometric HG exercise; and 5) identify whether potential changes in vascular and cognitive function are linked.

Hypothesis 1 = Rejected

- 12 weeks of resistance training did not improve FMD or carotid structure, or CCA blood flow

Hypothesis 2 = Accepted

- The resistance training intervention improved a number of tests of processing speed (Stroop 1, Stroop 3 and Trails A)

Hypothesis 3 = Accepted

- Speckle-tracking derived CCA compliance was improved after the 12-week resistance training intervention

Hypothesis 4 = Accepted

- The isometric HG exercise demonstrated differences in CCA compliance between groups which were absent during resting conditions

Hypothesis 5 = Rejected

- No associations were observed between the improvements in vascular variables and cognitive function after the 12 week intervention

Twelve weeks of resistance training improved measures of upper and lower body strength and $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ in the previously sedentary healthy middle-aged cohort. In addition, time to peak brachial artery FMD, CCA blood flow, and pulse transit time (PTT) were all reduced at the $P < 0.05$ level after the 12 week intervention. Whilst reduced time to peak diameter has been believed to represent reductions in the endothelial ageing process (Black et al., 2008),

faster PTT may indicate that resistance training also negatively influences regional arterial stiffness, which has been reported in young males previously (Miyachi, 2013). However, resistance training did not affect brachial artery FMD, carotid structure, CCA PCS, PSR, or conventional CCA stiffness measures during resting conditions. Whilst measures of PCS, PSR and PCS corrected for PP did not improve when assessed exclusively at rest, they were all higher at the $P < 0.05$ level after the 12 week intervention only when measured immediately before, during and after the acute HG exercise.

The time taken to complete information processing speed tasks during certain Stroop and Trails tests were also reduced at the $P < 0.05$ level after the 12 week intervention. A previous meta-analysis supports the use of resistance training to be most effective at improving executive function, memory and working memory in middle-aged and older adults (Northey et al., 2018). Whilst the results from Study 4 do not support the improvements in executive function and memory domains, it does demonstrate that low-frequency high-intensity resistance training can positively influence information processing speed. However, the results found that the improvements in vascular compliance seen after the 12 week intervention was not associated with the improvements in cognitive performance. Therefore, whilst initially hypothesised that superior exercise-mediated vascular compliance may influence cognitive function similar to intra- and extra-cranial examples reported previously (Brown et al., 2010; Chapman et al., 2013; Okamoto et al., 2019), no such associations were present between the improvements in carotid compliance and information processing speed after the resistance exercise intervention. Rather, greater declines in PTT, and smaller improvements in corrected PCS and PSR was associated with enhanced information processing speed.

The results of Study 4 therefore suggest that 12 weeks of once-weekly high-intensity resistance training has a selective effect on improving vascular and cognitive health, and thus may reduce or delay certain age associated physiological and neuropsychological impairments. Furthermore, although decreases in PTT demonstrates increased regional arterial stiffness after the training, elevations in PCS and PSR represent improvements in local arterial compliance, although only when measured alongside and immediately after a short period of isometric exercise. Consequently, the vascular benefits of resistance training may not necessarily be observed exclusively at rest. However, exercise-induced improvements in vascular compliance do not appear to influence enhancements in cognition within healthy middle-aged females

8.3 Importance of Findings and Future Directions

8.3.1 Vascular

The current thesis set out to investigate the influence of long and short-term exercise training on the vascular and cognitive function within healthy middle-aged and older adults. The approach which was taken within Study 1 (Chapter 3) collated existing research which had assessed the effects of long and short-term endurance training on brachial artery FMD in healthy older adults. The results emphasise the importance of participating in regular endurance-based exercise throughout the lifespan to slow the progression of age-associated endothelial decline, and thus the development of further endothelial dysfunction. Moreover, the results from the meta-regression identified that increasing age did not reduce the benefits of endurance-training on FMD, as a similar benefit was observed by those aged between 62 and 75 years compared to their healthy age-matched sedentary counterparts. Thus, these findings may further encourage the continuation of exercise participation to or beyond the 7th

decade of life as the vascular benefits will remain similar to those experienced by individuals' decades younger. Whilst the positive effect of endurance exercise on FMD has been understood for some time, Study 1 was the first meta-analysis to investigate the influence of long-term endurance training in exclusively healthy older adults. Consequently, the results demonstrate the beneficial effect of long-term exercise on endothelial ageing exclusively, rather than in combination with pre-existing medical conditions which have been studied previously (Ashor et al., 2015; Early et al., 2017).

The results of this thesis may also suggest that similar benefits in FMD and possibly other vascular and cognitive variables may also occur from unstructured PA as various measures in Studies 2 and 3 were, at the $P < 0.05$ level, not different between the trained and untrained groups. These results therefore differ from those in Study 1 in which the sedentary group exhibited lower FMD, having mostly not engaged in regular PA for at least the previous two years. Whilst further investigation may be required in this area, these results could emphasise the importance of participating in any form of PA, in addition to reducing sedentary behaviour to aid in preserving vascular and possibly cognitive health from age-related declines.

Although there is less evidence for improvements in FMD from short term endurance training, a large degree of heterogeneity was present between the included endurance-based training studies where interventions ranged from low to high-intensity, and durations of 2 to 12 weeks. Moreover, there are few short-term endurance training studies that have assessed FMD in healthy other adults, and consequently, only 4 interventional studies were included within the meta-analysis. Therefore, a greater number of short-term studies are required to identify whether different combinations of training specifics such as the intensity, frequency

and duration, may be required to facilitate improvements in FMD. Moreover, as FMD can respond quickly to exercise training (Tinken et al., 2008), interventional studies should also have frequent data collection timepoints to ensure that early improvements in FMD are detected before potential arterial structural adaptations occur.

Whilst regular exercise and short-term resistance training may not have improved brachial artery FMD, CCA compliance was superior at the $P < 0.05$ level from habitual PA and the short-term high-intensity resistance training. Studies 3 and 4 are the first to assess the influence of exercise on carotid compliance using the novel ultrasound speckle tracking technique in exclusively healthy middle-aged females. Consequently, these studies contain an insight into the extent of exercise-induced arterial benefits using a novel technique that is more closely related to $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ than conventional measures of arterial stiffness, and thus may be more sensitive at detecting changes in compliance in individuals with differences in cardiorespiratory fitness (CRF) levels. These findings agree with previous reports which highlight the superior levels of sensitivity exhibited by carotid speckle tracking compared to conventional based arterial stiffness measurements (Bjallmark et al., 2010).

The findings from Study 4 contrast with previous resistance training studies in middle-aged and older adults which state that resistance training has a negative effect, or no impact on arterial compliance (Miyachi et al., 2003; Cortez-Cooper et al., 2008). However, in comparison to Study 3 where superior CCA compliance was observed both in the presence and absence of the isometric HG exercise, the exercise-induced improvements in CCA compliance were not evident without the HG exercise after the 12 week resistance intervention in Study 4. As the majority of previous reports in older adults have assessed vascular measures at rest only,

it is possible that such approaches may not reveal the full effects of short-term resistance training which appear to improve compliance during and after periods of physiological stress. Therefore, future studies may benefit from assessing vascular variables whilst incorporating acute periods of physiological stress as this approach may provide a greater volume of information regarding arterial health.

Whilst this thesis focused on the effect of both, short and long-term exercise on a range of vascular variables, there are a greater number of studies which have looked at the influence of long-term PA and exercise on vascular health in ageing. Nevertheless, it is apparent from the literature and this thesis that duration of exercise (i.e., life-long/habitual versus a short-term intervention) can have an influence on peripheral arterial function (FMD). For example, the time course of endothelial adaptation to enhance shear stress is believed to occur relatively quickly after the onset of regular exercise training, shortly followed by structural adaptation to increase arterial diameter (Green et al., 2017). This therefore influences the time course by which changes in endothelial-dependent dilation and thus, endothelial function, can be viewed via the FMD method. Whilst the results from Study 1 conform with the argument that short-term exercise may not affect FMD due to increases in arterial diameter, conversely, short-term resistance training within Study 4 did not influence FMD or baseline brachial artery diameter. These data may suggest that factors including exercise type (endurance versus resistance), and training specifics (intensity and frequency), likely also play a role in endothelial and structural adaptations of peripheral arteries, as outlined below.

FMD has also been shown to have a dose response effect with exercise intensity, with a meta-analysis reporting a 1% increase in FMD with every 10% increase in relative exercise

intensity (Ashor et al., 2015). Moreover, exercise frequency was also shown to positively associate with FMD improvements within the same study. Key differences between existing literature and the current thesis include the health status of the participants undergoing exercise training, as individuals who exhibit cardiovascular or metabolic conditions may have greater scope for improvement following an intervention versus healthy cohorts. As the meta-analysis mentioned above included cohorts with various medical conditions, future meta-analyses should consider adopting meta-regression analyses on exclusively healthy cohorts to investigate whether a similar effect is seen out-with a clinical population.

Research surrounding the influence of long-and short-term exercise on central arterial structure and function is also extensive, although a number of discrepancies exist between the literature and in the findings of this thesis. For example, previous research has reported that engaging in regular exercise and exhibiting superior CRF reduces IMT (Lakka et al., 2001; Hamer et al., 2010; Kang and Ko, 2019), however, this was not observed in this thesis. A possible explanation could be attributed to study design; whilst this thesis employed a cross-sectional and short-term exercise approach, longitudinal studies have reported lower IMT in those with higher CRF and objectively measured PA (Lakka et al., 2001; Hamer et al., 2010; Kang and Ko, 2019). Furthermore, reports also suggest a dose response relationship exists between the level of exercise intensity performed and reductions in IMT advancement, though again when measured during a longitudinal study (Nordstrom et al., 2003). Similar to the findings in this thesis, cross-sectional approaches and interventional studies have been less likely to identify differences in IMT between exercisers versus non-exercisers (Moreau et al., 2002; Tanaka et al., 2002; Sandrock et al., 2008), or after short (8 – 15 weeks) or slightly longer-term (24 weeks) endurance or resistance exercise interventions (Tanaka et al., 2002; Thijssen et al., 2007; Park, 2016). However, those which have reported reductions in IMT

after similar durations of lower-intensity exercise training are limited to displays of statistical significance rather than potential clinical significance as only small decreases in IMT of 0.01mm were reported (Park et al., 2015, 2017a). Consequently, long-term exercise and superior CRF may reduce the rate of IMT accumulation, yet this likely reflects deceleration rather than inhibiting thickening, thus potentially explaining why changes in IMT after short-term research are rarely reported in the literature.

Changes in conventional stiffness measures could also be explained by training specifics. For example, within Chapters 6 and 7, conventional stiffness measures appeared unchanged by regular activity, or by low-frequency yet high intensity resistance training. However, recent findings provide reason to believe that a dose response relationship existed for arterial stiffness, whereby vigorous exercise > 5 days per week was sufficient to elicit vascular adaptation, but not > 3 days per week Tanaka et al. (2000). Thus, low-frequency short-term exercise, or potentially regular exercise performed below this ‘threshold’ may explain why conventional arterial stiffness measures appeared unaffected throughout this thesis. Furthermore, central arterial stiffness, as assessed via conventional stiffness measures, may be less sensitive to changes in arterial function when engagement in ‘casual exercise’ has occurred over shorter periods of time (i.e., < 2 years) (Tanaka et al. 2000) in comparison with ‘life-long’ exercisers (Shibata et al. 2018). Such findings may help to explain why conventional stiffness measures were unaffected by short term exercise in Chapter 7 (low frequency), or potentially not ‘life-long’ engagement in regular activity in Chapter 6. On the other hand, previous research may have been restricted to the measurement of conventional stiffness alone as novel approaches including ultrasound speckle-tracking have repeatedly been reported to exhibit greater sensitivity when measuring arterial function, as shown by this thesis and previous reports (Bjallmark et al., 2010; Pugh et al., 2018).

Whilst limited research currently exists investigating the influence of long-term exercise on arterial compliance assessed via ultrasound speckle-tracking in older adults, those which have agree with the findings in this thesis, whereby exercise trained healthy older adults exhibit superior compliance (Talbot et al., 2020). However, to our knowledge, other than Chapter 7, no other study has investigated the influence of short-term exercise training on arterial compliance using ultrasound speckle-tracking. As this particular method has the potential to identify small differences in compliance otherwise not observed via conventional measures, further research in this area is warranted.

Organisations such as the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM) have recommended incorporating resistance-based exercises in weekly PA guidelines for health (World Health Organisation, 2011; Chodzko-Zajko, 2014). It is emphasised that resistance-based exercise should be completed by older adults in order to maintain and improve strength for mobility, reducing the risk of falls, and ultimately maintaining independence (Skelton and Mavroieidi, 2018). Therefore, the findings from this thesis may also help to emphasise the importance of incorporating resistance training into PA and exercise programmes for ageing populations, not only for the improvement of arterial compliance and cognitive function but for independence and overall well-being.

Previous studies have also assessed the influence of endurance, resistance, and combined training on carotid stiffness in healthy middle-aged and older adults (Ashor et al., 2014). However, to our knowledge, no previous study has used carotid speckle-tracking to assess the influence of different modes of exercise either at rest or during physiological stress,

which together may reveal greater detail regarding cardiac mechanics. As current PA guidelines recommend regular participation in endurance and resistance-based exercise (Chief Medical Officers, United Kingdom, 2019), future research may benefit from assessing the influence of long- or short-term concurrent training on CCA compliance using the novel methodological approaches incorporated into Chapters 6 and 7 of this thesis. These data could help better identify the influence that recommended PA guidelines for older adults would have on CCA compliance, and whether such PA would be equally or perhaps more beneficial to arterial health than endurance or resistance exercise training alone. Consequently, using the speckle-tracking technique and incorporating physiological stress into such studies may provide greater detail than previously observed in similar studies involving healthy middle-aged and older adults.

8.3.2 Cognitive Function

The cognitive results seen in Studies 2 and 3 were not as expected, as they suggest that long-term endurance training and regular PA participation may not benefit cognitive performance compared to untrained cohorts. Nevertheless, the results of these studies could also suggest that low levels of unstructured PA and activity accumulated through daily routine performed by the untrained groups may also reduce age-associated cognitive decline, as seen previously (Ruscheweyh et al., 2011). However, previous reports have also identified poorer cognitive performance from untrained individuals of similar PA levels reported in Studies 2 and 3 when compared to masters athletes, such as those within Study 2 (Tseng et al., 2013; Zhao et al., 2016). As there are discrepancies between the current results and previous data, further research with larger sample sizes and the use of a greater range of neuropsychological tests may be required to fully understand the influence of habitual endurance exercise on the cognitive function within healthy ageing.

Whilst results of this thesis may not demonstrate cognitive benefits from long-term endurance activity, it does provide evidence that 12 weeks of once-weekly high-intensity resistance exercise can improve information processing speed at the $P < 0.05$ level within healthy middle-aged females. Such information is valuable as one; less research exists concerning the influence of resistance exercise on cognitive function compared to endurance-based exercise studies, and two; much of this existing research in middle-aged and older individuals contains mixed-sex cohorts. As cognitive decline may accelerate after menopause (Georgakis et al., 2016), and cognitive adaptations from exercise training differ between sexes (Kramer and Colcombe, 2018), these results provide insight into exclusive female-specific cognitive protection from resistance training.

These results, therefore, demonstrate that resistance training involving high efforts only once per week may help to reduce or delay the impairments in information processing speed which is known to become affected with advancing age. Although one of the simplest cognitive domains, impairments in information processing speed can affect overall cognitive performance (Harvey, 2019). Though further research is required within this area, greater durations of resistance training could have demonstrated improvements in other cognitive functions assessed. Nonetheless, high efforts of resistance training performed once weekly is an effective means of reducing the age-related cognitive decline within healthy middle-aged females who are at an increased risk of cognitive decline after menopause.

8.3.3 Vascular and Cognitive Interaction

This thesis also provides the first research which has investigated the influence of exercise on peripheral and central vascular measures alongside cognition within healthy middle-aged and older adults. Whilst research has assessed vascular and cognitive separately, less have assessed vascular and cognitive variables together to assess potential links between the two. However, the studies within this thesis do not provide evidence that improvements in cognitive function were mediated by concurrent improvements in vascular variables. Although there is a lack of research within this area, previous research has shown associations between an improved cognitive function with increases in CBF and decreased regional arterial stiffness after moderate to high-intensity endurance training (Chapman et al., 2013; Okamoto et al., 2019). Positive associations have also been observed between brachial artery FMD and cerebrovascular reactivity with cognitive performance in healthy middle-aged endurance-trained and untrained individuals (Tarumi et al., 2015). Furthermore, superior intracranial vascular conductance was a predictor of cognitive function in postmenopausal females with high and low levels of CRF (Brown et al., 2010). Therefore, there is evidence to suggest that superior cognitive function observed as a result of exercise may be linked with better vascular health.

However, there is limited evidence to show that long-term endurance exercise, regular PA, or short-term resistance training cause improvements in cognitive function from exercise-induced improvements in extracranial vascular health in healthy middle-aged and older adults. Investigating the potential associations between physiological and neuropsychological variables with ageing and exercise is important in order to understand how to best delay ageing-associated detriments within health and well-being. A greater body of research is still required

before we can fully comprehend the influence which PA and exercise may have in delaying the ageing process within vascular and cognitive health.

8.4 Limitations

It is important to note that the research within this thesis has a number of limitations. Specific limitations relating to each study have been outlined within each experimental chapter. However, similar limitations between chapters will be discussed within this section.

This thesis aimed to investigate the influence of long and short-term exercise on vascular measures and cognitive function within healthy ageing. In order to assess the influence of exercise on ageing, a number of studies were conducted which included specifically healthy middle-aged and older adults. Rigorous inclusion and exclusion criteria were used to increase confidence that the individuals recruited were free from common age-related conditions and the use of agents known to alleviate the ageing process. Thus, it is with confidence that the individuals included within Studies 1 - 4 represent a healthy cohort whereby the true effects of exercise on health could be assessed. However, as age is one of the biggest risk factors for cardiovascular impairments, middle-aged and older adults become vulnerable to age-associated vascular impairments – particularly those who are sedentary. Whilst attempts were made to recruit healthy sedentary older adults within Studies 2 and 3, many of the sedentary individuals who were initially recruited did not meet the inclusion criteria deeming them as ‘healthy’. Consequently, the majority of participants included within Studies 2 - 4 were not sedentary, but rather participated in low volumes of unstructured PA. Although speculative, greater differences in physical and neuropsychological function may have

occurred in Studies 2 - 4 if the untrained participants were fully sedentary, similar to those contained within Study 1.

Additionally, small sample sizes within Studies 2 - 4 may have reduced the power of the studies, and thus may have also contributed to the lack of change or differences in a number of the physical or neuropsychological variables within the studies. Furthermore, although 10 studies were included in the long-term endurance training section of the meta-analysis in Study 1, only 4 studies met the inclusion criteria for assessing short-term endurance training on FMD. Although the included studies identified no improvement in FMD, a large degree of heterogeneity was present likely due to differences in intervention specifics between studies. Therefore, whilst the results state that short-term endurance training does not influence FMD, a meta-analysis should be performed again when a greater number of interventional studies which meet similar criteria become available.

Although Studies 2 and 4 used the same ultrasound machine for vascular imaging for all included participants, two separate ultrasound devices and linear transducers were used to assess brachial artery FMD of the active and inactive cohorts within Study 3. Despite the FMD data reported in Study 3 being similar to results reported in Study 2, it could be possible that variations in image quality and acquisition may have influenced the results of the brachial artery FMD examination. Additionally, images of the brachial artery were not assessed alongside an electrocardiogram (ECG) trace. As measurements of brachial artery diameter can fluctuate throughout a cardiac cycle, there is the possibility that FMD values may have been affected by continuous measurement of diameters at non-standardised stages of each cardiac cycle within Studies 2 – 4 (Harris et al., 2010). Furthermore, whilst participants in Studies 2 - 4 were asked to refrain from strenuous exercise and caffeine for a period of time prior to brachial artery FMD measurements, they were not asked to adapt their diets or refrain from the

consumption of nutritional supplements. As it is recommended that participants undergoing FMD assessment should refrain from the consumption of ascorbic acid and high fat or rich nitrate diets (Harris et al., 2010; Greyling et al., 2016; Thijssen et al., 2019), stricter dietary instructions for participants may have increased confidence in the FMD values reported in this thesis.

Another limitation within this thesis includes not screening older participants for dementia prior to the assessment of cognitive function. However, although no screening test for dementia was used, participants at risk of depression and low mental well-being were excluded from the cognitive analysis within Studies 3 and 4, as such individuals are believed to be at a higher risk of cognitive impairment (Lim et al., 2013; Rock et al., 2014). Additionally, years of education was used as a covariate when assessing the cognitive data within Study 2, as this particular variable may also influence cognitive function. Although these steps were taken to improve the quality of cognitive test results, it cannot be confirmed that all participants were free from cognitive impairment or dementia. Thus, it could be possible that the cognitive results may have been influenced by the presence of a neuropsychological condition.

Finally, as participants within Studies 1 and 2 consisted mainly of males, the results of these specific reports may not generalise to healthy older females. Conversely, the results of Studies 3 and 4 may not generalise to males as exclusively healthy middle-aged females were included. In addition, all participants were healthy and with the exception of one female within Study 4, none were using cardiovascular medication or hormone replacement therapy (HRT).

Therefore, the results of the study again may not generalise to populations using medications commonly used in ageing such as hypertensive medication and HRT.

8.5 Conclusion

A number of conclusions have been made from the results of the four experimental chapters within this thesis. Firstly, long-term endurance training is effective for slowing the age-associated decline in FMD of the brachial artery when compared directly with age-matched healthy sedentary adults. Moreover, the benefit of long-term endurance training is experienced equally across the age range in healthy older adults, meaning that increases in age do not reduce the vascular benefits of maintaining physically active. However, it is possible that small volumes of unstructured PA may also preserve FMD in healthy ageing similarly to levels experienced by age-matched regular exercisers and masters athletes. Nonetheless, short-term endurance and resistance exercise do not appear to improve brachial artery FMD within healthy middle-aged and older adults.

Participation in regular PA without being highly endurance-trained is sufficient to induce superior carotid compliance in healthy middle-aged females compared to untrained individuals. In addition, 12 weeks of high-intensity low-frequency resistance training improved carotid compliance in the previously inactive middle-aged females. Though improvements in compliance demonstrate superior vascular health after the 12 week resistance training intervention, such benefits were only present when measured alongside an acute bout of physiological stress, and not during resting conditions alone.

Whilst long-term endurance training and regular PA did not positively influence cognitive function, 12 weeks of resistance training can benefit information processing speed. However, exercise-induced enhancements in information processing speed do not appear to be facilitated by simultaneous improvements in vascular compliance.

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APPENDICES

Chapter 5

Appendix 1

	Young	Older Trained	Older Untrained
Medication	Citalopram (n=1)	Salbutamol (n=1) Allopurinol (n=1) Thyroxine (n=1)	Finasteride (n=2) Tamsulosin (n=1) ADCAL-D3 (n=2) Thyroxine (n=1) Alendronic Acid (n=1) Tamoxifen (n=1)

List of medications reported by participants included in Chapter 5.

Appendix 2

	Young	Older Trained	Older Untrained
Nature of Exercise	No exercise (n=1) Recreational (n=8)	Recreational (n=1) Systematic (n=12)	Recreational (n=14)
Endurance Exercise (hours/week)	1.4 ± 1.6 *	8.2 ± 2.8	0.8 ± 1.1 *
Resistance Exercise (hours/week)	0.6 ± 0.7	1.2 ± 1.2	0.8 ± 0.9
Main Sport/Event		Athletics (n=4) Running (n=6) Cycling (n=2) Cycling and Running (n=1)	

Self-reported exercise behaviours of participants included in Chapter 5. The presence of a difference from the older trained group at the $P < 0.05$ level is identified with an asterisk (*; ANOVA $P < 0.05$).

Appendix 3

Sport/Event	Participation Level	Hours Per Week	Years Consistent	Other Sports
Athletics	Club and national	10	47	Hillwalking
Athletics	Club and national	10	15	Swimming
Athletics	Club, national and international	9	33	No
Athletics	International	9	49	Golf
Running	Club (previously international)	7	40	Triathlon
Running	National (previously international)	6	30	Mountaineering and fishing
Running	Club	8	35	Gym and swimming
Running	Club	5	20	Cycling
Running	Recreational, club, national and international	15	10	No
Running	Club, national and international	7	50	No
Cycling	National (previously international)	-	9	Swimming
Cycling	Recreational and club	16	10	No

Cycling and running	Club	-	10	No
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Sports, participation level, and duration of training of the exercise trained older adults included within Chapter 5.

Chapter 6

Appendix 4

	Active	Inactive
Medication	Antidepressant (unspecified) (n=1) Fexofenadine 120mg (n=1) Alendronic Acid 70mg/week (n=1) Adcal 1500mg (n=1) Sumatriptan 6mg 'as required' (n=1)	Hay fever medication (n=1) Citalopram 10mg (n=1) Pizotofen 0.5mg (n=1) Levothyroxine 100mg (n=1)
Medical Condition	Osteoarthritis (n=1) Osteoporosis (n=1)	Hypothyroidism (n=1) Migraine (n=1)

List of medications and medical conditions reported by the active and inactive middle-aged females included within Chapter 6.

Chapter 7

Appendix 5.

Inactive	
Medication	Hayfever medication (n=1) Citalopram 10mg (n=1) Pizotofen 0.5mg (n=1) Levothyroxine 100mg (n=1) Blood Pressure Medication (n=1)
Medical Condition	Hypothyroidism (n=1) Migraine (n=1)

List of medications and medical conditions reported by the inactive middle-aged females included within Chapter 7.